

> DESIRE6G <

D2.3: Techno-economic Analysis and Data Set Definition

HEU 6G SNS JU Project

Grant No. 101096466

Co-funded by
the European Union

Document properties

Document number	D2.3
Document title	Techno-economic Analysis and Data Set Definition
Work Package	2
Editors	Marc Ruiz (UPC)
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Internal reviewers	1. Stephen Parker (ACC) 2. Miguel A. Carnero Fernández (TID)
External reviewers	1. Michele Gucciardo (NEC) 2. Merve Saimler (EBY)
Dissemination level	PU (Public)
Status of the document	Final version
Version	2.0
File name	D2.3_Techno_Economic_Analysis_and_Data_Set_Definition
Contractual delivery date	June 30 th 2025
Delivery date	June 30 th 2025

Document history

Revision	Date	Issued by	Description
V0.1	14/05/2025	Marc Ruiz	Initial draft
V1.0	01/06/2025	Marc Ruiz	First Version
V1.2	13/06/2025	Marc Ruiz	Version for Internal Review
V1.5	20/06/2025	Marc Ruiz	Version for External Review
V2.0	30/06/2025	Marc Ruiz	Final Version

Abstract

This deliverable details the methodologies developed in DESIRE6G to identify and define datasets. It includes a tailored methodology especially designed for demo use cases, as well as an alternative methodology for those datasets generated as the results of different DESIRE6G components. Moreover, the deliverable presents several techno-economic studies oriented to show the benefits in terms of cost reduction (related to CAPEX and OPEX) and expected revenue/income increase by adopting DESIRE6G innovations to improve current benchmarking infrastructures and technologies. Regarding these techno-economic analysis contents, the deliverable presents some chapters where infrastructure, traffic, and service analysis coming from real operator measurements and data are provided as starting reference point. Then, studies organized by individual chapters are focused on one or more DESIRE6G architectural components, with the objective to evaluate the potential benefits in both qualitative and quantitative terms.

Keywords

Datasets, techno-economic studies, DESIRE6G architecture, CAPEX/OPEX, revenues

Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101096466.

DESIRE6G is supported by the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking.

This report reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning
AR/ VR/ XR	Augmented Reality/ Virtual Reality/ Extended Reality
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
CFG	Control Flow Guard
CODP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CU	Centralized Unit
CUDA	Compute Unified Device Architecture
D6G	DESIRE6G
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End-to-End
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broad Band
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUI	Graphic Users Interface
HD	High Definition
HH	Heavy hitter
HL	Hierarchical Level
HLIR	High-Level Intermediate Representation
HQoS	Hierarchical Quality of Service
HW	Hardware
IML	Infrastructure Management Layer
INT	In-band Network Telemetry
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicators

L2fwd	L2 Forwarding
LHQoS	Link-by-link Hierarchical Quality of Service
MAS	Multi Agent System
MIMO	Multiple-Input and Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLFO	Machine Learning Function Orchestrator
NF	Network Function
NF-DP	Network Function Data Plane
NHQoS	Network-wide Hierarchical Quality of Service
NIC	Network Interface Card
NN	Neural Network
NS	Network Service
O-RAN	Open RAN
P4	Programming Protocol-Independent Packet Processors
PDP	Programmable Data Plane
PM	Performance Monitoring
PoC	Proof of Concept
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RTT	Round-Trip Time
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SECaaS	Security as a Service
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SMO	Service and Management Orchestrator
SNS IA	Smart Networks and Services Infrastructure Association
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SO	Service Orchestrator
SW	Software
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UC	Use Case

UE	User Equipment
uRLLC	Ultra-High Reliability & Low Latency Communications
VNF	Virtual Network Function

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope

Deliverable D2.3 summarizes the techno-economic analyses performed in Work Package 2. It starts from the preliminary DESIRE6G system architecture described in MS2.2, updated in D2.2, and includes CAPEX/OPEX studies for DESIRE6G solution to support services for the selected use cases. Additionally, D2.3 includes the definition of the data sets collected, together with the scenarios of interest (MS2.3).

This deliverable is the third one of a series of WP2 deliverables, namely, D2.1 (Definition of Use Cases, Service Requirements and KPIs/KVIs) and D2.2 (Functional Architecture Definition).

1.2 Executive Summary

This deliverable represents a major milestone in the DESIRE6G project by providing a comprehensive framework for both dataset definition and techno-economic analyses in support of 6G network evolution. The document is structured in two main parts:

Part I: Dataset Definition (Chapters 2-4)

The first part focuses on the methodology and structure for dataset definition, critical to evaluating 6G services and components. Two complementary methodologies are proposed:

- **Use Case (UC)-oriented:** Tailored for specific 6G use cases like Augmented/Virtual Reality (AR/VR) and Digital Twin (DT), this approach defines datasets through a multi-phase process, including the definition of service graphs and data flows, and the mapping of those data flows to DESIRE6G architectural components.
- **Component-oriented:** Designed for reusable 6G functionalities such as ML-based Elastic Scaling or SLA Decomposition, this method outlines datasets from the perspective of component interactions across various services.

Each use case and component are dissected through detailed phases, identifying data producers, consumers, and the structure and characteristics of relevant datasets. This work, that extends the initial

contributions in MS2.3, forms the foundation for consistent data collection and performance evaluation across DESIRE6G's technological solutions.

The contents in this deliverable about datasets are strictly related with definition and characterization aspects. For data collection aspects, as well as for details about open accessible datasets (links and data availability), please refer to the contents in D5.1 [1].

Part II: Techno-Economic Studies (Chapters 5-16)

The second part presents a series of techno-economic analyses, offering qualitative and quantitative evaluations of how DESIRE6G technologies contribute to cost savings, efficiency, and performance enhancement. This part contains:

- **Reference network scenarios:** establish baseline scenarios using Telefónica's existing 4G/5G NSA deployments and define an equivalent Open 5G Standalone (SA) baseline for comparative purposes.
- **Service Analysis:** detailed traffic analysis and service class identification from real operator measurements provide the benchmarking for performance evaluation.
- **Qualitative and Quantitative Evaluations:** several studies are explained and carried out with the objective of showing benefits of DESIRE6G for several purposes:
 - 6G Service Characterization: identifies representative services, defines KPIs/KVIs, and compares human-based and AI-based service classification approaches.
 - Efficient Resource Utilization: explores methods for enhancing resource efficiency across DESIRE6G scenarios, enabling cost reduction and increasing cost savings.
 - Enhanced Heavy-Hitter Offload: quantifies energy savings and load balancing improvements by offloading large flows using programmable data plane technology.
 - Hierarchical QoS: demonstrates capacity savings through network-wide QoS policies and bandwidth prioritization, reducing congestion and improving service delivery.
 - AI Model Acceleration: evaluates the energy efficiency benefits of hardware-accelerated inference and training for AI models used in 6G services.
 - OPEX Reduction via MAS: shows how multi-agent systems for autonomous flow routing reduce power consumption and operational costs in aggregation and core networks.

- Remote Attestation & Integrity Verification: assesses the financial and operational impact of blockchain-based runtime integrity mechanisms for securing service payloads.
- Intent-Based SLA Assurance: illustrates reduced service activation time and revenue loss using IBN frameworks for SLA translation and enforcement in enterprise and public use cases.
- ML-Assisted RIS Configuration: validates improvements in RIS configuration latency and data rate stability using neural network (NN) models trained via federated learning.

Together, the two parts of this deliverable offer a well-integrated framework that supports the deployment and economic viability of advanced 6G services. The methodologies and analyses presented here serve as a critical reference for subsequent technical development and experimental validation within the DESIRE6G project.

1.3 Document organization

The remainder of the document is structured as follows:

- Chapters 2 to 4 define the dataset identification methodologies and describe datasets associated with specific use cases and components.
- Chapters 5 and 6 present the reference network architectures and traffic/service characterization used as input for techno-economic studies.
- Chapter 7 approaches the expected benefits in qualitative terms of each of the main components and systems belonging to the different layers of the high-level DESIRE6G architecture.
- Chapters 8 to 16 each present an individual techno-economic study, covering different services and technologies in DESIRE6G.
- Chapter 17 concludes the document, summarizing key outcomes and lessons learned.

2. Dataset identification methodology

2.1 Introduction

This section explains the proposed methodology that allows identifying datasets to be generated and collected within the framework of this project. Besides its use within WP2 scope, the methodology aims to provide a basic procedure and guidelines for handling the data collection that will be performed in WP5 for those selected demo use cases.

To adapt to the different cases considered in this project, we designed two alternative methodologies:

- **UC-oriented:** when the primary focus is a 6G use case (UC) or service supported by D6G infrastructure.
- **Component-oriented:** when the primary focus is a D6G component/functionality used by multiple UCs and services at the same time.

The following sections detail the different phases of both alternatives.

2.2 UC-oriented methodology

This methodology consists of four main sequential phases that are described below:

- **Phase 1** - Describe the set of services/components S that define the UC. Note that a single UC might contain several services. This phase consists of enumerating and briefly describing the different services and/or components that are involved in a given UC. The description might introduce, in plain words and/or high level, schematic figures, the characteristics and the main aspects of the components in order to identify the service graph and data components that support it (which happens in next phase).
- **Phase 2** - For each service/component $s \in S$, create the service graph $G(s)$ and identify data components. In this phase, the definition of the service graph(s) for each of the previously identified components needs to be done prior to identifying data components. Thus, a data component is the data that arrives or leaves from a given network function (NF) of a given service graph (Figure 1). In other words, we consider that NFs (in its general form), are processes that receive, process and

output data. Each of these input/output data components need to be clearly identified, in order to select which of them are relevant for data generation and collection purposes.

FIGURE 1: IDENTIFICATION OF DATA COMPONENTS

- **Phase 3** - For each identified data component, describe its data producer(s), consumer(s), and main characteristics (sample frequency, sample features, etc). In view of the typical type and structure of data components that might be potentially identified in UCs belonging to D6G ecosystem, we defined the following attributes to characterize those data components:
 - **Data component:** Name of data component
 - **Producer:** NF/element that generates data
 - **Consumer:** NF/element that consumes data
 - **Frequency rate:** The time between consecutive samples or, alternatively, the number of samples per time unit.
 - **Features:** Description of the type of data generated, if it contains several fields or features, estimated size of samples, etc.
- **Phase 4** - Map service/component $s \in S$ into D6G architectural components and identify additional data components. In this phase, the objective is to map the different functions in D6G elements, in order to identify the additional data Z that is generated when the UCs are served and supported on the D6G infrastructure. Without loss of generality, we consider two different options for the aforementioned mapping (Figure 2):
 - The D6G component generates additional data Z and transforms the input data X to deliver modified data Y (Figure 2a)
 - The D6G component generates additional data Z and does not transform the input data X , which is simply bypassed (Figure 2b)

FIGURE 2: MAPPING OPTIONS

2.3 Component-oriented methodology

This methodology follows a similar approach of that of the UC-oriented methodology, but typically focuses on a single, well-identified component that can be used by multiple UCs. Due to the nature of the component and the type of data to be generated, this methodology can be fully defined by means of three distinct phases:

- **Phase 1** - Describe the component or family of components that are the focus of this dataset collection. This phase consists of enumerating and briefly describing the different aspects and/or elements that are involved in the target component. The description might introduce, in plain words and/or high level, schematic figures, the characteristics and main aspects of the component to identify the data components that support it (which happens in next phase).
- **Phase 2** - Since different components can have different characteristics, this phase needs to be adapted for each particular case. However, following the rationale of phase 2 of the UC-oriented methodology, this phase aims at detailing the architecture, graphs, and workflows involved in this component. This needs to be done prior to identifying data components. Thus, a data component is the data that arrives or leaves from a given element/subsystem identified in the previous architecture and/or workflow, as well as the data that arrives to/leaves from the target component. Each of these input/output data components needs to be clearly identified, in order to select which of them are relevant for data generation and collection purposes.
- **Phase 3** - This is, in essence, equivalent to the corresponding phase in the UC-oriented methodology, but with some necessary adaptations. Thus, for each identified

element/system of the component, describe its data producer/s, consumer/s, and main characteristics (sample frequency, sample features, etc). In view of the typical type and structure of data components that might be potentially identified, we defined the following attributes to characterize those data components:

- **Data component:** Name of data component.
- **Producer:** Element/system that generates data.
- **Consumer:** Element/system that consumes data.
- **Frequency rate:** The time between consecutive samples or, alternatively, the number of samples per time unit.
- **Features:** Description of the type of data generated, if it contains several fields or features, estimated size of samples, etc.

2.4 General considerations

The purpose of the methodologies described above is to offer a set of guidelines to help with identifying the data to be generated/collected within the DESIRE6G project. Moreover, the proposed organization of dataset description allows readers to better understand data-related aspects such as the nature of the data and its origin and purposes, etc. The methodologies have been written in a sufficiently general way to allow adapting to the needs of each particular UC and component.

Regarding Phase III (both methodologies) and Phase IV (UC-oriented), the format to define/describe the different attributes (producer, consumer, frequency rate, etc) is not fixed. Indeed, depending on the UC/component, it might be necessary to define either alternative attributes or new ones for the sake of a broader and clearer dataset definition.

3. UC-oriented datasets definition

This chapter presents the definition of the datasets that primarily focus on a 6G UC or service supported by D6G infrastructure.

3.1 Augmented Reality / Virtual Reality (AR/VR)

3.1.1 Phase 1

Two main services generating data can be distinguished in the AR/VR UC (Figure 3):

- **Forward Chain:** several video streams are generated by the cameras of different mobile Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) and/or fixed elements (static IP dome cameras). The videos are elaborated locally at the source elements, to perform initial object detection and classification, using local AI models. This produces first-step augmented videos that are then streamed to a computing chain, hosted in the edge computing node(s). The computing chain performs data-stream merging, combination, and data fusion, to obtain a second-step augmented video with a wide-angle view of the scene. Finally, the user equipped with the VR/AR Headset will have a wide-angle real time video with AI augmentation. Specific objects will be automatically recognized and augmented with 3D reconstruction, zooming functions and specific information.
- **Backward chain:** Users, equipped with the VR/AR Headset, have the freedom to select and change the visual parameters of the AR scene. They may use the headset in transparent mode, maintaining their own point of view or switch to the camera view to get better visual on the scene or to get closer to specific objects. Using the interactive Graphic Users Interface (GUI) of the Headset, the user will send interactive commands to the source nodes to change/tune camera angles/zoom/perspective of one or more cameras. The final impression is a natural perspective change as the user is effectively moving autonomously within the scene.

FIGURE 3: AR/VR - PHASE 1

3.1.2 Phase 2

Figure 4 shows the application of this phase on the AR/VR forward chain identified in Phase 1. Note that several NFs have been identified:

- UAV position measurement and video captures.
- Camera video captures.
- Object detection.
- Processing for first-step video stream augmentation.
- Fusion for second-step video stream augmentation.
- Headset video reception and decoding.

Then, the following data components have been identified:

- UAV Positioning and other related metadata.
- Raw video streams.
- Object detection data.
- First-step and second-step augmented videos.
- AR/VR video stream.

FIGURE 4: AR/VR PHASE 2

3.1.3 Phase 3

The following table shows the characteristics of the main data components illustrated in Figure 4 for the AR/VR use case:

TABLE 1: AR/VR - PHASE 3

Data	Producer	Consumer	Frequency rate	Features
Raw Video Stream	UAV camera	Process 1-2, Object Detection 1-2	1 sample (frame) every 40 ms	Frame pixels (image coding)
Positioning Stream	UAV	Object Detection 1	1 sample every 100 ms	GPS latitude, longitude, azimuth
Detection data	Object Detection 1	Process 1	1 sample (frame) every 40ms	Frame pixels + object frame artifact
First-step augmented video	Process 1-2	Fusion 1	1 sample (frame) every 40 ms	Frame pixels (image coding) + object frame artifact
Second-step augmented video	Fusion 1	Object Detection 3, Fusion 2	1 sample (frame) every 40 ms	Frame pixels (image coding) + object frame artifact + object AR reconstruction
AR-VR Video Stream	Fusion 2	Sink (Glasses)	1 sample (frame) every 40 ms	3D frame pixels arrays

3.1.4 Phase 4

Figure 5 shows the mapping applied to the forward chain in Figure 3:

FIGURE 5: AR/VR - PHASE 4

The D6G elements involved and represented are Pervasive Monitoring (PM) systems and Multi-Agent Systems (MAS). As an illustrative example, Figure 6 details the PM3 block, that describes the In-band Network (INT) telemetry collected at the P4 switches that support the transport of video streams from Process 1 and 2 to Fusion 1. Note that these functions modify the input data, since they add the INT timestamps to video packets, in order to perform INT functionality. However, since the content of the video is not actually modified, then this mapping will follow the second option mentioned before (Figure 2b). For the sake of clarity, Table 2 details the different additional data that is generated by the D6G elements identified in Figure 6. Note that this table follows the same format and structure than the table corresponding to Phase 4.

FIGURE 6: DETAILS OF PM3 BLOCK

TABLE 2: AR/VR - PHASE 4 (EXTENDED DETAILS)

Data	Producer	Consumer	Frequency rate	Features
UE INT	UAV system	INT Collector	Flow rate packet	GPS Latitude, Longitude, Azimuth; UAV State (CPU%, GPU%, battery), Radio Channel Level (RSSI), Timestamp, Hop latency
RAN NT	RAN	MAS	1 sample per second	Radio channel quality, RSSI, CQI, estimated UE Latency and Distance, other radio metadata (per-slice)
INT/INT Report	Programmable switch	INT Collector	Flow rate packet	Ingress timestamp, Egress timestamp, Hop latency, Switch ID, Flow ID, egress queue length
INT Statistics	INT Collector	MAS	1 sample per second (configurable)	Switch ID, Flow ID, Average Latency, Max Latency, Min Latency
App IT telemetry	App VM/container/pod	MAS	1 sample per second (configurable)	CPU %, Memory %, GPU % (if available), Execution latency, other IT statistics

3.2 Digital Twin (DT)

3.2.1 Phase 1

The Digital Twin (DT) use case consists of a bi-directional communication system that establishes a closed control and feedback loop between physical robotic entities and their digital replicas (see the schematic view in Figure 7). Data flows can be characterized as follows:

- **Upstream Flow:** The physical robot is equipped with various sensors (camera, LiDAR, IMU) that continuously generate data streams. These data are processed by several applications, such as deep learning models, SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping), and autonomous navigation algorithms deployed on edge/cloud nodes, to maintain an up-to-date virtual representation of the robot in real time.

- **Downstream Flow:** The DT sends control commands to the physical robot to execute movement and tasks. These commands may originate from the user, via interfaces such as gesture-based remote control powered by AI, or from autonomous decision-making modules and are critical for maintaining synchronization between the real and virtual environments.

FIGURE 7: DT - PHASE 1

3.2.2 Phase 2

In this phase, the functional blocks of the DT system are decomposed into individual services or NFs, which are mapped onto a graph structure representing the data flows. Figure 8 represents a generic graph for the upstream flow identified in the previous section. The following NF and data flows are part of this upstream flow:

- **Sensor Acquisition:** Robot cameras, LiDAR, and IMU acquire real-world data.
- **Data Pre-processing and Analysis:** e.g., deep learning models process video frames for computer vision tasks and sensor fusion by combining data from LiDAR and IMU to improve localization accuracy.
- **SLAM and autonomous navigation:** Use LiDAR and odometry for localization and path planning.
- **DT Synchronization:** Virtual replicas update based on the incoming sensor data.

FIGURE 8: DT - PHASE 2

The downstream flow covers the following main NFs and data components:

- **Control Decision Modules:** Remote controllers or autonomous modules compute commands.
- **Robot Actuation:** Commands are sent to the robot actuators to execute the planned actions.

3.2.3 Phase 3

Each data component in the DT system has specific properties including its producer, consumer, generation frequency, and structural features. These properties are crucial for orchestrating data collection, processing, and actuation across the compute continuum. Table 3 details characteristics of potential data components that can be generated in this UC:

TABLE 3: DT - PHASE 3

Data	Producer	Consumer	Frequency rate	Features
Raw Video Stream	Robot cameras	DL model, remote controller, SLAM algorithm, auto-nav algorithm	1 sample (frame) every ~30 ms	Frame pixels (image coding)
Raw Lidar Stream	Robot LiDAR	SLAM algorithm, auto-nav algorithm	1 sample every ~50 ms	2D laser scan with distance and angle readings
Raw Odometry Stream	Robot IMU	remote controller, SLAM algorithm, auto-nav algorithm, virtual replica	1 sample every ~20ms	Estimate of a position and velocity in free space
Detection data	DL model	Remote controller, auto-nav algorithm	1 sample (frame) every 40 ms	Frame pixels (image coding) + object frame artifact
Localization Data	AMCL	SLAM algorithm, auto-nav algorithm	1 sample every 80 ms	An array of an estimated position with a reference coordinate frame and timestamp
Remote control data	Remote controller, auto-nav algorithm	Robot dog	1 sample every 20 ms	Velocity commands (e.g., linear and angular velocities) for high-level motion control of the robot dog.

3.2.4 Phase 4

When mapping the DT service graph onto the DESIRE6G architectural framework, additional data components are expected to be generated to support orchestration and monitoring across the compute continuum. Some DESIRE6G elements that are related with the generation of this additional data for the DT UC are:

- **Pervasive Monitoring (PM):** Collects telemetry from the robot, network, and application infrastructure.
- **SMO (Service Management Orchestrator):** Manages the deployment and lifecycle of DT-related services.
- **IML (Infrastructure Management Layer):** Abstracts and allocates resources; enforces SLAs and optimizes traffic.

Finally, with this mapping, the application telemetry data component is also expected to be generated. It includes reports from containers or VMs running the DT services, capturing metrics such as CPU usage, memory consumption, and latency.

4. Component-oriented datasets definition

This chapter presents the datasets that have been defined according to the component-oriented methodology.

4.1 ML-Based Elastic Scaling

The elastic scaling component in the DESIRE6G project is a critical part of the SMO framework, designed to ensure performance and resource availability in dynamic network environments. Elasticity, as defined in this context, refers to the autonomous ability to scale resources (up or down) in response to workload fluctuations, specifically for edge computing resources supporting a Cellular Vehicular-to-Network (C-V2N) service. This component is integral to maintaining service quality under varying traffic conditions, a key requirement for 6G networks that aim to support Ultra-High Reliability & Low Latency Communications (uRLLC) and enhanced Mobile Broad Band (eMBB).

4.1.1 Phase 1

Brief Description and Functionalities:

- **Purpose:** The elastic scaling component dynamically adjusts edge computing resources (e.g., CPU, memory, network bandwidth) to accommodate changes in vehicular traffic demand, ensuring that the C-V2N service meets its performance targets, such as low latency and high throughput.
- **Functionalities:** It monitors real-time traffic data, predicts resource needs, and triggers scaling actions (e.g., adding or removing virtual machines or containers) to optimize resource utilization while avoiding over-provisioning or service degradation.
- **Data Requirements:** The component relies on time-series data representing vehicle arrivals at Points of Presence (PoPs), which serve as edge nodes. This data must capture temporal and spatial patterns of traffic to enable predictive scaling decisions. High-level figures from the dataset include over 100 measuring locations and traffic intensity measured in vehicles per hour across a 10-month period.

High-Level Figures:

- **Dataset Scope:** Over 100 measurement points in Turin, Italy, covering January to October 2020. Figure 9 illustrates 5 representative PoPs used in this work.
- **PoPs:** 5 selected edge nodes for synthetic data generation.

In essence, the elastic scaling component acts as an intelligent resource manager, leveraging historical and real-time data to adapt to the C-V2N service's demands, aligning with DESIRE6G's goal of smart orchestration in 6G networks.

FIGURE 9: 5 REPRESENTATIVE POPS WITH AVERAGE CAR TRAFFIC INTENSITY.

4.1.2 Phase 2

This dataset drives scaling decisions by providing insights into vehicle traffic patterns at edge sites, specifically tailored to the Cellular Vehicular-to-Network (C-V2N) service. The elastic scaling operates within the context of a V2N system, where a base-station provides connectivity to smartphone users and connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) along a road segment. The V2N traffic, supporting applications like remote driving and hazard warnings, is processed at the network edge to meet stringent delay constraints. In DESIRE6G, service agents—aligned with the Multi-Agent System (MAS) approach—decide on scaling edge resources, potentially employing the DESIRE6G Infrastructure Management Layer (IML) to meet service requirements under varying workloads. Figure 10 sketches the elastic scaling component within the DESIRE6G architecture

FIGURE 10: DESIRE6G V2N SYSTEM WITH ELASTIC SCALING.

4.1.3 Phase 3

Data Producer(s):

- **Source:** The dataset originates from a real-world vehicular trace dataset collected in Turin, Italy, by traffic monitoring systems (e.g., sensors or cameras at over 100 measuring locations). This is managed by an external entity, likely a municipal authority or research group (referenced as Opendata Torino Traffic Data in D5.1).
- **Synthetic Generation:** We use Poisson processes to model vehicle arrivals at 5 selected PoPs, based on the traffic intensity from the source dataset.

Data Consumer(s):

- **Primary Consumer:** The elastic scaling component uses this dataset to analyze traffic patterns, predict resource needs, and trigger scaling actions at edge PoPs.
- **Secondary Consumers:** Other DESIRE6G components, such as machine learning (ML) models for orchestration (e.g., MLFO) or performance evaluation modules, might consume this data to validate scaling decisions or train predictive algorithms.

TABLE 4: ELASTIC SCALING - PHASE 3

Attribute	Variable Type	Sample Frequency	Description and Features	Potential Extensions
Arriving Time	Int64 (UNIX Time)	Every 5 minutes	Timestamp of vehicle arrival at a PoP, derived from the Turin dataset's 5-minute intervals.	Higher resolution (e.g., 1-minute or real-time) for uRLLC scenarios; could include millisecond precision.
Arriving PoP	String	Every 5 minutes	Identifier of the PoP (e.g., PoP1, PoP2) where the vehicle arrives, limited to 5 PoPs in the synthetic set.	Expand to more PoPs or include geographic coordinates (latitude, longitude) for spatial analysis.
Traffic Intensity	Float32 (vehicles/hour)	Every 5 minutes	The rate of vehicle arrivals per hour at each PoP, used as input to Poisson processes.	Add peak/off-peak flags, historical averages, or variance to capture traffic volatility.
Vehicle Count	Int32	Every 5 minutes	Number of vehicles arriving in the 5-minute interval (synthetic, based on Poisson distribution).	Include vehicle type (e.g., car, truck) or priority (e.g., emergency vehicle) for differentiated scaling.
Latency Demand	Float32 (ms)	N/A (simulated)	Not collected in D5.1 but could be inferred; latency requirement per	Simulated per-vehicle latency needs (e.g., 1ms for uRLLC, 10ms for eMBB) to guide scaling granularity.

			vehicle for C-V2N service.	
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4.2 ML-Based Service-Level Agreement Decomposition

In 6G networks, a service-level agreement (SLA) will likely span multiple domains – access, core, and transport networks – potentially across different operators. Before service instantiation, the end-to-end (E2E) SLA must be decomposed into partial service-level objectives (SLOs) for each domain to guide resource allocation. Due to the network complexity, AI-assisted SLA decomposition is key to enabling automation.

The SMO layer handles SLA decomposition but has limited real-time visibility into each domain's state. Instead, it relies on historical admission control feedback from previous service requests. Traditional approaches use heuristics based on periodic state reports. In contrast, prior work formulates SLA decomposition as a probability optimization problem and introduces parameter-free domain-specific risk models based on historical responses. However, the estimation of such models is computationally expensive. To address this, deep neural network (DNN)-based risk models are proposed to estimate SLA acceptance probabilities.

The dataset used for training the risk models is constructed by collecting historical feedback from domain controllers on past admission control decisions. This feedback captures whether previous service requests with specific SLA parameters were accepted or rejected by each domain. Over time, this data forms a valuable training set that enables the learning of domain-specific risk models, allowing NNs to estimate the probability of SLA acceptance accurately, even with limited real-time visibility into the network state.

4.2.1 Phase 1

SLA Decomposition Component: Description, Functionalities, and Data Requirements

The SLA decomposition component is responsible for translating an end-to-end (E2E) service-level agreement (SLA) into partial service-level objectives (SLOs) assigned to individual network domains (e.g., RAN, transport, core). This enables domain-specific resource allocation while ensuring that the global SLA is met.

Key Functionalities:

- Analyze incoming E2E SLA requests and determine feasible SLO splits per domain.
- Estimate the likelihood of SLA acceptance by each domain using trained risk models.
- Ensure that the decomposition respects service constraints (e.g., maximum delay, throughput).
- Support automation by integrating with the SMO layer.

Data Requirements:

- **Historical Admission Control Feedback:** Records of previous service requests and the accept/reject decisions from each domain.
- **SLA Parameter Metadata:** Details of requested SLA attributes (e.g., latency, bandwidth) and outcomes.
- **Domain Characteristics:** Network type, domain capabilities.

This data is crucial for training machine learning-based risk models that guide accurate and efficient SLA decomposition, even with limited real-time visibility into domain states.

4.2.2 Phase 2

Figure 11 depicts the architecture of an AI-assisted SLA decomposition system in a 6G network, based on the DESIRE6G framework. The E2E SMO component receives an E2E SLA requirement and uses NN-based risk models and an optimization engine to decompose it into domain-specific SLOs. These partial SLOs are sent to the respective network domains: the D6G edge site (RAN), the transport network, and the D6G core site. Each domain evaluates the request and provides feedback on its admission decision, which is fed back to the SMO. This feedback loop enables continuous learning and refinement of the risk models for more accurate and adaptive SLA decomposition over time.

FIGURE 11: SLA DECOMPOSITION SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

4.2.3 Phase 3

Here is a detailed breakdown of the key data components involved in the SLA decomposition system, including their **producers**, **consumers**, and **main characteristics** (sample frequency, features, potential metrics).

Admission Control Feedback Data

Attribute	Details
Producer(s)	Domain Controllers e.g., IMLs at RAN/Core, Software-Defined Networking (SDN) Controllers for Transport
Consumer(s)	E2E SMO (NN-based Risk Models)
Sample Frequency	Per service request
Sample Features	- SLA parameters (e.g., requested delay, throughput, reliability) - Domain-specific decomposition values - Admission outcome (accept/reject) - Timestamp - Domain load/state tags (if available)

Potential Metrics	- Success ratio of admission - Latency of decision - Trends over time - Feedback response delay
Format	Structured log entries or JSON-based records

E2E SLA Request Data

Attribute	Details
Producer(s)	Service Consumer / Application / Service Broker
Consumer(s)	E2E SMO (Optimization Engine, Risk Models)
Sample Frequency	Per service instantiation or modification
Sample Features	- SLA ID - Requested E2E delay (d_max_e2e) - Bandwidth - Reliability - Geolocation (optional) - Priority level - Timestamp
Potential Metrics	- Request volume - SLA strictness level - Rejection probability (derived) - Service types (uRLLC, eMBB, etc.)
Format	JSON or API request objects

NN-Based Risk Model Outputs

Attribute	Details
Producer(s)	Trained Neural Network Models (hosted in SMO)
Consumer(s)	SMO Optimization Engine
Sample Frequency	Per SLA decomposition
Sample Features	- Estimated acceptance probability per domain - SLA configuration - Input feature vector from historical data
Potential Metrics	- Prediction accuracy - Model confidence - Feature importance
Format	Internal model outputs, vectorized inputs/outputs

4.3 ML-assisted Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface Configuration at Edge Nodes

The dataset pertains to the proof-of-concept (PoC) for machine learning (ML)-assisted Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) configuration, where a NN is trained using a federated learning (FL) approach, as detailed in Section 5.1 of D3.1. The key components involved include a parameter server (PS), distributed computing resources, transmitters, receivers, and RISs. In a practical network deployment, the PS can be hosted within a Near-Real-Time Remote Intervention Control, distributed computing can be hosted in distributed units (DUs), transmitters correspond to radio units (RUs), and receivers represent user equipment (UEs), see Figure 12.

FIGURE 12: SERVICES AND/OR COMPONENTS THAT ARE INVOLVED.

4.3.1 Phase 1

Note that the transmitter sends data to its intended receiver. In this respect RIS is enhancing the quality of the end-to-end transmission by appropriately configuring its reflecting elements. Instructions on how to configure the RIS elements are determined by a computing resource such as DU. To this end, the DU

requires channel information. This is illustrated in Figure 13. Based on channel information, DU determine the RIS configuration, which is then made available at the RIS, see Figure 13. Note that, the channel information is typically estimated based on pilots originated by the transmitter and the RIS to RIS and the receiver, respectively. This is depicted by using black arrows in Figure 12 and Figure 13. Thus, the essential components for training of related ML algorithms are feedback chain related to CSI and the forward chain corresponds to RIS configurations.

FIGURE 13: ML-ASSISTED RIS - PHASE 1.

4.3.2 Phase 2

Next, we explicitly describe the related data components of the feedback chain, and the forward chain, as depicted in Figure 13. The feedback chain is directly linked to the channel state information (CSI). More specifically, we need 1) the CSI between the transmitter and the RIS, i.e., \mathbf{h} , 2) the CSI between the RIS and the receiver, i.e., \mathbf{g} , see Figure 14. As mentioned earlier, in a practical deployment, the CSI \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{g} are estimated using pilot signals transmitted by the transmitters and RISs, as indicated by the black arrows in Figure 12-Figure 14. Each RIS estimates its corresponding CSI \mathbf{h} based on pilot signals received from the transmitter. Similarly, each receiver estimates its corresponding CSI \mathbf{g} based on pilot signals received from the RIS. The estimated CSI pairs (\mathbf{h}, \mathbf{g}) are then made available to a computing resource, such as the DU in Figure 12, which determines the optimal RIS configuration denoted \mathbf{y} . Finally, the computed RIS configuration \mathbf{y} is communicated to the RIS (see green arrows in Figure 14, which adjusts its configuration accordingly).

FIGURE 14: ML-ASSISTED RIS - PHASE 2

4.3.3 Phase 3

As previously shown, we have 3 data components: CSI h , CSI b , and RIS configuration y .

Table 5 outlines the producer and the consumer of the data components.

TABLE 5: DATA COMPONENTS, PRODUCERS, AND CONSUMERS.

Data component	Producer	Consumer
CSI h	RISs	DUs
CSI g	UEs	DUs
RIS Configuration y	DUs	RISs

More specifically, within our empirical setup, RISs provides realizations of estimated channels h and UEs provides realization of estimated channels g from a single antenna transmitter to the RIS and from the RIS to the single antenna receiver, respectively. Each realization is labelled by the ‘optimal RIS configuration’ that maximizes the receiver’s data rate. The ‘optimal RIS configuration’ is computed by choosing the best over N possible choices, which we refer to as quantization index. Each choice corresponds to a ‘representative RIS configuration’. Given channels h and g , the best choice y is the one

that corresponds to the representative RIS configuration yielding the maximum achievable rate computed by considering the commonly used Shannon’s formula [2]. Thus, associated with each pair \mathbf{h} , \mathbf{g} the label y is assigned as the ‘optimal RIS configuration’. The number N ranges from 2 to 10. Therefore, technically, we have one dataset for each N , which in turn results in 9 data sets. The dataset consists of 50,000 samples split heterogeneously across 4 RIS environments indexed by $r \in \{1,2,3,4\}$.

The detailed attributes of the dataset are outlined in Table 6.

TABLE 6: ML-ASSISTED RIS – PHASE 3.

Attribute	Variable type	Description
CSI \mathbf{h}^r	Complex vector of length N^r	Channel between a single antenna transmitter and the RIS in the RIS environment r
CSI \mathbf{g}^r	Complex vector of length N^r	Channel between the RIS and a single antenna receiver in the RIS environment r
Quantization index N	An integer from 2 to 10	N is a parameter that represents a level of quantization used when computing the ‘optimal RIS configuration’. In the original dataset (see Section 5.5 of D5.1), $N=2$
Optimal Configuration y^r	RIS An integer from 0 to $N-1$	Represent the index that corresponds to the ‘representative RIS configuration’ which yields the maximum rate.

4.4 Payload Performance Self-Monitoring

4.4.1 Phase 1

In DESIRE-6G, we are exploring the feasibility of a workload performance self-monitoring, providing near real time payload performance ratio, measuring the effective speed of execution of a software payload in its execution environment. The merit of the considered technique is to obviate external dependencies

for the monitoring (i.e., the monitoring software must be installed on the execution environment), inducing heavy performance penalty on the payload).

The general description of the data path is given in Figure 15:

FIGURE 15: SELF-MONITORING PERFORMANCE WORKFLOW

The solution modifies the assembly code of the executable workload, appending “trampolines” over the control flow graph, leveraging the `i9patch` tool for executable instrumentation [3]. The trampoline is a jump to a functional snippet then return to the Control Flow Guard (CFG). Trampolines are set on code blocks, uniquely identified `i9patch`. Our trampolines generate time series on the shared memory segment, then used by the process Reader. The time series analysis delivers two different metrics as stated below.

Metrics Produced

- **CF (Call Frequency):** Captures frequency of control flow blocks
- **ET (Execution Time):** Captures execution time of injected code blocks

Encountered issues

- Architectural design of the solution had to be progressed to remove synchronization issues between the metrics generation and reads, leading to data losses.
- CFG undecidability breaks dynamically the CFG, precluding to the traversal of our GFG-defined trampolines.

4.4.2 Phase 2

This phase has consisted in solving phase 1 technical issues and notably fixing issues encountered by CFG undecidability by the generation of specific ET reference blocks.

This phase also consists in applying the solution to L2 forwarding (abbreviated as L2fwd) network function, implementing a specific testbench capable of traffic generation using DPDK. This phase showcased the technical relevance and usability of CF and ET metrics to monitor a network function. Phase 2 demonstrated that CF can be a marker for ingress traffic volume while ET be a marker for platform resource congestion. In short, phase 2 has brought a more mature understanding on merits and limitations of both metrics and how they shall be used. CF reflects the call frequency of a CFG code block but not all blocks are called according to the software ingested arguments. Typically for L2fwd, the packet content engenders different types of processing and calls to different code blocks of the CFG. Figure 16 presents a simple packet processing workflow by L2Fwd. CF positioned on the New Trampoline location reflects the frequency of packet processing, hence reflecting in non-saturated mode, the frequency of presence of a new entrant packet to process which is a measure of the ingress traffic volume (i.e., entrant packets/sec). Reversely, our placement of the trampoline at the old trampoline location was actually measuring the frequency of the test of packet presence by L2fwd, a parameter which does not correlate with the ingress traffic volume.

FIGURE 16: LOCATIONS OF CF TRAMPOLINES

Our testbench simulates platform resource congestion or attrition, adding “workers” in adjustable number. The impact on L2fwd performance is analyzed through ET and CF metrics.

Instrumentation and Data Collection

- Time extractors are injected at key points in the control flow (entry/exit of blocks).
- Metrics are captured during runtime, producing time series of CF and ET.

Processing and Analysis

- Metrics are compared to the baseline profile established during calibration.
- CF gives insight of process performance but its placement in the workload requires a good understanding of the workload functioning, identifying the different functional branches of the code. CF performance penalty is insignificant.
- ET highlights effects of dispatcher interruptions, especially useful in shared CPU contexts. For that, our novel ET inseparable reference code block must be sufficient long, which could generate a performance penalty if too frequently instantiated.

4.4.3 Phase 3

Phase 3 clarifies the data components and streams as follows. Data extraction and processing is worked out in TSS infrastructure.

Data Producers

Benchmarking and traffic injection tools (DPDK testbed, PRIME datasets)

Data Consumers

Network Function administrators analysing performance patterns

Production Frequency

Continuous or sampled runtime extraction, adaptable for low-penalty on-demand measurement

Sample Features

- L2fwd network function. (i.e., the self-monitored workload)
- Network simulation by T-Rex

- Platform resource attrition by adjustable workers (i.e., using stress-ng)

Potential metrics

- L2fwd ingress traffic volume
- Platform stress level

Format

- On shared memory: Time series with following structure
- On our analysing tool

Outcomes

- CF metric when placed in L2fwd packet processing main loop (e.g., dealing with packet parsing packet, packet forward) is tightly correlated to the ingress traffic volume. The variation of CF reflects the variation of the traffic volume from nil to the saturated level plateau.
- ET reference code block is tightly correlated to the resource attrition and quantity of workers.

4.5 Payload Remote Attestation and Runtime Integrity Verification

In DESIRE-6G, we develop a blockchain based mutual remote attestation scheme called D-MUTRA to attest payload before their execution or during their execution. The solution takes profit and is defined for containers. Hence, containerized payloads are measured by a side car mounted container. As latency at payload start and performance penalty are key elements to measure and optimize for 6G services. Figure below shows the measurements which are done

Once the agent has been deployed and its reference measurement generated, blockchain-based remote attestation can begin. First, the MLFO triggers the sidecar to launch the agent, initiating seamless remote attestation. The sidecar begins measuring the agent and sends the data to the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) with a "register agent" event. The DLT then selects the first freshly attested agent to act as the verifier for any pending attestation requests. In the case of the first agent, the Security-as-a-Service (SECaaS) is selected as the verifier and compares the reference measurement with the newly received measurement. The SECaaS records the result in the DLT, and an event is sent to determine whether the agent should be started.

4.5.1 Phase 1

The **D-MUTRA component** enables blockchain-based mutual remote attestation of agents before their secure deployment. The goal is to ensure that each agent, managed through SECaaS, remains trustworthy by verifying integrity through a DLT.

Functionalities:

- Generation of reference integrity measurements for each agent at initial deployment.
- Automatic measurement and attestation of agent integrity before starting the agent.
- Use of blockchain (DLT) to transparently record, verify, and manage attestation events.
- Selection of attested agents or SECaaS as verifiers to perform mutual attestation.
- Decision-making to approve or deny agent execution based on attestation outcomes.

Data Requirements:

- **Reference measurements:** Cryptographic baseline for each agent.
- **Real-time measurements:** Integrity state collected by sidecars at runtime.
- **Attestation results:** Verified measurement outcomes recorded on-chain.
- **Agent metadata:** Unique identifiers, deployment timestamps, verifier assignments.

4.5.2 Phase 2

The D-MUTRA process leverages DLT to establish trust among SECaaS-managed agents through mutual attestation. The workflow follows these steps:

1. **Deployment Initialization:**
 - a. SECaaS deploys agents, generating their reference measurements.
2. **Trigger Attestation:**
 - a. The MLFO triggers the sidecar to start the agent, initiating remote attestation seamlessly.
3. **Measurement Collection & Registration:**
 - a. The sidecar continuously measures the agent's runtime integrity and submits measurement data to the blockchain via a "register agent" event.

4. Verifier Selection:

- a. The blockchain dynamically selects a recently attested agent as verifier for pending attestations.
- b. For the first agent, SECaaS acts as the verifier.

5. Integrity Verification:

- a. The verifier compares runtime measurements with stored reference measurements, providing an integrity decision.

6. Decision & Record on DLT:

- a. The verifier records the result of attestation (pass/fail) onto the blockchain.
- b. An event triggers the decision to either allow or prevent the agent's execution.

FIGURE 17: REMOTE ATTESTATION WORKFLOW

D-MUTRA overview

In this table, we have compiled the average results from the different phases of D-MUTRA.

- The measurement is a memory operation that generates a hash of the memory. Duration: very fast.
- The verification consists of retrieving a hash from a database and comparing it with another hash. Duration: fast.

- Events are emitted by the blockchain across the network. Duration: slow.

4.5.3 Phase 3

Reference Measurement Data

- **Producers:** SECaaS at agent deployment.
- **Consumers:** Verifiers (SECaaS or attested agents).
- **Sample Frequency:** Once per agent deployment.
- **Content:**
 - Agent Identifier (ID)
 - Cryptographic hashes of binaries
 - Timestamp
- **Format:** Structured JSON

Runtime Measurement Data

- **Producers:** Sidecars co-deployed with agents.
- **Consumers:** Blockchain (DLT), Verifier Agents, SECaaS.
- **Sample Frequency:** At each attestation request/event.
- **Content:**
 - Agent ID
 - Current integrity hash of running agent
 - Measurement timestamp
- **Format:** JSON-structured events sent to DLT.

5. Reference Network Architecture and Technologies

To establish economic and business advantages of the DESIRE6G technological advances towards 6G, it is essential to establish a representative 5G baseline architecture.

To do this, the starting point is the existing Telefónica 4G LTE & 5G NSA site deployments, which provides a realistic SotA (State of the Art) Public MNO (Mobile Network Operator) network. These current deployments are a mix of 4G LTE and 5G-NR added in a non-standalone (or 5G Release 15 Phase 1) mode to the 4G core, utilising traditional network appliances, such as BBU (Baseband Units) at the macro cell towers, connecting to a centralised 4G EPC, with just backhaul transport networks and no '5G Edge'.

However, to demonstrate and quantify the techno-economic benefits of DESIRE6G, the baseline needs to be a fully 5G Standalone (5G Release 15 Phase 2 or Release 16/17) network, with a disaggregated architecture of software defined network functions, with many of them deployable on COTS servers, which can be deployed at cell sites or Edge servers, thereby including midhaul transport networks, and with the introduction of the O-RAN Alliance extensions of further disaggregation of RU/DU (introducing fronthaul) and addition of RAN intelligence through the RAN intelligent Controller (RIC). Furthermore, the 5G mobile core (5GC) will support separation of user and control planes, with Edge UPF deployments for local breakout.

Currently, deployments of 5G SA are only now starting to happen, but the significant rip/replace CAPEX costs of upgrading from 5G NSA to SA are NOT considered in this analysis, as it is not strictly relevant to DESIRE6G. Therefore, this study defines an equivalent Open 5G SA as the baseline, with costs/benefits from this baseline, but not any costs to reach this baseline.

To establish a realistic baseline, the following methodology is applied:

- Leverage the existing reference Telefónica 4G LTE & 5G NSA site deployments for three focus environments, as described below in 5.1, namely 1) Rural, 2) Dense and 3) High Dense scenarios.
- Define a reference Open RAN based 5G Standalone architecture, with corresponding RAN, transport & mobile core components that can be deployable in different configurations (from fully centralised to distributed) to best suit the reference envisaged baseline, described in 5.2.
- For each of the three focus environments, define a detailed equivalent 5G SA baseline deployment, with representative BoM (Bill of Material) for RAN, transport network and core.

From the equivalent 5G SA baseline, apply the deltas and improvements brought by DESIRE6G.

5.1 4G LTE & 5G NSA baseline deployment

The current Telefónica site deployments are a mix of 4G LTE & 5G-NR radios in a 5G non-standalone network, with three focus environments, is shown below (Table 7):

TABLE 7: TELEFÓNICA CURRENT RAN SITES DEPLOYMENTS

	Rural environment	Dense environment	High dense
Frequency bands	N28/B20/B8	N28/B20/B8 & B1/B3	N28/B20/B8 & B1/B3/B7 & n78
MIMO order	2T4R/4T4R	2T4R/4T4R	4G: 2T4R/4T4R 5G: 64T64R
Total 4G cells	6	12	15
Total 5G cells	3	3	6
BW/sector (Non-MaMIMO)	30MHz	70MHz	90MHz
BW/sector (Massive MIMO)	-	-	100MHz

For reference, the used frequency bands are as follows:

- B1: LTE IMT FDD 2100MHz (1920-1980 up, 2110-2170 down)
- B3: LTE DCS FDD 1800MHz (1710-1785 up, 1805-1880 down)
- B7: LTE IMT-E FDD 2600MHz (2500-2570 up, 2620-2690 down)
- B8: LTE eGSM FDD 900MHz (880-915 up, 925-960 down)
- B20: LTE DD FDD 800MHz (832-862 up, 791-821 down)
- N28: 5G-NR APT FDD 700MHz (703-748 up, 758-803 down)
- N78: 5G-NR C-Band TDD 3500MHz (3300-3800 up/down)

The following general top-level view can be observed from the above (with further details presented in 5.1.1):

- A rural environment (5.1.1.1) uses low frequency (700-900MHz) bands to maximise coverage and indoor penetration over a large area, with relatively few and dispersed high-power macro cells. As the total number of users is relatively low, only limited bandwidth (30MHz) is utilised.
- A dense environment (5.1.1.2, typically urban or suburban areas) has a much higher number and density of users, requiring more bandwidth (70MHz) and extra capacity, obtained in higher

bandwidth channels (1800-2100MHz), but with resultantly reduced penetration, requiring macro cell towers closer together to support this denser environment.

- The high dense (5.1.1.3, sometimes called ultra-dense) are typical urban centres, travel hubs (like railways station & airports), shopping malls, sports stadiums, and other locations that can have massive numbers of users at their busiest times. These locations need as much coverage and capacity as possible, including additional bandwidth and frequencies (2600-3500MHz) and dense small cells, supporting Massive MIMO (64T64R) 5G-NR, to complement denser macro coverage.

The Telefónica networks are interconnected via the fixed (optical) transport network which are categorized via Hierarchy Levels, as detailed in 5.1.2.

5.1.1 RAN (Radio Access Network)

The current 5G NSA deployment of macro cells, for all 3 scenario deployments, is illustrated below in Figure 18

FIGURE 18: TYPICAL 5G NSA MACRO CELL DEPLOYMENT FOCUS ON RAN AND CORE, NOT TRANSPORT

The macro towers use high-gain (often 13-16dB) sectorised panel antennas fed by RRH (Remote Radio Heads), mounted on towers or poles, providing 120° beamwidth, typically tilted downwards to illuminate a wide area. They are connected to power and optical fibre (Split 8 CPRI fronthaul, which while being

partially standardized is effectively vendor incompatible) to the high-powered Baseband Units (BBUs) installed in a cabinet at the base of the tower.

To support multiple frequency bands, multiple sets of RRU/BBU are typically used (especially as 5G-NR were typically added later than the initial LTE RAN), though some integrated multiband solutions support multiple bands in single enclosures (e.g. some RRH have 8 ports, supporting 2x4 or 4x4 MIMO to 2 frequency bands). This is typically repeated per sector (so 3 sectors for 120° beamwidth antennas).

These RRU/BBU provide the full RAN capabilities for 4G LTE eNB (eNodeB) and 5G-NR gNB (gNodeB), with time & frequency synchronization typically provided by the addition of GPS antennas. They provide non-massive MIMO of 2T4R (2x4) and 4T4R (4x4), typically with 20-40W per transmit port (so 2 for 2x4 and 4 for 4x4 MIMO), depending to an extent on the frequency.

The RRU/BBU eNB/gNB are interconnected through an optical backhaul transport network to a centralised 4G Core (EPC). In some cases, where there is no optical transport available, macro cells have a point-to-point microwave wireless (unlicensed line of sight) backhaul relayed to 'donor' macro sites with optical backhaul. In some very remote regions or islands this backhaul is sometimes provided via satellite links (using permanent traditional GEO or MEO 'bent pipes').

Although there were technical solutions for local breakout even in 4G, the assumption is that there is no Edge (MEC) compute in the architecture with 'Edge DC: Data Centres' only relevant to termination and interconnection of access/aggregation and metro/core optical network end points.

5.1.1.1 Scenario 1: Rural Environment

A rural environment uses low frequency (FDD 700-900MHz) bands to maximise coverage and indoor penetration over a large area.

The antennas and RRHs are normally mounted on very high towers to maximise coverage, while minimising the number of cell towers, hence limiting CAPEX costs (rural environments, with low average user densities and consequent revenues, have difficult business use-cases, unless MNOs are required to provide rural coverage to fulfil their license terms and USO (universal service obligations).

Very high-power transmission is used, increasing downlink coverage, but as that the BW per sector is limited (here 30MHz), there are limits for maximum spectral density, defined by the spectrum regulation

and licensing, corresponding to the macro cell propagation model for a rural area in 3GPP TR 36.942 [4] §4.5.3 and §4.6.

The architecture is as described above in 5.1.1 but we assume all macro cells are interconnected via optical transport networks, hence no wireless or satellite backhaul is considered.

A typical rural environment scenario consists of 6 4G LTE cells and 3 5G-NR cells.

An anonymised reference small rural network deployment is shown below (Figure 19)

FIGURE 19: SMALL RURAL SCENARIO: HIGH-LEVEL VIEW (A) AND ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE (B)

5.1.1.2 Scenario 2: Dense (typically Urban) Environment

The antennas and RRHs are normally mounted on medium height towers to provide wide coverage, with denser macro cell deployments than rural environments.

BW per sector is increased (here 70MHz), with maximum spectral density defined by the spectrum regulation and licensing, corresponding to the macro cell propagation model for an urban area in 3GPP TR 36.942 [4] §4.5.2 and §4.6.

The required extra capacity is obtained through adding higher bandwidth channels (FDD 1800-2100MHz), but with corresponding reduced penetration, requiring the cell towers for these higher frequency bands to be closer together to support this denser environment or poorer coverage at cell edges (and for instance, to use 1800-2100MHz for primarily outdoor coverage with the 700-900MHz bands for indoor/outdoor coverage).

The architecture is as described above in 5.1.1 and we assume all macro cells are interconnected via optical transport networks.

A typical dense urban environment scenario consists of 12 4G LTE cells and 3 5G-NR cells.

An anonymised reference urban network deployment is shown below in Figure 20:

FIGURE 20: URBAN SCENARIO: HIGH-LEVEL VIEW (A) AND ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE (B)

5.1.1.3 Scenario 3: High (or Ultra-) Dense Environment

The high dense (sometimes called ultra-dense) can have massive numbers of users at their busiest times, thus require extremely high bandwidth.

In addition to a dense urban deployment of macro cells at all available frequencies (including 2600MHz B7 FDD LTE), this scenario adds pole or wall mounted 5G small cells in mid-band (C-Band, 3500MHz), supporting Massive MIMO (64T64R) 5G-NR in TDD, to complement denser macro FDD coverage, as illustrated below in Figure 21.

FIGURE 21: HIGH DENSE DEPLOYMENT ADDING TDD MMIMO SMALL CELLS TO THE MACRO COVERAGE

The addition of higher frequency (3.5GHz) spectrum, using mMIMO small cells, typically provides additional line-of-sight outdoor capacity to the low frequency (< 1GHz) coverage layer and intermediate frequency (2-2.5GHz) coverage/capacity extension. This MFN (Multi-Frequency Network) is visualised below in Figure 22. Note that High-band is often synonymous with FR2 mmWave & Mid-band with C-Band N78. But here the usage of high-band corresponds to C-Band, while intermediate/mid-band is in the range 2-2.5GHz and low-band means less than 2GHz.

FIGURE 22: MFN (MULTI-FREQUENCY NETWORK) OF LOW BAND COVERAGE THROUGH HIGH BAND CAPACITY

An anonymised reference high (ultra) dense urban network deployment is shown below in Figure 23:

FIGURE 23: DENSE URBAN SCENARIO: HIGH-LEVEL VIEW (A) AND ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE (B)

5.1.2 Fixed Transport Network

In the last decade, all Telefonica Networks have been simplified to a hierarchical level architecture for all Countries including Mobile Only Operations as well as Fixed/Mobile Country Networks. In all of Telefonica operations, the transport network is composed by 4(+1) hierarchical levels as shown in Figure 24.

FIGURE 24: TELEFÓNICA TRANSPORT NETWORK 'HIERARCHY LEVELS'

Levels 1 and 2 perform the core and interconnection functions. The lower levels, at the provincial level, perform the IP aggregation and access functions. In some cases, at levels 3 and 4, there will be some nodes with specialized functions, responsible for aggregating connections for certain types of accesses, but those are details out of the topic of this section and not in the scope of this project.

All transport network equipment will have protection against a single failure of common elements and, except for part of the HL5 plant, will also have protection against a single link failure. Levels 1 to 3 equipment will be located in the so-called "Network Core" buildings, which will have the best infrastructure features, while levels 4 and 5 will be located in FTTH head ends (category 4 buildings).

5.1.2.1 Backbone and Interconnection Level

- Level 1 (HL1) This level supports interconnections with content providers and carriers, so the functions of this level are the same as those of legacy IP network interconnection routers.
- Level 2 (HL2) This level switches traffic between HL3 devices and between HL3 and HL1. HL2 devices are equivalent to legacy IP network transit routers. In this level there are also the Connection with the Telefonica Mobile Core, UPF, Security Gateway and Telco Cloud VNF's and services.

5.1.2.2 Provincial Level

The provincial level is organized into what is known as an HL3 area or zone. Each HL3 area is made up of a HL3 nodes pair and all the lower-level Telefonica nodes that “hanging” from them.

Depending on the type of access elements that connect to a fusion area, three types of HL3 areas are distinguished:

- Residential HL3 area: an area that collects traffic from fixed access networks, DSLAMs, and OLTs. Therefore, it will serve all types of services with indirect access: residential, business, wholesale, and commercial services, although, by volume and number of customers, residential services predominate.
- Business/Mobile HL3 area: an area that collects traffic from business services, mobile access, wholesale, and commercial services with direct access (dedicated access port).
- Multi-Service HL3 area: an area that collects access traffic from the different services supported by the transport network. Most HL3 areas are multi-service as the ones in the scope of the three scenarios selected in this project.

5.1.2.3 Level 3 (HL3)

In order to ensure the scalability of this network level, as well as to minimize interventions within it, this level only performs two access equipment (PE) functions:

- The only platform connections supported are those corresponding to video injection (CSL, CDN) and mobile synchronization (TP5000).

- "LTE/3G/2G Bypass,". The HL3 nodes in each zone convert the traffic from the different BSSs connected in that zone to Level 3.

Therefore, these nodes primarily have a transit function. They deliver video and synchronization traffic to the HL4 levels (with which they will have direct connectivity) and to the HL5 devices (through the HL4 devices), performing the necessary traffic transit for the remaining services through their links with the different fusion levels.

HL3 nodes are connected to upper-level equipment with a U- and V-shaped topology with Nx100G links.

FIGURE 25: HL-3 TO HL2 CONNECTIONS (LEFT: U CONNECTION, RIGHT: V CONNECTION)

There will be, at least, one HL3 Pair per Province in the network, existing two or three HL3 pairs in larger provinces.

5.1.2.4 Level 4 (HL4)

This level is the most complex in Telefonica Networks. In a very general way, it has assumed the access functions of both the Ethernet and IP networks. With the following connectivity:

- Fixed access network nodes (IP DSLAM and OLT).
- Mobile access network nodes (Base Stations).
- Customer access with dedicated fiber.
- Wholesale service access
- Mobile Core platforms and elements (GGSN, SGSN, CGW, etc.), which are scheduled for shutdown and will not be integrated into the final virtualized solution.

HL4 Nodes are connected to the higher-Level nodes (HL3) with V Topology with Nx10G or Nx100G

FIGURE 26: HL4 TO HL3 CONNECTIONS USING V TOPOLOGY

HL4 Nodes will be installed in network core buildings co-located with HL3s and also in FTTH head ends, which will generally concentrate more than 20,000 inhabitants.

5.1.2.5 Level 5 (Capillarization Level), HL5/mMTU

It corresponds to a level of network capillarity serving locations with low-to-medium concentration of demand, generally towns with fewer than 15,000 inhabitants.

Achieving this capillarization becomes even more necessary, if possible, due to the expansion of FTTH services requiring 10 GbE connectivity, and the increase in business and mobile service provision to increasingly smaller populations, and therefore with more scarce transmission media.

The current and future scenario involves serving rural and provincial areas not only new demand for business and mobile services, but also connections from new OLTs. The capillarization of fiber triggered the need for IP aggregation equipment, but smaller than those used in higher levels, to ensure its economic efficiency.

FIGURE 27: HL5 TO HL4 CONNECTIONS USING V TOPOLOGY

HL5 Nodes are connected to the higher-Level nodes (HL4) with V Topology with Nx1G or Nx10G. HL5s will be located in the FTTH head ends defined as “HL5 head ends”

5.2 Baseline Open 5G Standalone Equivalent Architecture

As stated above, to demonstrate and quantify the techno-economic benefits of DESIRE6G, the baseline needs to be transposed from the current Telefónica 5G NSA of 5.1 into an equivalent 5G Standalone network, leveraging a disaggregated Open RAN based architecture (see 2.2.1) and

The baseline optical transport network will then also be evolved (see 5.1.2) to reflect the addition of RAN fronthaul and midhaul, the local Edge breakout capabilities of a 5GC for relevant scenario environments and an advancement of the SotA of the optical transport technologies to a 5G-Advanced architecture, thereby showcasing the DESIRE6G optical innovations.

5.2.1 5G SA RAN (Radio Access Network) & 5GC

The DESIRE6G evolved baseline is a 5G Standalone (5G Release 15 Phase 2 or Release 16/17) network, with a disaggregated architecture of software defined network functions (CU: Central Unit and DU: Distributed Unit), with many of them deployable on COTS servers, which can be deployed at cell sites or Edge servers, thereby including midhaul transport networks, and with the introduction of the O-RAN Alliance extensions of further disaggregation of RU/DU (RU: Radio Unit, introducing a standardized Split 7.2 eCPRI based fronthaul) and addition of RAN intelligence through the RIC & SMO. Furthermore, the SBA (Service Based Architecture) 5G mobile core (5GC) will support CUPS (Control & User Plane Separation), with Edge UPF (User Plane function) deployments for local breakout (EAS: Edge Application Services), such as at the Edge or Metro DC (Data Centre). A high-level overview of this architecture is illustrated below in Figure 28.

FIGURE 28: D6G BASELINE 5G SA ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW (SUPPORT FOR 5G-NR ONLY, NO LTE)

The RAN CU supports separation of control and user plane functional separation into CU-CP and possibly multiple CU-UP (to support slice or PLMN specific instances of CU-UP, as well as scalability for high volume user plane traffic) with the midhaul (or HLS High Level Split 2) F1 interface correspondingly split between F1-C and F1-U, as illustrated below in Figure 29.

FIGURE 29: FURTHER DISAGGREGATION OF CU INTO CU-CP AND CU-UP (CONTROL AND USER PLANE SEPARATION)

For support of 4G LTE in this evolved 5G Standalone baseline, there are 3 options considered:

1. Support of O-eNB, which is defined by O-RAN Alliance, adding E2 and O1 interfaces to a traditional monolithic eNB (CU/DU with CPRI to RRH), but which will require a dual 4G/5G (EPC/5GC) stack to operate.
2. Disaggregated eNB with the W1 (3GPP Release-15 T2 37.470 [5] and related standards) interface, which standardized the disaggregation of the LTE DU (ng-eNB-DU) to the CU with 5G capabilities (ng-eNB-CU), to allow this eNB to be directly connected to a 5GC in Standalone mode (not requiring a 4G EPC core) and also supporting separation of control and user plane functional separation with W1-C and W1-U (similar to the F1 interface between gNB-CU and gNB-DU) . Despite standardization, there are almost no commercial products supporting this option.
3. For the baseline, map all LTE carriers to equivalent 5G-NR carriers, for a '5G-NR Only' baseline. This option is artificial in that Public MNO networks still need to support LTE, for compatibility of the installed base of older UEs that don't support 5G.

Option 2 (W1 interface between ng-eNB-DU and ng-eNB-CU) has been selected for this D6G equivalent baseline, so the CU in Figure 29 can be interpreted as either being a gNB-CU (disaggregated into gNB-CU-CP and multiple gNB-CU-UP) connected via F1 for a gNB-DU, for 5G-NR, or a ng-eNB-CU connected via W1 to ng-eNB-DU for 4G LTE.

5.2.2 Fixed Transport Network

Although current transport network architecture and redundancy schemes will ensure physical layer connectivity and capacity, Telefonica planning towards fully 5GSA deployments will focus on the capillarization and the de-centralization of some network functionalities.

In addition, special services to be provided by cellular network will have stringent requirements that will require from clear mechanisms for their provisioning, e.g., prioritization and/or any other means that respects net neutrality regulation.

These capabilities should be built on top of what is already included in 5G SA standard

5.2.2.1 Core Network

6G core network should evolve from 5G SA core. This evolution should be smooth and justified by the need of new services and use cases hiding from any additional complexity. SBA architecture should be preserved.

Network Slicing

When analyzing the RAN evolution, providing differential connectivity to satisfy specialized services and additional customer demands is critical. The capabilities to provide differentiation in 6G should be enhanced compared with what it is available in 5G SA. In our opinion, slicing and its evolution should be the way to support differential connectivity required by new use cases.

SBA architecture enhancement

The complete revolution that represented the implementation of SBA architecture have consumed a tremendous effort in our industry. Simplification or enhancement of the core should not mean rebuilding SBA capabilities and its concepts.

SBA should become the network control layer of capabilities across multi domain and technology accesses, core, AI, etc. SBA enhancement should not involve a re-deployment of core network but should be achievable through simple upgrades.

Cloud Nativeness for Life Cycle Management Automation

Automation is a need to increase efficiency and quality of our networks. In the case of the core network, it is key the automation of the life cycle management taking advantage of the cloud native paradigms bringing automation as the implementation CI CD CT pipelines and In-Service Software Upgrades (ISSU) for CNFs.

Platforms and architecture should be able to run over multi cloud environment providing same level of automation. There is a need of Standards for the Infrastructure stack, which will allow this multicloud environment, without spending tireless efforts on certification and deployment. Maybe Open-Source Organizations (e.g. Linux Foundation) should address this task.

5.2.2.2 Packet Core Distribution

As explained in Section 5.1.2.1 the Mobile Core components are always connected to a HL2 transport network element. However, this does not mean that all HL2 Offices contain a Mobile Core instance.

Figure 30 shows that Telefonica will deploy new Mobile Packet Core nodes in new HL2 locations in the next years, reducing the distances to the Base Stations and improving the quality of services related to Round-Trip Time (RTT) latencies

FIGURE 30: TELEFONICA PACKET CORE EXPANSION PLANNING

5.2.2.3 RAN components split with oRAN implementations.

Apart from performance, openness will be another key element. 6G radio should follow the Open RAN principles, allowing elements of the RAN to be sourced from different suppliers and implemented based on O-RAN Alliance interfaces. Additionally, cloudification in 6G RAN should allow bringing all cloud-native principles to the RAN, benefiting for higher scalability, portability and greater automation, which allows to introduce further innovation in the RAN.

Due to Open RAN initiative the split of RU, CU, and DU distribution is being analyzed in many areas of the company, acknowledging the benefits of capacity centralization. Anyway, it seems that the idea in the next years is to maintain the functionalities distributed. What it is clear is that with open RAN the capability of deploying the different functionalities in different parts of the Network could be an enabler to optimize service deployments depending on what the service requires and this way the network

capacity could also be optimized. This functionality split will be further studied in the coming studies in this document.

5.2.2.4 Computing Capacities to the Edge

Currently Telefonica developed services, CDN services and cloud services are hosted in datacenters connected to some of the HL2 Central Offices. In addition to the expansion of the UPF sites shown in Figure 30 there is also a defined plan to extend the EDGE computing capacities closer to the subscribers. This will translate into new computing capabilities deployed from 2025-2028 not only to HL2 network hierarchical levels but also to up to 17 HL4 datacenters. These deployments will be used not only for Telefonica services but also to provide external services closer to the users' terminals in order to improve services latency as well as reducing the volume of the traffic to the transit and interconnection levels.

6. Service Characterization

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a detailed service characterization coming from the descriptive and exhaustive analysis of real traffic measurements from the Telefonica Mobile Network. Specifically, it shows the traffic evolution in a mobile network in the last 5 years, as well as the mapping of different traffic into separated services, showing the difference in the traffic patterns of each service along a week.

For the different technoeconomic studies, the current traffic of mobile networks, the expected DESIRE6G use cases specific traffic profiles, and the current traffic evolution need to be provided as the baseline. In the next sections the traffic evolution, the different traffic trends and the service mapping into services will be described.

6.2 Input Traffic Data

Two data inputs have been requested and analysed from Telefonica mobile network. On the one hand, a data file containing the mobile traffic evolution in the last 5 years has been used to analyze the trend of the traffic growth.

On the other hand, a large data file containing real traffic measurements of Telefónica mobile network along one week has been obtained. The raw traffic data file contains two tabs: the download (DL) traffic from the 100 domains with a highest traffic and the upload (UL) traffic to the top 100 destination domains with the highest traffic load. To be more precise, there are 97 domains per direction and other traffic already grouped by Telefonica, namely “P2P”, “DDoS” and “Other” including the rest of domains and other minority traffic flows. On each of the tabs there is one entry with the average peak traffic per destination taken each half an hour during a whole week, so for each of the destinations there are 336 traffic samples per “flow”, thus, in total there are 33600 registers per direction (Upload-Download)

6.2.1 Traffic evolution

In the last five years, global mobile data traffic has seen significant growth, driven by increased 4G and 5G adoption, and a shift towards more data-intensive applications like video streaming. Mobile devices

have also become a dominant source of internet traffic, surpassing desktops. Despite this significant growth, it can be observed in the graph below that traffic increase trend is not exponential like in the early years of XXI century, but it is a linear growth, with a slope of 27-30% in the last years.

So, even that industry predictions are around 23% annual growth until 2023, for the analysis of some Techno-economical studies, 27-30% yearly increment will be considered.

FIGURE 31: TRAFFIC GROWTH IN TELEFONICA RAN ACCESSES IN THE LAST 5 YEARS

6.2.2 Service Characterization/Categorization

6.2.2.1 Data Input

As explained before in this chapter, the input data received includes

- The total traffic from the RAN Accesses in a week, in slots of 30 minutes (average throughput on each timeslot) both in UL and DL directions
- The traffic to each of the TOP 100 “destinations” in a week, in slots of 30 minutes., both in UL and DL directions.

It can be observed that in both DL and UL traffic there is an error from the traffic analytics platform on 2025/03/13 affecting all the traffic graphs probes.

It can also be seen that the Download graphs of all these traffics are much more “periodic” and repetitive as shown in the next graphic.

FIGURE 32: TRAFFIC GRAPHS FROM TOP 100 DL DOMAINS IN TELEFONICA MOBILE NETWORK

FIGURE 33: TRAFFIC GRAPHS TO TOP 100 UL DOMAINS IN TELEFONICA MOBILE NETWORK

To reduce the number of destinations and get a more useful information we have sorted the traffic in categories. The methodology consisted in searching what is behind each of the origin/destinations of the DL/UL traffic and group them in 10 types of service. This way we have a reduced the flows with a similar nature combining them to see the shaping of those services in the network. From 100 flows we have reduced the scope to 10 categories listed and described in the next sections. The categories of the different traffics were: “Technology”, “IoT”, “Web Browsing”, “Streaming”, “Social Network”, “email”, “Cloud”, “CDN”, “Non-Human Generated Traffic” and “Other”

In order to see the impact of each category in the total amount of traffic in the network the next charts show the % of traffic of each of the categories in the whole week as well as in peak and valley hours.

FIGURE 34: % OF 10 CATEGORIES' TRAFFIC IN THE WHOLE WEEK, IN PEAK HOUR AND IN VALLEY HOUR

6.2.2.1 Categories Description

In this section it is explained how the different streams have been included in the different categories of traffic. The order of the categories has nothing to do with volume of traffic or the number of streams on each category, it is purely alphabetical.

CDN Category Includes:

- Urls containing CDN prefix such as other.cdn.zenlayer.
- Storage services platforms such as onedrive.microsoft.com, drive.amazon.com, drive.google.com, dropbox.com.
- Software updates download URLs: update.apple.com, update.google.com, update.microsoft.com,
- Sites or platforms managing SSL certificates such as ssl.akamai.net, ssl.cloudflare.com, ssl.cloudfront.com, ssl.fastly.com, ssl.fastly.com

Cloud Category Includes:

- All Urls with a cloud. Prefix such as cloud.alibaba.com, cloud.tencent.com, icloud.apple.com
- Cloud apps such office.microsoft.com,
- Other domains offering Cloud computing and cloud services such as other.ovh.com, other.ec2.amazonaws.com, other.fdcservers.net, zscaler.com,
- ssl.s3.amazonaws.com

Email Category Includes:

- Mailing services such as gmail, mail.microsoft.com, other_mail

IoT Category Includes:

- Domains related with BI, Web Analytics and AI
- Geolocating services such as google maps, findmy.icloud.apple.com
- Telemetry services such as telemetry.tesla.com

Non-Human Generated Category Includes:

- DL is basically the traffic classified by Telefónica as P2P
- UL, besides p2p, also includes traffic from devices without human interaction such as fitbit.com, push.apple.com, etc

Other Category Includes:

- Other Categorized traffic, rest of traffic from total
- UL also includes Malware categorized traffic

Social Network Category Includes:

- Messaging and media sharing platforms such as whatsapp, telegram, teams, reddit

- Social Network apps Content oriented such as instagram, tiktok, facebook, snapchat, pinterest

Streaming Category Includes:

- Video Streaming sites and services such as, appleTV, netflix, twitch, prime video, dazn, video.facebook.com
- TV Streaming like OrangeTV, MovistarTV, atresmedia, rtve.es
- Gaming platforms: playstation, roblox, epicgames, discord
- Music Streaming such as iTunes or Spotify,
- Adult websites
- Audio/Video conference services such as, meet, skype, zoom...
- Other domains with video services relation such as video surveillance service platforms

Technology Category Includes:

- Services for web developers including
- Online tools for video editing, graphic design
- Business Intelligence analytics
- Google APIS for developers to connect with google services,
- Certificate validation services

Web Browsing Category Includes:

- Web Stores URLs and search engines (including for example www.google.com, www.apple.com, amazon.com)
- Advertisement services and platforms such as ads.google.com, taboola.com, ads.google.com
- DNS traffic and Safe/secure browsing including VPNs, TLS,

6.2.2.1 Aggregated Classes

As explained in the previous section the 100 traffic volumes have been categorized in different “services”. With a detailed visual analysis of those “service” traffic patterns it is possible to group them into classes, on which the different categories can be grouped taking in account the traffic patterns independently of the traffic volume.

Class A (CDN & Others)

As it can be seen in the following graphs (more clearly in DL graph) all these categories show a similar behaviour with very significant “peaks” of traffic at the same moments of the days and in the same moments of the week. Categories included with this pater are (CDN, Cloud, Non-Human Traffic and Other)

FIGURE 35: CLASS A DL TRAFFIC

FIGURE 36: CLASS A UL TRAFFIC

In the Upload vision, all categories maintain a similar silhouette except for Cloud Services Category which shows a very constant profile almost 24hrs a day due to automatic storage services like Apple’s, Google’s, Microsoft’s or Amazon’s “drive” backup systems.

Besides the silhouette of the traffics, it can be observed that for “CDN” category the DL is up to 20 times the UL, for “Other” category the UL is almost 10 times the UL and for the “non Human traffic” the DL Peaks are much higher than the UL but in general, the volume difference between both directions is much smaller.

Class B (Entertainment)

Removing “CDN”, “Cloud”, “NonHuman traffic” and “Other” categories clear similarities are shown between “Social Network”, “Streaming”, and “Web Browsing” Services profiles. As depicted in the next graphs it can be detected that the peaks of these traffics are all after office hours, being the Streaming the one with the latest peak or demand and the Web browsing the only one which slightly reduces the demand during the weekends.

FIGURE 37: CLASS B DL TRAFFIC

FIGURE 38: CLASS B UL TRAFFIC

Regarding the volumetry, and comparing with the previous group of services, it can be seen that traffic quantities are much higher. It can also be seen that for “Streaming” the relation between DL/UL is extreme (50x), for “Social Network” this relation decreases a lot (around 10x) and finally for “Web Browsing” Category the difference is even smaller (5x).

Class C (Tech)

Finally, It can be clearly observed that “Technology”, “email” & “IoT” show a similar pattern, with highest traffic in the first hours of the day and decreasing along the rest of the days. It also can be seen that also the email and the IoT graphs have an smaller volume of traffic along the weekends.

FIGURE 39: CLASS C DL TRAFFIC

FIGURE 40: CLASS C UL TRAFFIC

6.2.3 AI Analysis

As the previous categorization was made manually by searching for the service behind the domain of each traffic, and it was difficult to visually compare each of the traffic flows with the rest (100 in total), an alternative approach has been performed using an AI Analysis.

With the traffic dataset input in Excel file format, all domains were given an identifier (to preserve Telefonica confidentiality and avoid the AI to use context information) and the DL and UL Traffic excel sheets were attached to an AI (Perplexity Pro) and requested to analyze the different traffic patterns and group them in 10 different clusters (from A to J).

The AI also analyzed the flows and grouped (not all) them in categories identifying patterns such as:

- Peak hours (e.g., work-related traffic vs. night-time traffic)
- Daly seasonality
- Temporal Consistency

After receiving the AI results the identifiers were substituted again by their domains and the traffic could be analyzed.

- In the next tables, a result of the AI clustering for UL and DL traffics is shown.

- The second column shows the main domains of each cluster,
- The third column shows the categories where those domains were classified in the previous subsection of this chapter
- The last column shows an evaluation of each cluster. A visual review of all graphs contained on each cluster has been carried out. Some of them have very similar traffic patterns but others have really different shapes or patterns. The Evaluation Criteria for each AI Cluster has been:
 - 0: Non or almost none of the traffic patterns are similar
 - 1: Few traffic patterns are similar
 - 2: Most of the traffic patterns are similar to the rest
 - 3: All or almost all the patterns are very similar

TABLE 8: AI DL TRAFFIC CLUSTERING

Cluster	Main Domain Examples	Domain Based Main Categories	Quality (0-3)
A	atresmedia.com, discord.com, image.netflix.com, max.com, rtve.es, netflix.com, playstation.com, twitch.tv, plus.disney.com	Gaming and Streaming	3
B	icloud.apple.com, instagram.com, itunes.apple.com, mask.icloud.apple.com, ns.apple.com, oppomobile.com, other	Cloud, Social Network and Streaming	1
C	tv.apple.com	Streaming	3
D	flumotion.com, tritondigital.com, update.google.com	Technology, Streaming and CDN	2
E	pornhub.com, reddit.com, reflected.net, xhamster.com, advancedhosters.com, xvideos.com,	Web Browsing (advancedhosters.com, CDN and Streaming (Adult))	2-3
F	dailymotion.com, gmail.com, googletagmanager.com, linkedin.com, mail.microsoft.com, maps.apple.com, media.amazon.com	Streaming, Email, Social Network and Technology	0-1

G	other.cloudflare.com, other.fdcservers.net, p2p, r2.cloudflare.com, ver.movistarplus.es, dazn.com, orangetv.orange.es	Clod, Streaming and Non-Human Traffic	2-3
H	Mediaset.es	Streaming	3
I	ssl.cloudfront.com, x.com, tiktok.com, valve.com, ssl.fastly.com, ssl.s3.amazonaws.com, telegram.org,	CDN, Cloud Social Network and Gaming	1-2
J	facebook.com	Social Network	3

TABLE 9: AI UL TRAFFIC CLUSTERING

Cluster	Main Domain Examples	Domain Based Main Categories	Quality (0-3)
A	tiktok.com, unity3d.com, weather.com, apple.com, whatsapp.com, applovin.com, capcut.com, video.facebook.com,	Social Network, Gaming, Streaming, Web Browsing and Technology	0-1
B	drive.google.com, netgear.com	CDN and Web Browsing	2-3
C	ssl.s3.amazonaws.com, telemetry.tesla.com	Cloud and IoT	0
D	fitbit.com, google.com, googletagmanager.com, itunes.apple.com, kinesis.amazonaws.com, linkedin.com, maps.apple.com	Non-Human Traffic, Web Browsing, Technology, Streaming, IoT and Social Network	1-2
E	canva.com, dropbox.com, gmail.com, gpc.paloaltonetworks.com, mail.microsoft.com, meet.google.com	Technology, CDN, email, Web Browsing, and Streaming	1-2
F	Een.com (cloud based Video surveillance)	Streaming	3

G	icloud.apple.com, ns.apple.com	Cloud and Web Browsing	2
H	image.netflix.com, netflix.com, rtve.es, twitch.tv, discord.com, facetime.apple.com	Streaming and gaming (discord)	2
I	other game, other.cdn.zenlayer, p2p, push.apple.com, relay.icloud.apple.com, ssl.cloudflare.com, telegram.org	Other, CDN, Web Browsing, Non Human Traffic and Gaming	1-2
J	Bytedance.com (tiktok hosting)	Social Network	3

6.3 Conclusions

After these two approaches to traffic categorization, we can draw some conclusions

1. Domain Based Classification is complicated and may lead to the following issues:
 - a. Not all the time the description of the domains is clear, and it is difficult to guess which services are behind the domain
 - b. Different arguments can make one domain to be classified in one category or another. Some categories are very related and therefore some services could be classified in different categories. Most significant examples are with CDN and Cloud services or Social Network and Streaming categories.
 - c. Last, but not least, some domains (e.g., apple.com or amazon.com) have different kinds of services and different kinds of traffic. Deciding where to classify them is sometimes a subjective decision.
2. Reviewing the AI analysis based on traffic patterns, it can be seen that it is not always very accurate.
 - a. Some clusters look really good but some others do not
 - b. In some cases, clusters with just a few traffic flows are not well designed and some of the traffics show clear differences.

- c. It can be seen that in many cases the AI showed a better performance classifying DL traffic than UL traffic.

7. Descriptive Techno-Economic Analysis

This section describes the main expected benefits in terms of techno-economic related metrics (costs and revenues) of the different innovations and components designed, developed, and tested in DESIRE6G. It is organized following the main layers described in D2.2. This will help to introduce the different numerical studies conducted in the ongoing chapters.

Moreover, it presents the proposed techno-economic description template to help describing and clarifying the impact, scope, and expected results of each of the numerical studies

7.1 Programmable Data Plane Layer

Figure 41 highlights the programmable data plane layer and its main components. Next subsections are devoted to introduce the expected benefits of main components in this layer, as well as those components whose benefits are expected to have large impact in this layer.

FIGURE 41: PROGRAMMABLE DATA PLANE LAYER IN THE D6G ARCHITECTURE

7.1.1 Benefits from hardware acceleration

To meet the stringent performance requirements of next-generation networks, DESIRE6G leverages hardware accelerators to enhance the throughput and latency performance of both network and

application functions. These accelerators enable the offloading of computationally intensive tasks from general-purpose processors to specialized hardware (e.g., FPGAs, GPUs, ASICs, DPUs, smartNICs). This approach improves efficiency, supports scalability, and ensures consistent performance across diverse workloads.

In the D6G concept it is assumed that different variants of certain Network Functions (NFs) or different implementations of specific NF functionality may exist on the data plane (DP) to provide more customized performance for specific services, as shown in Figure 42.

FIGURE 42: DIFFERENT VARIANTS FOR DP IMPLEMENTATION THAT CAN BE USED IN PACKET CORE NETWORKS

In WP4 we have proposed infrastructure support for hardware acceleration. One of the core components of IML is the Control Plane Proxy, that serves as a separation layer between the data and control planes of packet processing NFs as described in Section 5.2 of D4.2. [6]. Its primary role is to enable data plane optimization, including rearrangement, aggregation, or disaggregation of P4 programs in a manner that remains invisible to the upper layers. With the Control Plane Proxy, it thus becomes possible to deploy and use multiple types of HW accelerated DP components. The Control Plane Proxy separates the data plane optimization logic from the network function logic, enabling the network function developers to solely concentrate on the functionality to be implemented, and thus reducing the complexity and cost of network function component development.

Yet another supportive framework for hardware acceleration developed in D6G is vAccel. The vAccel framework is designed to facilitate seamless access to diverse hardware accelerators in remote or cloud environments. Unlike traditional hardware acceleration frameworks, which often rely on specific libraries or hardware calls, vAccel abstracts functionality to expose high-level, application-specific operations (e.g., image classification, object detection), rather than low-level calls (e.g., CUDA or OpenCL).

This approach provides applications with a uniform, easy-to-use interface, regardless of the underlying hardware, making it suitable for deployment across various edge devices (e.g., NVIDIA Jetson, Raspberry Pis, Smart NICs and switches etc.) and cloud servers. At its core, vAccel provides a dispatch handler mechanism that maps application-level API calls to the appropriate underlying plugin, seamlessly integrating with different accelerators without requiring application modification. By focusing on high-level operations, vAccel empowers developers to harness hardware acceleration without direct dependency on any single accelerator library.

The hardware accelerators may enhance the throughput and latency performance of both network and application functions. These accelerators enable the offloading of computationally intensive tasks from general-purpose processors to specialized hardware (e.g., FPGAs, GPUs, ASICs, DPUs, smartNICs). This approach improves efficiency (including energy efficiency), supports scalability, and ensures consistent performance across diverse workloads.

One example assessment of the achievable benefits with using hardware acceleration coupled with the cloud-native NF-DP infrastructure components for load optimization is done later in Chapter 11.

7.1.2 Benefits from application acceleration

The D6G project has developed the SOL Server as a means for AI model acceleration. The SOL Server improves on some important KPIs, like model training latency or inferences per second, which ultimately results in a lower power consumption. Besides, using SOL server could also result in more energy-efficient network operation, see the assessment in Section 12.

We have also integrated the P4 code generation tool P4RROT that aims at supporting application logic (e.g., sensor stream processing, low level control processes) offloading to the data plane. By providing low response times on dedicated hardware, P4RROT may also enable new operator services in the area of network compute offload. P4RROT's response time relies on the executing data plane target. For a sensor stream processing example, on Tofino Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) the response time was below 1 usec, while on a Netronome Agilio smartNIC it was between 50-80 usecs. In both cases, the observed jitter was not significant [7].

7.1.3 Benefits from the INT framework

Among others, in WP4 we have proposed novel approaches for

- Telemetry collector that enables for in-network control, i.e., very short network reaction times through decisions taken at the data plane. This can again increase service reliability.
- P4 In-band Network Telemetry on UE: enables end-to-end service KPI measurement and verification (e.g., latency), opening the way for new type of operator services, where the service guarantees are end-to-end, rather than edge-to-edge
- RAN telemetry exposure, improving the network observability by providing RAN-related telemetry information.

By these new features, the monitoring framework proposed in the D6G project could open the way for new Operator services, or cost reduction of the current ones, i.e., by providing less redundancy with similar service KPIs and increasing the automatism in operating the network. Besides, the time-to-repair in the network also improves by detecting the problem earlier (e.g., which switch has the problem etc). Also, from the monitoring data-lake one can have an experimental validation of time-to-failure.

We note that the monitoring framework also provides the necessary KPIs for the higher, optimization and network control layer functionality, see section 7.2.

7.1.4 Benefits from the novel traffic management methods

In the WP4 activity, new traffic management solutions have been designed to provide performance isolation for supporting deep slicing. State-of-art mechanisms may increase latency and computational load, which can disrupt high-throughput, low-latency applications. Solutions often involve trade-offs, like grouping users or using approximate methods, to balance scalability with practical performance. For example, service guarantees for multi-tenancy could be achieved by separately provisioning for each tenant. With the proposed methods, the probability of resource guarantees increases for the same provisioned capacity, thus a better usage of network capacity becomes possible. The reduced provisioned capacity will then result in reduced cost for providing the same services for a multi-tenant system. The traffic management solution is used in the digital twin demo to isolate the traffic of different slices and users. A numerical assessment of capacity reduction may be found in Chapter 11.

7.2 Optimization and Network Control Layer

Figure 43 highlights the optimization and network control layer and its main components. Next subsections are devoted to introduced the expected benefits of main components in this layer, as well as those components whose benefits are expected to have large impact in this layer.

FIGURE 43: OPTIMIZATION AND NETWORK CONTROL LAYER IN THE D6G ARCHITECTURE

7.2.1 Benefits from MAS

Autonomous network operations supported by Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) within the DESIRE6G architecture promise substantial benefits in terms of CAPEX, summarized as follows:

- *Optimized Infrastructure Utilization:* MAS allows for fine-grained, service-specific decision-making, including routing and resource allocation, which improves infrastructure efficiency. Better utilization of existing network assets reduces the need for over-provisioning or premature hardware investments.
- *Reduced Need for Centralized Hardware Scaling:* Instead of relying solely on centralized orchestration systems, MAS shifts decision-making closer to the edge. This decentralization minimizes the demand for scaling up centralized compute infrastructure, contributing to lower upfront investments.

- *Flexible Service Deployment:* With dynamic, AI-driven orchestration via MLFO and MAS (see more details in Section 7.3.4), services can be instantiated on demand, reducing the need for statically deployed, dedicated hardware resources.

In terms of OPEX, MAS contributes to overall benefits and savings in the following ways:

- *Near-Real-Time Decision Making Reduces Operational Overhead:* MAS performs continuous, autonomous optimizations (e.g., flow rerouting, delay budgeting) based on live telemetry. This eliminates the need for frequent manual interventions and reduces costs related to network tuning and troubleshooting.
- *Lower Fault Management and SLA Violation Penalties:* Proactive monitoring and service assurance by MAS help identify and resolve issues locally and rapidly. This minimizes service disruptions, which in turn lowers penalty costs associated with SLA breaches.
- *Energy Efficiency and Cost Savings:* By enabling adaptive scaling and offloading (e.g., load balancing using packet and optical networks), MAS supports dynamic resource allocation that can significantly reduce energy consumption, a major OPEX component.
- *Streamlined Network Management:* MAS offloads routine and near-real-time tasks from centralized controllers, allowing human operators to focus on strategic management, thereby improving operational efficiency.
- *Security and Resilience with Lower Maintenance Needs:* Built-in security measures like mutual attestation and ledger-backed trust mechanisms reduce the frequency and severity of attacks or faults, leading to reduced downtime and associated costs. Extended analysis on security aspects is detailed in next section.

Therefore, MAS within DESIRE6G is not just a technical innovation—it also provides a transformative economic model for 6G networks by balancing distributed intelligence with centralized orchestration, yielding both cost efficiency and scalability.

7.2.2 Benefits from secure remote attestation and runtime integrity verification

DESIRE-6G's D-MUTRA blockchain-based mutual remote attestation brings about several operational and security benefits to workload operators. First, on the operational side, workload operators are relieved from the risky, meticulous and time-sensitive operations of (i) reference measurement and

signing key management, (ii) pre-deployment verification of the targeted platform with all required dependencies. As a result, remote attestation is made possible at far less DevSecOps efforts and expertise requests. The operational gain can be simply qualified as “making SDOs recommended remote attestation of networking workloads practicable and at no operational costs”. The relaxation of operational tasks makes remote attestation possible even when dealing with short-lived workloads such as ML models as it has been demonstrated with dynamically-generated MAS agents in DESIRE-6G. Finally, storing the attestation results in the blockchain brings immutability and transparency to permissioned stakeholders, leveraging the strengths of the blockchain in a very sustainable way (i.e., memory consumption). On the security aspect, D-MUTRA’s brings distributed and continuous security, highly valued benefits compared to the centralized and static measurement offered by the state of the art. The distribution of the verification prevents DoS attacks against a centralized remote attestation verifier, aligned with the distributed security concept of the blockchain and offers a change of paradigm in software security. With D-MUTRA, any workloads take part of the verification of its peers. Software security is worked out in a collective and unpredictable manner, making the attack more complex. Last, D-MUTRA ‘s continuous workload integrity provides workload security without the elevated constraints and risks of TEE (e.g., DoS attacks by system freeze incumbent to TEE hard-lock policy, undetectable vulnerable code exploit, memory and processor overconsumption). The solution is aimed at delivering a minimal performance penalty of less than 1% to all payloads while they are constantly verified and without imposing dependency (i.e., TEE), a bottleneck in workload deployment.

Here again, the solution can be qualified as “offering continuous software integrity without imposing deployment restriction, computational and memory heavy costs”

7.2.3 Benefits from workload self-monitoring

First, DESIRE-6G’s workload self-monitoring obviates the installation of external dependencies for monitoring, thus permitting to collect metrics without check on the execution environment. Noticeably, when using cloud managed services, the installation of these dependencies requires administrative rights that the operator may not granted for. Third, the solution removes measurement biases caused by the monitoring itself, typically significant performance penalty. Third, the solution assesses the execution environment stress level without any administrative right on the platform.

7.3 Intent-Based Orchestration Layer

Figure 44 highlights the intent-based orchestration layer and its main components. Next subsections are devoted to introduced the expected benefits of main components in this layer, as well as those components whose benefits are expected to have large impact in this layer.

FIGURE 44: INTENT BASED ORCHESTRATION LAYER IN THE D6G ARCHITECTURE

7.3.1 Benefits from SO

The SO implementation within the DESIRE6G SMO framework enables secure, modular, and scalable lifecycle management of services across the continuum. The orchestrator exposes a RESTful interface via FastAPI for service deployment, retrieval, and deletion, with RabbitMQ facilitating asynchronous communication between SMO components. This design choice ensures loosely coupled services, resilience in case of failure, and scalable inter-service messaging.

The SO coordinates with the infrastructure management layer (IML) to manage service instantiation, relying on shared data models and standardized formats (JSON/YAML) to ensure compatibility. Each service request—expressed as a service ID and site ID—is handled through specific and documented endpoints (POST /service, DELETE /service/{id}, GET /deployed_services, etc.), ensuring full lifecycle

visibility. Real-time data updates are propagated through the message bus, improving responsiveness and integration with intent-based components and the optimization engine.

The integration of the SO with the Topology and Service Catalog components of SMO supports accurate resource selection and validation against site-specific capabilities, streamlining the orchestration process. The underlying use of S3 storage for model and data blob persistence and Kafka for telemetry streaming supports advanced AI/ML operations downstream while decoupling the SO from direct data processing responsibilities.

Overall, the SO's role contributes to efficient resource allocation, reliable service instantiation, and continuous synchronization with dynamic topology states and deployment catalogs supporting intent translation, automation of SLA-based service instantiation, and federated multi-site deployment—all crucial to achieving the programmability and performance guarantees foreseen in DESIRE6G.

7.3.2 Benefits from IBN and SLA-to-Intent Translation

A fully autonomous network can adapt its requirements on its own, without human help. To build such a network, intents must be used across different parts of the network architecture—such as the business, service, and resource layers.

Today's telecom networks mostly offer general services, while private networks provide more customized options at a higher cost. With 5G and 6G enabling new use cases like XR and COBOTs, there is a growing need for more specific and reliable services. This makes Service Level Agreements (SLAs) more important, as they help clearly define customer needs and ensure the network can meet them.

Under WP3, we presented a study on receiving service requests from the customer and initiating them either as new services or by matching them with existing ones. This work is based on transitioning to an intent-based service architecture, where the customer's request is delivered to the SMO layer as an intent—focusing only on what is needed, while leaving the how part to the automated network management.

The SLA-to-Intent translation function improves the interaction between the customer and the CSP by making service requirements clearer and more accurate. By automating what was previously a manual

process, it reduces the need for human effort, speeds up service delivery, increases CSP revenue, and enhances customer satisfaction through intelligent handling.

At the same time, we collaborated with other components in the SMO to map high level customer requests received through IBN to existing services and then decompose them for lower network layers. This is an important step toward enabling a zero-touch network and supports faster operations and cost reduction through automation.

These technologies reduce the service activation time from ten to fifteen days in manual processes to one to two days with automation, which lowers revenue loss and reduces operational workload.

7.3.3 Benefits from Optimization Engine

Autonomous network optimization is crucial due to the complexity, scale, and stringent performance associated with next-generation network services. To manage these requirements, modern networks must autonomously handle resource allocation within the infrastructure, performing continuous optimization before, during, and after service deployment to consistently deliver the expected performance levels.

For network services, a comprehensive optimization framework is necessary to dynamically determine optimal configurations, align with infrastructure capabilities and resource availability. Network services optimization is necessary for providing ultra-reliable and adaptive services that efficiently utilize network infrastructure resources across a diverse set of use cases. Optimization plays a pivotal role at all lifecycle stages: pre-deployment, during operation, and post-deployment. It can leverage predictive placement strategies, real-time adjustments, automated node scaling, fault recovery, etc.

A general, AI-driven optimization framework can address multiple optimization dimensions simultaneously and provide scalable and adaptive orchestration throughout the entire service lifecycle. This holistic approach significantly reduces operational costs and resource expenditure while consistently maintaining high performance standards.

In WP3, we introduced the Optimization Engine (OE), an AI-based optimization framework. The OE receives annotated service graph requests specifying the Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and Service Level Objectives (SLOs) and then selects an optimal model from a diverse pool of available optimization

models. The selection is performed algorithmically or with Large Language Models (LLMs), as they can extract context from textual data, such as optimization code and network service requests efficiently. Custom prompts can direct the LLM towards internal Chains of Thought (CoTs) that lead to a comparison and decision of the best optimization algorithm to be used. The selected model uses the annotated information to perform targeted, context-aware service optimization.

General optimization frameworks, such as the OE are a great step towards zero-touch orchestration, as it positions network providers to proactively address the dynamic demands of future network environments and ensure high-quality service delivery and efficient resource utilization.

7.3.4 Benefits from MLFO

The Machine Learning Function Orchestrator (MLFO) within the DESIRE6G framework provides distinct CAPEX and OPEX advantages by optimizing the deployment and operation of AI/ML pipelines that support autonomous service management. MLFO, as enabler of MAS, is responsible for deploying, configuring, and securing MAS agents across sites. Therefore, any cost efficiency achieved via MAS-like distributed intelligence or localized optimization—depends on MLFO's orchestration. Indeed, MLFO ensures that MAS agents are deployed only where needed, avoiding unnecessary compute/resource reservation. In turn, MAS handles service assurance and localized optimization, creating a feedback loop that continuously improves resource use and operational efficiency.

Related with CAPEX reduction, MLFO contributes with the following features:

- *Efficient Resource Allocation for AI/ML Tasks:* MLFO computes optimal placement of ML functions (e.g., data collectors, processors, aggregators) across edge and core infrastructure by solving placement optimization problems. This minimizes resource usage (containers/VMs, compute nodes, bandwidth), thereby reducing the need for excess hardware provisioning
- *Support for Service-Specific AI Pipelines:* By orchestrating only the required AI modules on demand and associating them with specific services, MLFO enables targeted and minimal deployment, avoiding blanket infrastructure expansion.
- *Integration with Lightweight Execution Environments:* Demonstrations using unikernels show MLFO can deploy hardened AI functions with significantly reduced CPU, memory, and storage

footprints, allowing operators to delay or reduce investments in high-capacity compute infrastructure

Moreover, in terms of OPEX, MLFO is expected to contribute with benefits and savings as follows:

- *Autonomous Lifecycle Management:* MLFO automates the deployment, monitoring, and reconfiguration of AI/ML pipelines, drastically reducing manual operational labor and associated costs.
- *Dynamic Reconfiguration Reduces Downtime and Intervention:* in response to network or service changes, MLFO can dynamically reconfigure pipelines with minimal disruption, enhancing uptime and lowering costs related to SLA violations and fault recovery
- *Secure and Federated Operations:* MLFO leverages DLT to securely manage inter-agent communication and software integrity checks, reducing security incident overhead and maintenance costs associated with centralized verification systems
- *Energy and Carbon Cost Optimization:* by choosing optimal deployment points and algorithms, MLFO reduces computation and communication energy costs, helping contain energy-related OPEX while also improving sustainability

Hence, MLFO, as the central orchestrator of AI/ML intelligence, is crucial for realizing the financial and operational efficiency of the DESIRE6G vision. It maximizes the return on AI-native 6G by automating intelligence deployment across both centralized and edge domains.

7.4 Techno-economics description template

For the sake of a better organization and to facilitate the understanding of the ongoing techno-economic studies, the following template is proposed as a requirement to be included in each of the ongoing chapters:

TABLE 10: TECHNO-ECONOMIC STUDY DESCRIPTION TEMPLATE

Field	Value
Name	<i>Name of the study</i>

Description	<i>Brief description</i>
Layers / Components	<i>Which D6G innovation tackles this study</i>
Benchmarking	<i>To which benchmarking you should compare with</i>
Use case	<i>Is this oriented/focused on a particular DESIRE6G use case/s? or applies to a broad range of use cases/ services?</i>
KPI/KVI	<i>Is targeting a well-defined KPI and/or KVI?</i>
Methodology	<i>Briefly explain the methodology: algorithms, simulations, cost models, etc.</i>

The table includes the name and a short description of the study. Then, the DESIRE6G layers and/or components that are specifically targeted are listed, as well as the benchmarking technologies/scenarios to perform fair and valuable evaluation. In case that the study applies to a specific use case, it is detailed, as well as those KPI/KVI that are the main focus of the study. Finally, a brief explanation of the used methodology is described.

8. Characterization of DESIRE6G services

8.1 Abstract

In Chapter 6, it was explained how the traffic from Telefonica Mobile Network has been compiled, and the two classification methods. The “manual” characterization/categorization, where the traffics were grouped by the main service behind its own domain (it was explained that sometimes can be tricky and subjective), and the AI “clustering” where Perplexity Pro classified in 10 different clusters or categories (A-J) the anonymized traffics from/to each domain.

In this chapter, the functional requirements and the KPIs related to traffic of each of DESIRE6G use cases described in D.2.1 [8] has been considered and analysed, and a characterization of each of the use case traffic (UL and DL) using the categories defined in Chapter 6 has been performed.

8.2 Description Template

TABLE 11: AI-BASED CHARACTERIZATION STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>Characterization of DESIRE6G services</i>
Description	<i>Each use case download and upload traffic has been characterized according to the traffic classification performed in chapter 6</i>
Layers / Components	<i>Using AI for traffic characterization based on Upload and download traffic patterns</i>
Benchmarking	<i>4G/5G traffic scenarios (used as reference starting point)</i>
Use case	<i>All 6G use cases described in D2.1</i>
KPI/KVI	<i>KPI: Mainly focused on bandwidth, although other metrics such as latency and reliability are considered.</i>

	<i>KVI: Economical sustainability.</i>
Methodology	<i>For each use case the Functional Requirements and the traffic KPIs has been considered and mapped to Chapter 6 “Manual” Service Classification by traffic nature. In addition, the same functional requirements and traffic KPIs has been provided to an AI (Perplexity pro) along with an excel sheet with all traffic flows of Telefonica Mobile Network in a week, requesting the AI to match the DESIRE6G service UL and DL traffics to any of the real flows of the operator’s network.</i>

8.3 D6G Use Cases

This section contains an analysis/description of the different traffics expected to be obtained in the 5 use cases presented in Deliverable “D2.1 Definition of Use Cases, Service Requirements and KPIs/KVIs”

8.3.1 AR/VR Use Case

As described in D2.1, “this use case has the goal to test an “Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality (AR/VR) in a drone-human operator cooperation scenario” aiming surveillance and inspection applications.”

Obviously, the end traffic will flow between the operator’s headset and the own drone and passing through the different network nodes

FIGURE 45: AR/VR USE CASE TRAFFIC FLOW

One of the objectives is “to provide steady data streaming between the operator’s headset and the drone, with perceived zero latency”, so the two/three main requirements for this AR/VR use case, in terms of Traffic needs are

- Relative high Bandwidth in DL direction: Depending on the video features (resolution, fps, field of view). Camera streams from UAV and/or fixed camera: 50-100Mbps (4K 60fps HEVC265). Streams to the Headset: min 130Mbps – max 960Mbps,
- Ultra Low Latency between the operator’s headset, the application’s components and the Drones. 5ms for the network delay <20ms total (ideal), <50 ms total (tolerated)
- Resiliency (extracted from D2.1): The application should be resilient, meaning that should grant stable and continuous communication, in any possible application scenario for the use case.

8.3.2 Digital Twin Use Case

This USE case describes how robots will be controlled in real-time remotely by a virtual remote controller or fully autonomous algorithms that reside in the Edge as part of the Digital Twin application. Robot sensor information (e.g., lidar, camera, odometry, joint states) is sent upstream to update the virtual models in real-time, while control instructions about the robot pose will be sent downstream to navigate the robots.

FIGURE 46: BASIC LOGIC BEHIND ROBOT DT

In terms of communications and traffic needs, the main requirements of this use case are

- Low-latency Radio Access Technologies for connecting the robots (Wi-Fi6, 5G)
- Ultra Low Latency between the operators interface (or the digital twin app), the application's components and the Real Robots in the factory. 5ms for the network delay <20ms total (ideal), <50 ms total (tolerated)

8.3.3 Intelligent Image Monitoring Use Case

This use case relies on communication between machines and sensors to operate smoothly and autonomously, e.g. in Factories. Sensors can be simple, like thermometers, or more complex, like cameras and lidar, all of which need efficient data transmission. Transmitting high-resolution video streams can strain the network and increase costs, so a stable wireless solution is needed.

Currently, many factories use wired networks, which are costly and hard to reconfigure. With the advent of 5G and future 6G networks, wireless communication is improving, offering reliable, low-latency options. Not all cameras need to stream data constantly; the network can filter and reduce unnecessary video quality based on high-level rules set by operators, helping to optimize bandwidth and keep the network stable

FIGURE 47: IMAGE MONITORING SYSTEM OVERVIEW

In terms of communications and traffic needs, the main requirements of this use case are

- Low-latency Radio Access Technologies for connecting the sensors, video streams and robots. (Wi-Fi6, 5G) Variable Bandwidth Video Streaming (10-50Mbps per active camera) depending on the applied video encoding)

8.3.4 Latency Sensitive Robot Control Use Case

This use case aims to achieve a few key things:

- managing both real-time (immediate response needed) and non-real-time (less urgent) control processes for robotic arms from the edge cloud, bringing processing closer to the machines.
- ensuring that the edge computing infrastructure can handle real-time control tasks reliably, even under strict requirements like ultra-low latency and minimal jitter.
- allowing the system to scale reasonably by increasing computational resources and energy consumption as needed. Lastly, keeping real-time control processes isolated from each other and from less urgent tasks to ensure smooth, safe, and efficient operation.

FIGURE 48: REAL TIME AND NON-REAL TIME COMPONENTS RUNNING IN THE EDGE COMPUTING INFRASTRUCTURE

In terms of communications and traffic needs, the main requirement of this use case is

- Low Latency (0.5 – 10 ms)

8.3.5 Cloud Rendered Gaming Use Case

In this use case, the user only executes a thin client and the game application itself runs at a remote location (e.g., edge cloud) as depicted in Figure 49

FIGURE 49: CLOUD RENDERED GAMING SCENARIO

In terms of communications and traffic needs, the main requirements of this use case are

- high throughput (e.g., 4K or 8K video streams) 10Mbps to 150 Mbps (per gamer user)
- low latency: 20-30 ms for the latency budget of the network Note that RTT less than 150ms results in acceptable gaming experience, but good user experience requires <120 ms.

8.4 DESIRE6G UC Categorization Methodology

For each use case the Functional Requirements and the traffic KPIs has been considered and mapped to Chapter 6 “Manual” Service Classification by traffic nature. In addition, the same functional requirements and traffic KPIs has been provided to an AI (Perplexity pro) along with an excel sheet with all traffic flows of Telefonica Mobile Network in a week, requesting the AI to match the DESIRE6G service UL and DL traffics to any of the real flows of the operator’s network.

8.5 Results

8.5.1 Human-based approach

Analyzing the traffic requirements of each use case it can be seen that for DL direction one of the main constraints is the Realtime Video. So, for all those profiles the category Streaming has been selected, probably the most similar traffic (in terms of volume) would be the Video Conferencing streams such in Microsoft teams, Skype, Zoom, etc but with an assured low latency and a high resilience requirements not provided in those services nowadays.

In the case of UL traffic, the main constraint of the services is the necessity of ultra-low latency, and service assurance and resiliency. These three factors need to be one of the most important areas to improve in the network in order to guaranty the correct provision of 6G Services.

In the next table there is summary of the mapping of the traffic needs of each use case and the possible matching with current services described in previous sections of this chapter.

TABLE 12: SUMMARY OF HUMAN-BASED APPROACH

Use Case	Direction of the Traffic	Low Latency /UL Latency	High/Very High BW	Strict Reliability	Service Mapping
AR/VR	DL	NO	YES	YES	Streaming
	UL	YES	NO	YES	Streaming
Digital Twin	DL	YES	NO	YES	IoT
	UL	YES	NO	YES	IoT
Image Monitoring	DL	NO	YES	YES	Streaming
	UL	YES	NO	YES	Streaming
Robot Control	DL	YES	NO	YES	IoT
	UL	YES	NO	YES	IoT
Cloud Gaming	DL	NO	YES	YES	Streaming
	UL	YES	NO	YES	IoT

In conclusion, the traffics have been mapped to current traffic shapes, but it can be seen that reliability and availability of the traffics is very high compared with current services, so network slicing capabilities as well as elasticity of networks and network programmability is a must for future 6G services to be accomplished with a commercial quality. In order to reduce latency to comply with many of the

DESIRE6G UC traffic flows, it will be very positive to deploy UPF and computing capacity to the edge (HL4 and/or HL3 sites), as explained in Section 5.2.2.

8.5.2 AI-based approach

As explained before in the chapter, we uploaded a Word document with DESIRE6G use cases functional requirements and traffic KPIS. In addition, we also uploaded an Excel sheet with the UL and DL traffics from Telefónica Mobile Network. The AI was requested to analyze the requirements, the traffic patterns and to assign a different traffic pattern for each Use case explaining/justifying the traffic flow selection, and the result is shown in the next table. Details of the selected traffic flows can be found in [9]

TABLE 13: SUMMARY OF AI-BASED APPROACH

Use Case	DL Traffic ID	DL Traffic ID Justification	UL Traffic ID	UL Traffic ID Justification
AR/VR	DL_045 (Other Traffic)	Bandwidth ≥ 500 Mbps (ideal for streaming 3D) Average latency 18 ms	UL_012 (caixabank.es)	QoS prioritization for interactive commands with a latency ≤ 25 ms
Digital Twin	DL_078 (streaming.amazon.com)	Constant 200 Mbps Throughput and packet loss $\leq 0.05\%$ (accurate sync)	UL_033 (googletagmanager.com)	Continuous Sensor data traffic with a 28.89 Mbps Bandwidth
Image Monitoring	DL_100 (youtube.com)	Stable HD Streaming Caapcity (30 fps)	UL_008 (apple.com)	High volume of data (1.97 Gb/s) and packet loss $\leq 0.08\%$
Robot Control	DL_019 (gmail.com)	Latency =3.2 ms and jitter ≤ 0.8 ms (industrial requirements)	UL_055 (onedrive.microsoft.com)	Latency=3.5 ms y 99.99% reliability
Cloud Gaming	DL_091 (video.facebook.com)	800 Mbps Bandwidth (4K/120 fps)	UL_067 (Roblox.com)	Need of packet prioritization with a latency =28 ms

The most positive outcome from this table, is that values provided by the AI (in terms of traffic volume and latencies) are very close in 90% of the cases to the value ranges proposed by DESIRE6G as functional requirement and traffic KPIs for every UC. What is more surprising is that the values proposed by the AI are not exactly the same as the ones described on each Use Case, so we can assume that the AI has not copied them but has researched other fonts to adjust the requirements for each of the Traffic Flows (being the results really close to those detailed in D2.1 [8]).

On the other hand, although the IDs provided from the AI for high volumes of traffic demand make sense, if we take a look to the IDs proposed for the traffic demands with low volume of traffic demand but with high latency restrictions are not so good. We assume that, as the data sent to the AI in the spreadsheet only has the volume but neither latency nor reliability information, the outcome from the AI is whichever with low traffic volumes.

In conclusion the AI has done a good job in the analysis of the requirements and the approach to what it is needed for the use cases traffic demands (both UL and DL), but due to the lack of parameters in the Excel Sheet the election of the traffic flows has failed for the streams with a lower traffic volume demand, proposing an arbitrary service matching the volume. But AI does not point out that the latency or reliability needs, may not be accomplished with that traffic flow.

8.6 Conclusions

After traffic classifications made by hand (using the domain context) and with the AI support and after analyzing the Service selections made from the AI, our best lesson learnt for traffic classification and traffic characterization for DESIRE6G use cases is that we can rely on AI analysis for the rough classification and the characterization of high volumes traffic flows but for a detailed mapping and characterization of low volumes traffic it is better to know the domain context to eliminate incorrect traffic mappings from the AI.

9. Network resource utilization and cost analysis

9.1 Abstract

As described in the fundamentals of DESIRE6G project, the final objective of this research and innovation action is to design and develop a novel zero-touch control, management, and orchestration platform, with native integration of AI, to support applications with strict requirements over a performant, measurable and deep programable data plane. It is worth mentioning that a kind of infrastructure like this is envisioned as necessary, since 5G systems are expected to fall on meeting the stringent performance requirements of future 6G use cases such as the ones presented in Chapter 8.

However, operators are still on the path of deploying a fully operative 5G SA infrastructure (as explained in Chapter 5). Hence, more advanced technologies such as the ones developed in this project are envisioned for a mid-long term. Thus, we can imagine the situation where more mature 5G SA networks to be reached in the short-term (2-3 years) will be the baseline infrastructure to support the incipient, fast-growing demand of 6G services. In particular, for those dense urban scenarios where the demand of 6G use cases is expected to be high and where resources availability in terms of both bandwidth and computing is large, 5G SA can be a feasible transitory solution. Of course, the lack of dynamicity and flexibility of 5G SA with respect to DESIRE6G solutions will make the former more expensive and inefficient than the latter, even too much restrictive for service critical services such as eXtreme URLLC.

Then, before reaching the inevitable point of collapse of 5G SA infrastructures, the question is to evaluate the expected benefits in terms of cost of adopting DESIRE6G innovations to replace the still operative (but inefficient) 5G SA infrastructures. This chapter presents a numerical evaluation for that goal by means of a simulation study starting from the network and service specifications in Chapters 5, 6, and 8.

9.2 Description Template

TABLE 14: RESOURCE UTILIZATION AND COST ANALYSIS STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>Network resource utilization and cost analysis</i>
Description	<i>Numerical study to evaluate the utilization and associated costs of serving traffic scenarios combining current and 6G services on reference network topologies. The study focuses on network (bandwidth) and computing resources across different hierarchical levels and network segments, for distinct operational modes and cost functions.</i>
Layers / Components	<i>DESIRE6G overall architecture and main innovation components</i>
Benchmarking	<i>5G SA operation</i>
Use case	<i>Services and use cases described in Chapters 6 and 8.</i>
KPI/KVI	<i>Mainly focused on bandwidth, although other metrics such as latency and reliability are indirectly considered.</i>
Methodology	<i>A simulation environment (Python) has been implemented to emulate the operation of a network infrastructure supporting the main functionalities and capabilities of DESIRE6G in support of efficient, flexible, and dynamic managements of services along their lifetime. Modifications to allow a 5G SA operation have been implemented for benchmarking purposes.</i>

9.3 Methodology

For numerical evaluation purposes, we developed a Python-based network simulator that emulates a network infrastructure following the details and characteristics in Chapter 5. In particular, it allows

emulating topologies such as the urban dense one in Figure 23, where a number of BSs are connected to HL4 and HL3 nodes. Moreover, a hierarchical fixed network topology with all the levels specified in Figure 24 provide connectivity between all HLLs, including a gateway for interconnectivity with other networks. Each link connecting two different sites (BS-to-HL or HL-to-HL) is equipped with a bandwidth capacity, whereas sites are equipped with a computing capacity for hosting network functions.

The simulator allows configuring a number of traffic generators that inject traffic according to the real behaviour of currently existing services specified in Chapter 6, as well as the forecasted DESIRE6G use cases presented in Chapter 8. To be more precise, the traffic patterns and time series provided in those chapters are normalized to per-user profiles. Then, a generator is attached to each BS, thus emulating the users that are served from that BS. Each generator is configured then with the total number of users for each of the services, as well as with the normalized per-user traffic profiles (defined in terms of bitrate). In this way, scaling the traffic with time is a straightforward operation.

Besides the normalized per-user traffic profile, each service is characterized by a service graph that includes the disaggregated RAN functions (RU/DU/CU), the 5GC and UPF elements, and a generic processing function that holds the specific tasks of the service, e.g., video processing tasks for the case of AR/VR DESIRE6G use case. The service graphs distinguish between uplink (UL) and downlink (DL), so both directions need to be configured for each service. Moreover, a bitrate scaling factor is specified for each of the virtual links connecting two consecutive functions in a service graph. Note that this is required because traffic volume is not constant along the service graph, e.g., for the same input user traffic, front-haul traffic (between RU and DU) is larger than backhaul one (between CU and 5GC/UPF). For the sake of simplicity, we assume that the computing demand of each function in the service graph is proportional to the traffic that this function processes (receives from previous one and/or forwards to next one).

At a given time t , the simulator manages simultaneously a number of service graphs; each function of the service graph needs to be *assigned* to one site, while each virtual link needs to be assigned to either one physical link or more than one if it bypasses one or more hierarchical level(s). Hence, each service graph consumes a number of resources in terms of computing capacity in sites and bandwidth in physical links. In order to guarantee the proper service performance and to meet QoS requirements, each function and virtual link in the graph needs to have sufficient *allocated* resources in each site and

each physical link it uses. These computing and bandwidth resources are exclusively used by the service and are not shared with other services. From now on in this chapter, the reserved resources for a given service graph at a given time t will be referred as a *service slice*.

At this point, we can distinguish two different operation modes that can be executed in the simulator. The first one is the benchmarking 5G SA approach, where it is assumed that slices remain invariable during the service lifetime, which means that the allocated resources are fixed for the entire duration of the simulation. A simple example of this operation is sketched in Figure 50a. The example shows a service graph in green across multiple sites and network segments. The supporting slice is represented in orange, for both computing resources in sites and bandwidth resources in links. For simplicity, let us assume that the height of the functions and virtual links represent the demand, while the height of slice segments represents the amount of resources reserved to that service. The figure shows two different time steps: t_1 representing a peak hour where demand is high, and t_2 representing a valley hour where demand is low. As can be seen, both the placement of service functions and the allocated resources remain fixed and sufficiently high to guarantee proper service operation during the entire time period.

In 5G SA operation mode, we are assuming that the placement of functions and allocation of resources is performed in a way that guarantees the service and optimizes an overall cost function, i.e., minimizing computing capacity costs and/or bandwidth costs. Although not represented, other services are deployed in different slices in order to efficiently use the remaining capacity resources in sites and physical links. In the context of this project and for the sake of a fair comparison, we are assuming an optimistic 5G SA approach, where slices are tightly dimensioned to ensure the continuous service performance with the minimum overall cost.

In contrast to 5G SA operational mode, the DESIRE6G operational mode is based on all the innovations that allow flexible and dynamic service management, based on multi-timescale control loops, for different phases of the service lifecycle including service creation, deployment, and assurance (see [10] for extended details). Thanks to these capabilities and functionalities, an operation as the one sketched in Figure 50b can be achieved. This figure shows the same service and demand scenario of those in Figure 50a, but operated in a way that allocated resources are reduced when service demand is reduced (and will increase again when needed). More specifically, the example shows that, in time t_2 , service functions can be grouped at BS and HL2 sites, thus releasing the capacity resources previously allocated

in HL4 and HL3 at time t . Moreover, bandwidth in aggregation and transit network segments can be adjusted to a low traffic demand, which saves costs associated to network bandwidth usage.

With the two operational modes implemented, the simulator is configured with one scenario (topology + service demand) and one operational mode and executed for a simulated time duration, e.g., one week. In case of 5G SA approach, the optimal placement is computed in advance. A randomized algorithm finds the placement and allocation of resources of each service (from a set of available deployment options for each service slice) that minimizes the cost for the maximum traffic value. After converging to a stable and minimal cost solution, it stops the optimization, instantiates that best-found solution for all the services, and simulate the operation. In the case of DESIRE6G approach, at every simulated time interval t , the demand is forecasted based on the previous time periods, and the best placement and resource allocation of each service slice (using the same algorithm than that of 5G SA operation) is computed and evaluated. For both cases, the evaluation carried out during the simulation is done in terms of cost and use of resources.

FIGURE 50: SIMULATOR OPERATIONAL MODES: (A) 5G SA VS (B) DESIRE6G

9.4 Results

The innovations of DESIRE6G promise to offer support for challenging 6G services such as eXtreme URLLC applications that cannot be successfully achieved by current 5G SA infrastructures. Under this strict assumption, making a comparison between both DESIRE6G and 5G SA approaches is meaningless, since DESIRE6G benefits cannot be compared against a valid benchmarking. In view of this, in this section we focus on a numerical evaluation in a scenario where a 5G SA system can potentially deal with the expected demand and service requirements. To this aim, we configured our simulator with a network topology based on that of the dense urban presented in Figure 23. Table 15 presents the main parameters of the network in terms of maximum capacity and costs in all HL and network segments.

TABLE 15: NETWORK AND SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Network Segment	Capacity (n·100 Gb/s)	Cost (per Gb/s)	Site Type	Capacity (proc. units)	Cost (per proc. unit)
Access (BS-HL4)	1	1	BS	1000	200
Aggregation (HL4-HL3)	10	10	HL4	1000	100
Transit (HL3-HL2)	10	100	HL3	1000	10
Core (HL2-HL1)	10	1000	HL2	1000	1

Several simulations have been carried out for an incremental number of users, thus representing an evolution such as the one pointed out in Figure 31. Hereafter, the number of users has been normalized in order to facilitate results analysis. Thus, the minimum number of users represents the current starting point, where the mix of services in Chapter 6 is assumed and no DESIRE6G use cases are served. As soon as the number of users increases, the proportion of DESIRE6G use cases increases, following the characterization in Chapter 8. We assume a yearly increment equal to 50% for those DESIRE6G services, in contrast to the 20-25% of current services. When normalized number of users equals one, the proportion of DESIRE6G use cases is near 50% of total traffic. Moreover, assuming the dimensioning values in Table 15, a normalized number of users larger than one produces some service rejection due to the lack of resources.

For each operation mode, we carried out simulations with two different objective functions. Figure 51 shows the results when only network bandwidth costs are minimized, whereas Figure 52 shows the results when only computing costs are minimized. The figures show the amount of allocated resources of bandwidth and compute, respectively, as a function of the incremental number of users. As can be observed, regardless of the objective function, DESIRE6G operation provides a much better average use of resources than that of 5G SA operation (see Figure 51a, Figure 51c, Figure 52a, Figure 52c). This leads to a reduction of costs derived from resource usage of services in a pay-as-you-go business model. In addition, OPEX savings (energy consumption, maintenance) are reduced by a lower amount of active

and running capacity resources, i.e. physical and virtual servers/machines running in sites and active ports/transponders in network links. Moreover, it can be observed that maximum network resource utilization, which directly links with CAPEX, is more beneficial at some moments (see Figure 51b, Figure 51d). In fact, the number of users that can be served with the same amount of invested resources is larger with DESIRE6G.

FIGURE 51: ALLOCATED BANDWIDTH AT AGGREGATION (A-B) AND TRANSIT (C-D) SEGMENTS

FIGURE 52: ALLOCATED COMPUTING RESOURCES AT HL4 (A-B) AND HL2 (C-D) SITES

The previous analysis focused on the use of resources when targeting specific objective functions. Figure 53 shows cost figures assuming the parameters in Table 15. In particular, Figure 53a-b is for bandwidth minimization objective, whereas Figure 53c-d is for compute resources minimization objective. Two types of costs are shown: *i)* the total cost normalized to the maximum (Figure 53a and Figure 53c), and *ii)* the cost per user (Figure 53b and Figure 53d). In view of the figures, we can conclude that the DESIRE6G innovations allows reducing costs derived from operation with respect to 5G SA operation. The cost per users are significantly low, and the savings compared with 5G SA increase with the expected users and traffic evolution (savings are embedded as percentages in Figure 53b and Figure 53d.)

FIGURE 53: COST FIGURES FOR BANDWIDTH (A-B) AND COMPUTE (C-D) COST MINIMIZATION

9.5 Conclusions

This chapter evaluated, by means of a simulation study, the expected cost benefits of a fully operative DESIRE6G infrastructure with the innovations, capabilities and functionalities introduced in [10]. For benchmarking purposes, a 5G SA infrastructure has been considered. The reference network architecture and topologies in Chapter 5, as well as the characteristics of current services in Chapter 6 and foreseen DESIRE6G services and use cases in Chapter 8 have been used to configure the simulator with a reference scenario to compare both operation modes in a fair way.

The main conclusions that can be extracted from the results are:

- 1) DESIRE6G enables a much more efficient and scalable use of computing resources along services lifetime than that of 5G SA, which leads to OPEX savings as well as opens the possibility to reduce service costs by guaranteeing a feasible and robust pay-as-you-go business model.

- 2) DESIRE6G solutions allows a large exploitation of deployed physical capacity resources, mainly in terms of network bandwidth. Thus, investment rounds to increase capacity (related to CAPEX) can be delayed or at least, planned with more anticipation, due to its better efficiency in the use of resources.
- 3) Cost figures are remarkably low with DESIRE6G. The cost per service users drops when comparing with a 5G SA approach, reaching savings between 55% and 85% sustained in time (and even increasing), which again offers the possibility to operators to potentially increase revenues and establish SLAs that, guaranteeing committed QoS requirements, can lead to large incomes and operator infrastructure value.

For all the above, we can conclude that fostering the deployment and investment of DESIRE6G innovations will bring large and immediate benefits in terms of OPEX and revenues, as well as a better scalability of CAPEX in mid and long-term evolution.

10. Enhanced heavy-hitter offload functionality

10.1 Abstract

In this chapter we provide numerical evaluations on the potential energy efficiency gains when implementing the offloading of high-bandwidth (heavy-hitter) flows to a HW-accelerated node via a Load Optimizer (LO) logic proposed and implemented in WP4.

10.2 Description Template

TABLE 16: ENHANCED HEAVY-HITTER OFFLOAD FUNCTIONALITY STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>Enhanced heavy-hitter offload functionality</i>
Description	<i>We evaluate the processing latency improvement and the cost savings that may be achieved by off-loading certain high-volume UP traffic to HW-accelerated DP NFs (e.g., UPFs).</i>
Layers / Components	<i>Programmable DP with HW acceleration and Heavy-hitter handling</i>
Benchmarking	<i>UP traffic handling without HW accelerated resources and heavy-hitter offloader</i>
Use case	<i>No particular use case/s defined in D6G</i>
KPI/KVI	<i>KPI 4.2: Enabling the deployment of virtual P4 pipelines on at least two P4 targets</i>
Methodology	<i>Measurements results are used to evaluate the latency improvement as well as energy consumption, the latter based on an energy consumption model of HW based and CPU-based UPFs, respectively. The HH offloaded scenario is</i>

<i>compared with the case when the HHS are not offloaded to the HW device. The energy savings is assessed quantitatively based on the traffic distribution and an energy consumption model of HW based and CPU-based UPFs. This is augmented with a qualitative cost assessment.</i>
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10.3 Energy consumption comparison

The seamless support for heavy-hitter offloading of high-bandwidth flows to a HW-accelerated node is a concept introduced in DESIRE6G project. It is achieved via a Load Optimizer (LO) logic, which is an infrastructure network function, invisible to the higher layers. More details about the LO can be found in [6] (section 5.1).

The energy consumption behavior of a HW and CPU based NF differ considerable. This is illustrated in Figure 54. The relative (in packets per second, pps) energy consumption of a CPU-based device is relatively high and shows a diminishing saw-tooth behavior, as new and new CPUs or boards need to be switched on to handle the increased traffic. On the other hand, the HW based NF starts with a high switch-on cost i.e., increased relative energy consumption at low loads, but then its consumption barely increases as the traffic volume gets up, thus the relative energy consumption converges to a much lower value at high loads (pps) than that of the CPU-based device. We note that the programmability feature does not bring in difference in the energy consumption, see for example a comparison between a Tofino switch and a fixed function ASIC in [11].

It is thus concluded that it is advantageous to direct the highest possible traffic load to the HW-based NF DP to save energy. The HW NF DP has the following main characteristics:

- It may process a large volume of traffic at line rate performance. For example, the per port throughput of a Tofino switch is up to 400Gbps, and its total throughput in the 1-20Tbps regime,
- It is memory limited thus only capable of handling limited number of UEs/PDU sessions, and since
- Its programmability might also have limitations (It can in general perform simple UP actions like classification, forwarding and/or scheduling),

From the above it turns out that it is advantageous from the energy cost/bit perspective to identify and direct the broadband PDU sessions that generate the most traffic, i.e., the so-called heavy hitters, to the HW NF DP. The heavy hitter detection has been a subject of extensive research in the context of programmable data planes and software-defined networking (SDN) and there are good solutions for it, see e.g., [12].

FIGURE 54: EXAMPLE ENERGY CONSUMPTION DEPENDENCE ON THE PROCESSED TRAFFIC VOLUME FOR A HW-ACCELERATED UP NF (E.G., UPF)

We estimate the share of the heavy hitter PDU sessions by using the service characterization performed in chapter 6. The contributing service categories are:

- Streaming service
- Gaming service
- Social network traffic. Note that the social network traffic may also include non-heavy hitters, which likely give a low contribution to the total traffic in this category. This may be largely counterbalanced by the P2P traffic, where the peaks are also likely caused by the heavy hitters, which are, however, left out from this comparison.
- CDN traffic

From the above, it results that the heavy hitters contribute to about 75% of the download traffic overall.

We compare this estimation with the mobile traffic data analysis from the Ericsson mobility report [13].

Here, the “communication services” also include video calls that may be regarded as heavy hitters. The video, communication and social networking DL traffic ranges between 55-75% for the different

providers, which is in line with the analysis resulting from our reference measurement data shown in Figure 34.

FIGURE 55: SHARE OF TRAFFIC UL AND DL PER APPLICATION CATEGORY

The energy cost savings resulting from the heavy-hitter offload may be estimated based on a simple model that assumes that the HW NF-DP does not consume additional energy as traffic to be processed grows. This is based on the energy consumption behaviour shown in Figure 54, further assuming that using the following approximations:

- The cost of replacing the fixed function ASIC on the top of the rack with the programmable HW device implementing the HH offloader and the NF DP functionality is covered by the additional operator revenues, as discussed above

- There is sufficient capacity on the programmable HW NF DP to handle the heavy hitters. This is supported by the fact that the whole traffic in the rack would need to pass the HW device anyhow. So there is no need to add more HW NF DP to process the heavy hitter traffic
- We approximate that the CPU -based NF energy consumption is proportional with the traffic load on this device.

That is, we conclude that the energy savings are proportional to the share of the HH traffic directed to the HW NF DP, which is estimated to be in the range of 55-75%.

10.4 Conclusions

From the analysis above we conclude that the energy savings are proportional to the share of the HH traffic directed to the HW NF DP, i.e., in the range of 55-75%. This anticipates a huge savings potential from utilizing the heavy hitter offload concept.

The savings assessment above has not considered the performance benefits that are enabled by the HH offloader. The traffic handled by HW NF-DPs has lower packet processing latency (basically enabling line rate processing) and the HH offloader may also be configured to direct the QoS flows with strict latency requirements to the HWNF DP. The expected latency benefits from this framework can motivate the MNO replace some of their ASIC with programmable devices like Tofino, the required CAPEX being compensated by the new revenues received from the customers using these services.

As mentioned above, the HW NF DP is memory limited thus only capable of handling limited number of UEs/PDU sessions. Further analysis is needed on whether the HW NF DP can accommodate all the states needed for the identified heavy hitter traffic.

We are also pursuing an investigation related to transferring the states between the CPU based NF DP and HW based NF DP, needed to support the scenarios when a non-HH session becomes HH and vice versa. As seamless state transfer is required as possible not to disturb the ongoing flows.

11. Capacity savings with network-wide hierarchical QoS

11.1 Abstract

In this chapter we compare the efficiency of the state-of-art traffic management methods with the methods proposed and developed in the D6G project. In particular, we compare the link-by-link HQoS (LHQoS) with the Network-wide HQoS (NHQoS) method investigated and developed in the D6G project, and to be fully described in D4.3.

11.2 Description Template

TABLE 17: CAPACITY SAVINGS WITH NHQOS STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>Capacity savings with NHQoS</i>
Description	<i>We compare the capacity required to provide certain service guarantees (e.g., minimum throughput) when using the Network-wide Hierarchical QoS (NHQoS) method.</i>
Layers / Components	<i>Programmable DP implementing the packet classification, packet scheduling and potential resource sharing calculation methods needed to apply the NHQoS method.</i>
Benchmarking	<i>Legacy LHQoS, when Hierarchical QoS (HQoS) rules are configured on and applied by all the links individually.</i>
Use case	<i>No particular use case/s defined in D6G</i>
KPI/KVI	KPI5.8: In-network solution enforcing Hierarchical QoS (HQoS) among and withing slices across multiple (>2) hierarchical levels

Methodology	Simulation experiments and simple calculations are used to show the benefits of network-wide HQoS enforcement. On the same network topology, the NHQoS approach results in larger throughput allocation for the worst performing users than LHQoS, and keeps the throughput share between operators, slices and users close to the desired resource sharing policy.
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11.3 Bandwidth share comparison

As discussed in D4.1 [14] and D4.2 [6], a generic, multi-tenant and multi-service(slice) network requires HQoS methods to isolate the traffic at each of the layers. In our analysis, we compare the resulting throughput values from two such traffic management approaches:

- Link-by-link HQoS (LHQoS), where the quality-of-service policy is enforced independently at each link in the network, using existing HQoS policy enforcement methods, like Deficit Round-Robin scheduling for the higher hierarchy level (e.g., operator) and Fair Queuing for the lower hierarchical level (e.g., different users within an operator).
- Network-wide HQoS (NHQoS), which attempts to provide an optimal network-wide hierarchical bandwidth allocation. For this, a centralized throughput calculation logic may be used that computes the ideal throughput allocations based on the available capacity and offered load. Implementation alternatives of this method have been investigated in the D6G project and will be reported in D4.3, which will be the latest deliverable of WP4.

NHQoS is designed to ensure max-min fair allocation at every level of the policy hierarchy. For example, assuming two levels – operator level and user level within each operator – NHQoS enforces max-min fair allocation both at the operator level (aggregated throughput per operator) and at the user level (ensuring fairness among users of each operator). If additional levels (e.g., slices, subslices) exist, the same principle can naturally be extended to them.

To compare the resource sharing, we consider a simple network topology as depicted in Figure 56 with three nodes (A, B, and C), two links (AB and AC) with capacities of 1000 Mbps each. The network carries the traffic of two mobile network operators (MNOs), OP1 and OP2. The HQoS policy mandates an equal (1:1) allocation of network resources between the two operators, with uniform weight distribution across

all users. For simplicity, this example does not consider additional hierarchical levels, such as slices and subslices.

Figure 56 illustrates a situation where operator OP1 has one user in cell site B and three users in cell site C, while operator OP2 has the opposite arrangement: three users in cell site B and one user in cell site C. As shown in the left figure of Figure 56, applying LHQoS (i.e., enforcing the HQoS policy on each link independently) yields a fair share between operators but produces uneven allocations among each operator's users. Specifically, the policy first splits each link's capacity equally between the two operators (at the top level of the HQoS hierarchy). Thus, OP1 receives half of each link's capacity: its single user on link AB obtains the entire 500 Mbps share for that link, while its three users on link AC split the remaining 500 Mbps, each receiving 166 Mbps. Although operator-level fairness (1:1 sharing) is maintained on each link, user-level fairness is not satisfied.

By contrast, as shown in the right figure of Figure 56, enforcing the HQoS policy at the network level (NHQoS) aligns the allocated throughput with the actual distribution of users. Under this approach, each user—regardless of the cell site—receives 250 Mbps. This satisfies both operator- and user-level fairness and maintains the expected 1:1 operator share.

With the traditional LHQoS approach, we need 1.5 times more bandwidth on both links to get the same worst case throughput allocation, resulting in 250Mbps/UE for OP2 users in cell site B and the same for OP1 users in cell site C. One can observe that NHQoS cannot only provide better network-wide fairness but requires less system-wide bandwidth to achieve the same throughput allocation for the worst performing users (250Mbps per UE in the example), reducing CAPEX, improving overall utilization of the infrastructure and the end users' satisfaction.

FIGURE 56: EXAMPLE DOWNSTREAM SCENARIOS: BANDWIDTH SHARES RESULTING FROM LHQoS (LEFT) AND FROM NHQoS (RIGHT).

11.4 Conclusions

While enforcing HQoS policies on a link-by-link basis is straightforward, it often fails to achieve the intended global resource allocation when traffic loads are unevenly distributed. Since different operators, slices, and users may traverse distinct paths through the network, splitting resources equally on each link does not always reflect overall policy goals. Conversely, network-wide HQoS (NHQoS) accommodates the broader distribution of traffic and resources, making it more consistent with stakeholders' expectations.

To cater for the inefficiencies of the link-by-link policies, the transport network providers would need to apply overprovisioning. In the scenario discussed in section 11.3, for example, if the goal is to provide a minimum of 250Mbps/UE for each operator, expecting a maximum of 3 UEs per site, the link-by-link policies would require an overprovisioning of $250/166 \sim 150\%$ on the two links AB and AC, i.e., capacities of 1500Mbps vs 1000 Mbps each in the NHQoS case. In a network with large number of sites, considerable user movement and traffic distribution, this could result in large network provider savings if using NHQoS.

12. Energy savings from AI Model Acceleration

12.1 Abstract

Besides the well-known benefits of AI Model acceleration (reduced inference times and improved throughput) that have been reported in D4.2 [6] and which analysis will be expanded in D4.3, in this chapter we highlight another benefit resulting from using the SOL server, i.e., the reduced energy consumption of the NN models.

12.2 Description Template

TABLE 18: ENERGY SAVINGS FROM AI MODEL ACCELERATION STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>AI Model Acceleration</i>
Description	<i>This study focuses on the evaluation of energy consumption reduction from using SOL server during training and inference of NN models.</i>
Layers / Components	<i>Programmable Data Plane (PDP) layer implementing accelerated NN execution</i>
Benchmarking	<i>Existing NN execution frameworks, like Pytorch's Torchvision.</i>
Use case	No particular use case
KPI/KVI	It relates to the KPI3.4 and KPI 3.5
Methodology	<i>We use test measurements to evaluate energy consumption reduction with using the SOL server for NN acceleration.</i>

12.3 Energy consumption comparison

In DESIRE6G we use SOL for the acceleration of NNs. The mission of the SOL project is to transparently accelerate NN workloads, with as few computing overhead as possible. The SOL server is described in D4.1 [14], while the integration of SOL with the D6G framework is detailed in D4.2 [6] together with some initial results.

In this document we listed the techno-economic benefits of SOL in section 7.1.2. The SOL server has been continuously improved during the D6G project timeframe. The latest results underlying the technology benefits will be documented in the last WP4 deliverable, D4.3. In this chapter we present some complementary measurements that underline one specific techno-economic benefit when utilizing SOL optimization for NN model acceleration, related to energy consumption.

We have performed energy consumption measurements on 30 computer vision models from the popular computer vision library of PyTorch. The tests have been performed using *nvidia-smi* tool, on a NVIDIA L40 GPU¹. The results during inference with or without utilizing the SOL server for optimization are shown in Figure 57, where the performance of SOL optimization is compared with a PyTorch baseline. One can see that the SOL-optimized consumption figures are consistently lower than the default values, yielding an average gain of x3.04, i.e., the SOL version of the neural networks consumes one third of the PyTorch baseline, in average.

¹ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/data-center/l40/>

FIGURE 57: ENERGY CONSUMPTION PER INFERENCE - SOL IN GREEN, PYTORCH IN RED

The consumption measurements in the training phase are shown in Figure 58. Here the benefits are smaller, but still consistent, yielding an average gain of x2.1 in power consumption.

FIGURE 58: ENERGY CONSUMPTION DURING TRAINING - SOL IN GREEN, PYTORCH IN RED

As latency measurements showed a similar behavior, we can conclude that the energy consumption savings results from the latency savings (the GPUs being almost 100% used in both cases).

12.4 Conclusions

The energy consumption measurements show a consistent and considerable decrease when SOL server is used for NN acceleration, as the PyTorch baseline consumes in average three times more and two times more energy during inference and training respectively. This benefit is related to the fact that the inference and training times have been reduced considerably when applying optimization with the SOL server.

13. OPEX reduction by service MAS operation

13.1 Abstract

This work evaluates the performance in terms of operational expenditures (OPEX) reduction of multi-agent systems (MAS) in charge of the autonomous control of traffic flows supporting 6G connectivity services with stringent requirements. MAS enables in near-real time adaptation of resources to support connectivity services through multiple paths. In this way, energy savings are achieved with respect to the benchmarking approach, where connectivity is statically managed and consequently, resources for guaranteeing committed requirements under any circumstance are always active and consuming energy.

13.2 Description Template

TABLE 19: OPEX REDUCTION BY SERVICE MAS OPERATION STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>OPEX reduction by service MAS operation</i>
Description	<i>This work presents the benefits in terms of energy consumption reduction of operating autonomously a 6G network by means of a MAS, in comparison with a static benchmarking operation.</i>
Layers / Components	<i>MAS, INT</i>
Benchmarking	<i>Static operation where flow routing is managed by static load balancing policies and pre-planned (active) ports in programmable packet switches.</i>
Use case	<i>Valid for any use case requiring autonomous control of e2e flow connectivity. Aligned with demo use cases</i>

KPI/KVI	<i>KPI3.1: Autonomous operation based on multi-agent systems to reduce > 25% OPEX w.r.t. manual/static operation.</i>
Methodology	<i>Simulation and DRL-based operation, reproducing network topologies in line with transport network in Section 5.1.2. and flows according to traffic and services described in Chapter 6.</i>

13.3 Introduction

6G connectivity services foreseen for the next decades will impose strict Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, such as high bandwidth, ultra-low end-to-end latency, and ultra-high reliability, making them a key challenge for next-generation network operators. To support these complex demand scenarios, networks are evolving towards the network programmability paradigm i.e., advanced programmable switches equipped with high bandwidth pluggable interfaces. These adaptive and flexible network solutions facilitate the deployment of high-speed interfaces (from 100 Gb/s to 400 Gb/s) in a modular and cost-effective manner, allowing for greater flexibility in network design and scalability [15]. However, such programmability typically comes with large energy consumption, which is especially challenging when considering the scalability of the solutions.

Among different use cases supported by network programmability, autonomous flow routing is attracting special research interest. Thus, by dynamically selecting among multiple available paths based on different criteria, individual connectivity services (flows) can be accordingly balanced in near-real time in order to guarantee strict QoS requirements while minimizing multi-objective cost functions [16]. However, for the success of this autonomous operation, programmable networks need to be fueled with distributed intelligence and in-band telemetry in order to coordinate routing decisions with target QoS requirements and desired operational objectives. To this aim, multi-agent systems (MAS) are key to guarantee such adaptive and near-real time autonomous operation of 6G connectivity services [17]. As consequence of adopting all these technologies, autonomous networks promise to reduce operational expenditures (OPEX) including energy consumption reduction.

This paper focus on evaluating the performance of using MAS for autonomous network operation of traffic flows in support of 6G connectivity services in terms of energy consumption. In particular, we aim

at evaluating the energy consumption savings that a MAS-based autonomous flow routing use case provides with respect to a benchmarking static operation approach, where flows are routed following either single path routing or multi-path routing with static policies, e.g., equal cost multi-path (ECMP) strategy.

13.4 Autonomous Flow Routing Operation

In this section, we summarize the autonomous flow routing operation system considered in this work, based on the work presented in [16]. In a pure SDN-based approach, route selection can be performed at flow provisioning time based on the network topology and current and expected network conditions. However, in the distributed intelligence approach sketched in Figure 59a, a MAS deployment aims at dynamically controlling a connectivity service (traffic flow) between a source and a destination node. At the source node, the intelligent agent in the flow routing module, optimizes the path selection to meet committed QoS (i.e., do not exceed a maximum delay value) while minimizing cost. Traffic is routed through different paths, with multiple sub-flows following the same route. Upon reaching the destination, e2e delay is measured, statistics computed, and relayed to participating node agents.

The scenario depicted in Figure 59b is devoted to illustrate the challenging scenario where routing decision making is needed due to the variation of the traffic flow under-control (labelled as f1) and also the network dynamicity introduced by other traffic flows (f2 and f3). In particular, the illustrative network scenario contains five packet nodes and three different packet flows: R1-R3 (f1), R1-R4 (f2), and R2-R3 (f3), along with traffic variations over time for all flows. Initially, R1 has two alternative paths for flow f1: R1-R2-R3 and R1-R4-R5-R3. Note that traffic can be routed via R2 (the shortest path), if acceptable delay for flow R1-R3 can be assured. However, when flow R2-R3 is established or its traffic increases, the delay for flow R1-R3 exceeds the maximum, prompting R1 to divert traffic through the alternative route via R4, that can be longer (and consequently, have higher cost) to mitigate delay. This adaptive routing continues as traffic and delay conditions fluctuate, with R1 adjusting routing through available paths to optimize delay/cost.

This autonomous flow routing operation can be combined with port management actions, to dynamically dimension the resources supporting the available paths. Focusing on the flow source node, this means activating/deactivating interfaces (ports), to adapt capacity to current traffic needs. Although

node ports can be pre-assigned and fixed to paths, which entails a fixed deployment cost, dynamic activation/deactivation reduces OPEX costs coming from energy consumption. Thus, MAS can anticipate the need of adding/releasing ports in order to fulfil QoS in an energy-efficient way.

FIGURE 59: MAS FOR AUTONOMOUS FLOW ROUTING (A); NETWORK SCENARIO (B)

13.5 Node Architecture and Energy Consumption Model

In order to support the MAS-based autonomous flow routing presented in previous section, we consider the programmable switch architecture in [1] as reference node architecture. Note that this kind of devices have shown promising energy consumption savings by adopting dedicated control plane mechanisms oriented to maximize energy efficiency [18]. The programmable switch architecture centers around the Intel Tofino ASIC model, specifically within the Edgecore Wedge100BF-65X platform. This switch utilizes a protocol-independent switch architecture (PISA), enabling programmability through the P4 language. The switch is composed of a data plane and a control plane. The data plane executes match-action pipelines defined in P4, allowing for custom packet processing rules. The control plane, managed via software entities such as an SDN controller and/or a MAS agent, is responsible for configuration and state management. Additionally, the infrastructure includes telemetry capabilities

using P4-INT, which supports real-time monitoring of packets traversing the network, leading to telemetry agents integrated with the MAS infrastructure [17].

The switch supports a variety of port types and configurations such as Quad Small Form-Factor Pluggable (QSFP) ports capable of 100G operation, with a total switching capacity of 3.2 Tb/s. These ports are suitable for high-speed data transmission in aggregation or transit scenarios, i.e., connectivity between HL4/HL3 and HL3/HL2 sites detailed in Section 5.1.2. where the required capacity of different flows through multiple routes can be properly managed with the granularity of such ports. However new generation of Tofino-based programmable switches are supporting larger switching capacities, e.g. 12.8 Tb/s, by supporting 400G QSFP with double density (QSFP-DD) capabilities [19]. Note that this capacity expansion makes this kind of switches more adequate for core network scenarios, i.e., HL1 and HL2 levels, where flows under control might rapidly scale to ultra-high bitrates and more stringent QoS requirements.

Assuming the programmable switch model described before, we adopt the energy consumption computation approach presented in [20] and successfully applied in [18]. Thus, the switch has a baseline consumption (base) that is a fixed value in the state where no ports are enabled and it is independent of data/control plane software components running in the switch. Then, at a given time, each port can be in one of the following states: i) disabled, as for the baseline case, where they are not contributing to increase energy consumption; ii) enabled, where the port adds an additional power consumption cost (enable) due to its port configuration (administratively up, but optical interface not yet enabled); iii) active, where optical interface is up and running, which entails an additional power cost (active) that is typically larger than enable cost. Finally, the energy consumption scales with the utilization of its resources, namely, by processing packets at the ports and in the ASIC. Without loss of generality, we assume a linear cost (use) proportional to the traffic supported at each port.

Hence, as a result of MAS decision making (flow routing + port management), a given port p at a given time t can be active (which is denoted as $x_{pt} = 1$; 0, otherwise). If active, the amount of traffic in a port (which is denoted as y_{pt}) is computed assuming a load balancing among all the ports supporting the path. The following equation models the energy consumption (EC) of a given switch at a given time t as the contribution of the different parameters and variables described before:

$$EC(t) = base + \sum_{p \in P} (enable + (active - enable) \cdot x_{pt} + use \cdot y_{pt})$$

Table 20 details the different power consumption parameters for the two configurations described above, namely, aggregation configuration (3.2 Tb/s switch with 100G QSFP ports) and core configuration (12.8 Tb/s switch with 400G QSFP-DD ports). These values, which are in line with the reference power consumption values in [20], as well as product specifications in [19], will be consistently used in the results presented in next section.

TABLE 20: POWER CONSUMPTION PARAMETERS (IN WATTS)

<i>Scenario</i>	<i>Sw. Capacity</i>	<i>100 Gb/s Ports</i>	<i>400 Gb/s ports</i>	<i>base (switch)</i>	<i>enable (port)</i>	<i>active (port)</i>	<i>use (b/s)</i>
<i>Aggregation (HL4/HL3)</i>	3.2 Tb/s	32	-	108W	1.8W	4.5W	1.3e-11W
<i>Core (HL2/HL1)</i>	12.8 Tb/s	-	32	245W	3.2W	12W	2.1e-11W

13.6 Numerical Results

For numerical evaluation purposes, we developed a Python simulator that reproduces network scenarios as the one presented in Figure 59b. In particular, it aims at generating traffic flows of variable bitrate between source and destination nodes according to a mix of the services presented in Chapter 6. The traffic of each flow is routed through multiple paths, and each path is assigned to switch ports at each node, so that capacity is guaranteed. The simulator can be configured to reproduce two main approaches. On the one hand, the static approach assumes a fixed number of ports assigned to each path and performs ECMP to balance flow traffic among available paths. The number of ports is dimensioned to guarantee enough capacity at peak traffic, assuming perfect knowledge on future incoming traffic, which leads to tight and accurate dimensioning. This mode does not guarantee QoS requirements since no intelligent decision making is performed by any agent. On the other hand, the MAS approach follows the operation explained in Section II, i.e., telemetry is used to monitor actual flow QoS at destination node and perform routing actions and port management in the source node. According to those actions, the number of enabled/active ports assigned to every path change with time.

Figure 60 and Figure 61 show an example of performance of static and MAS approaches, respectively, for a scenario reproducing the network and traffic in Figure 59, assuming aggregation configuration for the switches. In particular, the figures show traffic at each of the alternative paths of flow f_1 (a-b) and the power consumption at source node (c). The traffic of flows f_2 and f_3 follow different weekly patterns but similar traffic volumes than that of f_1 . It is worth mentioning that, with the current traffic loads, both operation approaches allow accomplishing QoS requirements during all the time, so both are equally valid from the service assurance perspective. As expected, the ECMP operation of static approach perfectly balances traffic among alternative paths, whereas MAS adapts routing to use only two paths when QoS assurance requires it. In this way, deactivation of ports is possible during significant time in a day. This translates to remarkable power consumption savings, which can be observed in Figure 61c, in contrast with the flat, constant power consumption of static approach in Figure 60c.

FIGURE 60: STATIC APPROACH: TRAFFIC THROUGH ROUTE A (A) AND ROUTE B (B), AND POWER CONSUMPTION (C)

FIGURE 61: MAS APPROACH: TRAFFIC THROUGH ROUTE A (A) AND ROUTE B (B), AND POWER CONSUMPTION (C)

The benefits of MAS approach in terms of energy consumption reduction sketched in Figure 61, are exhaustively evaluated in Figure 62. The scenario has been extended with a third route, that uses a direct bypass to avoid congestion caused by other flows. Moreover, low and high congestion scenarios have been generated by reducing and increasing, respectively, the traffic of flows f_2 and f_3 flows. The figures show the average and maximum power consumption of f_1 source node as a function of f_1 traffic volume (normalized to the maximum traffic that can be supported without violating QoS in the absence of congestion). Curves are depicted in each case only for the loads that guarantee QoS assurance. Note

that, in line with the exhaustive analysis carried out in [16], the static approach using ECMP routing can support less traffic to guarantee the same QoS requirement than MAS approach. In terms of power consumption, static approach is planned in a way that alternative routes are activated only when the traffic peak for that normalized load requires it, which produces staggered power consumption as soon as new paths are activated. Moreover, weekly average and maximum traffic consumption remains similar, due to the nature of the approach.

FIGURE 62: PERFORMANCE OF STATIC VS MAS-BASED OPERATION FOR AGGREGATION (A-B) AND CORE (C-D) CONFIGURATIONS

Observing the results of MAS approach, one can observe a smooth increasing of power consumption with traffic load, which allows remarkable power consumption reduction in terms of both average and maximum values. Table 21 extends the information in Figure 62 with the relative savings with respect to the static approach for different switch configurations and congestion scenarios. The table also includes the energy efficiency computed as the amount of flow traffic that can be served with QoS guarantees given a target power consumption (200W in aggregation configuration and 500W in core configuration). The results show large benefits in terms of power savings and energy efficiency derived from adopting MAS infrastructure to control programmable networks in near-real time.

TABLE 21: MAS APPROACH RESULTS (W.R.T STATIC)

<i>Config</i>	<i>Congestion</i>	<i>Power Savings</i>		<i>Energy Efficiency</i>
		<i>mean</i>	<i>max</i>	<i>Gain</i>
<i>Aggregation</i>	<i>Low</i>	19%	32%	54%
	<i>High</i>	21%	33%	85%
<i>Core</i>	<i>Low</i>	25%	36%	75%
	<i>High</i>	26%	37%	114%

13.7 Conclusions

Adopting MAS for near-real time operation allows reducing energy consumption in programmable networks, achieving sustained switch power savings larger than 20%, reaching peaks larger than 30% under different scenarios. Indeed, energy efficiency is largely increased (even doubled) with respect to static operation, which allows us concluding that MAS-based autonomous network operation clearly reduces OPEX in 6G networks.

14. Assessment of application remote attestation and runtime integrity verification of software payloads

14.1 Abstract

When a software payload is onboarded off-premises in un-controlled platforms, remote attestation is the standardized security technique, assuring that the remotely deployed code is integrated. Remote attestation implies a locally based prover which produces the workload measurement and sign it before transmitting the signed quote to a remote verifier. The verifier is closed to or accessed by the DevSecOps operators and produce a comparison between the received signature and a stored reference measurement for that workload. In networking, remote attestation provides security assurance to workload operators or developers which deploy workloads and is practiced at the workload on-boarding stage. In contrast, code authentication brings a security assurance to the managing entity of execution environment of the workloads (e.g., infrastructure operator), hence delivers a different perspective. On the operational side, remote attestation is more practiced on stable, long-lived software as it induces the management of the reference measurement and the signing key at the verification side, associated with a complex sequence of operations. In practice, remote attestation is essentially used for system code. It is carried out at the on-boarding stage, before the code is running.

The verifier must store reference measurements supplied by the workload developer updated and its signing key for checking the signature before storing. This is business complex task, which may be risky with frequently changed workloads.

Moreover, on the prover side, as remote attestation is practiced at untrusted remote platforms, trust derives from trusted modules (i.e., Trusted Platform Module (TPM) or Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) which must be present and ready on these untrusted platforms.

In contrast, authentication is far easier to operate as all necessary cryptographic elements are inserted into the manifest of the onboarded workloads. Moreover, as the workload recipient (i.e., which produces the authentication) trusts itself, authentication does not require and leverage TPM or TEE.

As stipulated by ETSI or other SDOs, network function remote attestation and runtime integrity are essential techniques when services must be implemented seamlessly on the available platforms disseminated in

several security domains. In practice, remote attestation is rarely applied for due to the continuous efforts for provisioning and management of reference measurements and cryptographic keys. The hardware or kernel level dependencies on the execution platform restrict the workload deployment to dependency-verified and configured platforms only, another strong obstacle to remote attestation.

During the payload execution, runtime integrity verification enables to verify the workload during its operation, hence after the on-boarding. It is not a standardized operation and engenders a penalty on the performance of the workload.

D-MUTRA, standing for DLT-based Mutual Remote Attestation of software payloads, is a flexible framework which offers both remote attestation and runtime integrity verification, removing the technical and operational risks and complications as stated above.

Our discussion covers both remote attestation and runtime integrity verification, both based on D-MUTRA's measurement of the workload memory allocated pages once it has been loaded by the Memory Management Unit (MMU) at different timings (i.e., before and during execution).

For the sake of simplicity, we are providing a comparison of D-MUTRA with the configuration where the prover function is built-in a TPM. As a matter of fact, TPM can be considered as the standard to practice remote attestation today, although it is by far more used for system than application workloads.

14.2 Description Template

TABLE 22: REMOTE ATTESTATION AND RUNTIME INTEGRITY VERIFICATION STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>D-MUTRA</i>
Description	<i>Blockchain-based mutual remote attestation and runtime integrity verification of 6G service software payloads.</i>
Layers / Components	<i>Blockchain-based SECaaS payload security</i>

Benchmarking	<p><i>On remote attestation, elements of comparison are qualitative and relate to operational ease of use.</i></p> <p><i>On runtime integrity verification, performance penalty is key and is assessed.</i></p> <p><i>For both, an assessment of the memory footprint caused on one blockchain node by a transaction (i.e., block creation) is delivered here.</i></p>
Use case	<p><i>D-MUTRA remote attestation is exemplified with MAS agents on-boarding which is taking part of DEMO1. An additional PoC exemplifies continuous runtime integrity enabling Attest After Starting mode.</i></p>
KPI/KVI	<p><i>On remote attestation, the following KVI apply: Trust on deployed services integrity.</i></p> <p><i>The core KPI is deployment restriction. On runtime integrity verification, the core KVI stands for continuous trust in running services. The core KPI is the effective cost in terms of memory and CPU consumption.</i></p>
Methodology	<p><i>It consists in enumerating the operational gains first. Secondly, on the core aspect of runtime integrity verification, we have quantified the CPU cost impact only.</i></p>

14.3 D-MUTRA techno-economics analysis

14.3.1 D-MUTRA's key features

- No dependencies on hardware or kernel software
- Distributed (i.e., decentralized) security concept, through mutual attestation where any payloads measure themselves and verify their peers when elected for that by the blockchain orchestrated smart contract.
- Automatic generation of signatures and their secure provisioning to the elected verifiers.
- Blockchain registry of the remote attestation results.

- Zero touch automatic management of reference measurements, provisioned at the right location in due time.
- Applicable to ring-3 (i.e., application level).

14.3.2 D-MUTRA's users

The following stakeholders are considered for using D-MUTRA:

- Telecom operators, for service deployment in uncontrolled environment. Potential use case: xAPP deployment in O-RAN.
- Telecom suppliers, obviating to the requirement for TPM (typically on O-RAN)
- Telecom users: trust on services
- Infrastructures owners = trust on infrastructure and data security

14.4 Remote attestation service hardware, software and setup costs

14.4.1 SOTA (i.e., TPM-based remote attestation)

Setting up requires the checking and the validation of the configuration of server blades (e.g., presence of TPM + BIOS/UEFI TPM stack, Intel TXT's DTRM primitive + Linux IMA primitive) of each considered workload execution environments. Once these components are present and installed, they shall be configured (e.g., platforms BIOS configuration and initialized, create and storing Attestation and Endorsement Keys (i.e., AK,EK), identify verifier (i.e., MAC/IP) , allow link (i.e., at the prover side), configure and secure the verifier (e.g., closed network ports). Beyond this engineering costs, TPMs have their own costs. However, TPM's unit price of 3€/unit is insignificant versus server blade costs (#i.e., 3 K€/unit). All software enablers are open source and/or free to use when detained by processor or chip maker vendors.

14.4.2 D-MUTRA

Setting up requires the creation or reuse of a blockchain with sufficient nodes, positioned anywhere but with a relative proximity to the workloads execution environments.

A minimalist configuration is a four node blockchain. The nodes processing and memory requirements are easily covered by standard utility server blades. The blockchain nodes execution environment can be shared to run other services by the DevSecOps engineering.

Last, D-MUTRA blockchain nodes will be delivered for being totally self-instantiated and ready to run once deployed. All software (e.g., Ethereum, Hyperledger) are free to use. D-MUTRA smart contract and components will be delivered as open source and also free to use.

14.4.3 Conclusions

Remote attestation service implementation costs are essentially related to engineering costs, not to investment in hardware. The critical aspect of the SOTA relates to the verification and the setting up of each targeted execution environments with the required hardware, kernel and software components (e.g., the verifier code). DevSecOps is drastically simplified with D-MUTRA as blockchain nodes can be instantly created at any locations of sufficient resources and be running. We believe that for the operator of the remote attestation service, the creation of 4 or more blockchain nodes (if the blockchain is fully installed in the operator's domain) at any locations are marginal costs when compared to the expertise and time required to implement and configure a SOTA remote attestation service.

14.5 Running costs and operators revenues

14.5.1 SOTA (i.e., TPM-based remote attestation)

The operator shall timely collect the workloads signatures generated by the developers. This operation is error-prone and time-sensitive. Signatures and developers signing keys shall be transferred securely to the verifier for its future use. Before using these signatures, an authentication check shall be done before storage. The revocation of deprecated signatures must also be carried out and induces human intervention.

On the prover side, with a less frequent occurrence, the TPM configuration (e.g., AK, EK) may change, requiring for the same configuration change to be mirrored at verifier side.

Regarding revenues, the remote attestation of the payload execution file or container prevents rogue payloads at the onboarding stage, hence reducing service downtime caused by malicious provisioning of wrong workloads.

14.5.2 D-MUTRA

The SECaaS automatically generates the timely signatures and signing keys and provisions them securely to D-MUTRA elected verifier.

In addition to onboarding workload check as offered by the SOTA, D-MUTRA runtime integrity verification prevents running code tampering by privileged users, remote attacks (e.g., privilege escalation, maintenance channel attacks, corrupted runtime and systems).

14.5.3 Conclusions

D-MUTRA suppresses the tedious and risky tasks of workloads signature, developers key, platform's AK and EK provisioning and maintenance. Moreover, D-MUTRA prevents un-treated attacks by the SOTA, hence reducing service downtime caused by these forms of attacks.

14.6 Financial sustainability

Regulatory fines emerge with past incidents, when it was proven that all regulatory obligations were enforced or practiced by the operator. Assurance fees are assessed by assurers with past fines, the regulatory context (e.g., frequency of the fines imposed to operators) and an assessed security abilities and profile of the considered operator.

14.6.1 SOTA

Remote attestation delivers the proof that a security-prone workload version was in operation when an incident occurred. Hence, remote attestation strengthens the position of the defendant proving that all regulation measures were taken on the workload identified as the cause of the incident.

14.6.2 D-MUTRA

In addition to correct workload check at onboarding, D-MUTRA runtime integrity verification ensures that the code is untampered during execution and the monitoring traces can be used as complementary elements reinforcing the security posture and legal defense. Fewer regulatory fines and assurance fees will be supported by the service operator. Moreover, continuous integrity verifications provide valuable informations for the investigation of the incident, at the precise moment it took place.

14.6.3 Conclusions

Remote attestation does not alleviate the conformity with sector specific regulations but can be leveraged to demonstrate that the incident took place on a workload which was fully meeting these regulation provisions. Compared to the SOTA, D-MUTRA' accrued continuous runtime preservation, limits further fines and correlated assurances fees.

14.7 Regulatory compliance

Remote attestation in networking. Remote attestation, though highly discussed and recommended by SDOs (e.g., ETSI) is not yet mandated. The latest version of NFV security work group recommendations by ETSI does not strictly call for remote attestation but as a best-have for NFV security. The same position stands at IETF which recommends without specifying remote attestation. O-RAN security work group WG11 has the same approach of recommending remote attestation for xApp authenticity and integrity verification when on-boarding but without mandating it.

NIS2 regulation for critical services. For telecom operators, the regulatory framework has evolved with E.U's NIS2 directive in force in December 2024 and which put emphasis on continuous security of on-going services, in contrast with the former framework constructed on baseline security measure and periodic audits. In NIS2, vulnerability handling shall be permanent and incidents initial notification shall be produced in less than 24 hours to the national cybersecurity authority. NIS2's integrity preservation statement relates to data, not software. However, NIS2 explicitly demands for outsourced (software) dependency checks. As data integrity is directly exposed when one of this-data processing software is

tampered, data integrity requires software integrity and applies to all components of the processing including the dependencies.

14.7.1 SOTA

The SOTA satisfies NIS2's need for data integrity preservation, as it verifies the processing software at on-boarding stage. However, remote attestation can be considered as a static which does not fulfill continuous security.

14.7.2 D-MUTRA

D-MUTRA's continuous integrity aligns with NIS2 trend for continuous security, although not yet explicated. D-MUTRA does it at much lesser operational costs than by TEE placement. Noticeably, compared to the SOTA where integrity is not offered during workload operation, D-MUTRA's runtime verification shortens the delay between the time of attack and time of notification, hence easing the compliance with the novel incident notification directive.

14.7.3 Conclusions

D-MUTRA continuous integrity aligns with NIS2's continuous security direction and reduce the time to notify an incident.

14.8 Energetic costs

Energy expenses directly incurred by the solution.

14.8.1 SOTA

TPM-based remote attestation energy estimate is in the range of 100 mJ (i.e., 0,1J) per verification. This figure includes the nonce based protocols and notably the signature generation by the TPM.

14.8.2 D-MUTRA

Costs of measurement:

- 0,5 mJ (i.e., hash and RSA encryption in a standard server)

Costs of smart contract (or chaincode) remote attestation orchestration:

- 10-100 J on Ethereum
- 2-5 J on Fabric (chaincode)

Costs of blockchain transaction (i.e., tx) can be assessed as follows:

- Ethereum (Proof of Stake consensus): 20J/tx, hence two orders of magnitude higher than TPM-based remote attestation.
- Hyperledger Fabric: 1 J/tx (hence # 5 times more than TPM-based remote attestation)

The energy costs induced the blockchain based remote attestation are:

- Hyperleder Fabrik: in the range of 5 J
- Ethereum PoS: in the range of 100 J

14.8.3 Conclusions

TPM are significantly more energy-friendly than blockchains with advantage between 1 to 3 orders of magnitude according to blockchain type. However, remote attestation are produced only once, at workload on-boarding. Hence and in practice, the absolute energy costs for remote attestation are neglectable in all scenarios including in DESIRE-6G implementation (Ethereum's PoS).

14.9 Energetic costs for runtime integrity verification

Energy expenses directly incurred by the solution.

14.9.1 SOTA

Not applicable as the service is not existing.

14.9.2 D-MUTRA

The same figures as stated above stand.

Noticeably, a transaction will be produced only on **integrity failures**, which occurrence are much smaller than integrity verifications. We also planned to reduce the frequency of the verifications as soon as a failure occurs as we are not expecting any further change on that failure situation). This is aimed at limiting the energy costs as well as blockchain memory inflation rate.

14.9.3 Conclusions

An important limitation of energy costs derives from our policy to restrict transactions only when a **failure is detected** by the verifier and to downgrade the frequency of the verifications thereafter.

14.10 Memory consumption

Requirements in terms of disk and RAM memory

14.10.1 SOTA

The TPM's PCR (ie, registers) are used to store the measurements on the Prover side (i.e., workload execution platforms). On the verifier's side, sufficient memory shall be present to store the signature of the application (i.e., provision in the range of 10^3 to 10^4 bytes).

14.10.2 D-MUTRA

Depending on the blockchain type, blockchain nodes shall be provisioned with sufficient disk and RAM space:

Ethereum (Private, PoS)

- Disk: 500GB-1T
- RAM: 8-16 GB

Which complies with any standard processing board or server.

Hyperledger Fabrik (Chaincode consensus)

- Disk: 10-100 GB
- RAM: 2-8 GB

Which complies with any standard processing board or server

Minimum blockchain implementation

The minimum number of nodes is defined in consideration of aka crash-fault tolerance and resilience to aka Byzantine attacks. D-MUTRA minimal blockchain implementation is made of **4 nodes** (i.e., each of which shall comply with the above stated memory requirements). With regards to the known thresholds of less than 50% of faulty nodes and less than 33% of malicious nodes for a Byzantine attacks, four nodes would tolerate 1 faulty and 1 malicious node. As the blockchain can be bastioned in controlled environment, we believe that a four node blockchain can be easily deployed and assures a sufficient security level and can of course be expanded at almost no expense.

Locality constraint. It is worth stating that no locality constraint applies on the blockchain nodes. They can be installed anywhere and separately from the workload execution platforms. To limit latency caused by communication timings, the blockchain nodes shall be “relatively” close to the execution nodes however.

14.10.3 Conclusions

Whereas TPM based remote attestation implies no significant processing and memory provisions at the verifier side, the blockchain implies a four nodes configuration to be deployed.

14.11 Runtime integrity verification penalty

To get access to the process memory blob (and verify it), the prover must share the same process ID (or, alternatively, be installed with root privilege). Each measurement induces its penalty as the it is done using shared resources with the measured process. When these measurements are made at high frequency, the global penalty can be significative. D-MUTRA collects runtime integrity verification measures, produced in a loop executed in a separate thread, which CPU resource allocation can be adjusted leveraging Linux’s cgroup command.

14.11.1 SOTA

Not applicable as the SOTA does not produce runtime integrity.

14.11.2 D-MUTRA

Our measurements are presented in Table 23. The table relates to FFT calculation with an argument (i.e., input parameter value) of 100 000. The table shows the benefit of Linux's cgroup which affects a maximum CPU resource threshold (i.e., respectively 1%, 10% and 100%) to the integrity measuring thread, executed side-by-side of the measured workload. This resource allocation is directly correlated to the quantity of measures produced by a unit of time. Fixing the resource allocation value at 1% produces a penalty of 0,1% on the verified FFT while delivers approximately 9 measures per second. We have produced tests using ContextSwitch, CPUload, Diskload, FFT, Memory load, Networkload and Syscallload) which show similar results.

A conservative method is considered with one-time on-demand integrity measurement, triggered at any time by a DevSecOps operator and limiting the performance impact to null in all situations.

TABLE 23: FFT PERFORMANCE LOSS BY RUNTIME INTEGRITY VERIFICATION

CGROUP	Time taken (us)	Penalty (%)	Total number of measures	Number of measures/sec
(no cgroup) reference value	2 970 683.52	0	0	0
1	2 973 776.73	0.10	272	9.12
10	3 011 089.40	1.36	77.8	25.87
100	3 007 000.73	1.22	82.5	27.50

14.11.3 Conclusions

To restrict the penalty on the integrity verified workload, the allocated resources of the measuring thread are adjustable. In all cases, measures produced with a frequency of one second do not induce any significant

and measurable penalty on the workload. Noticeably, we consider that getting a measure with a 1 sec freshness is sufficient to deliver continuous integrity for deployed network functions.

14.12 Final Remarks

The techno-economic analysis of remote attestation reveals that no significant investment costs are engaged. With the SOTA, remote attestation is a heavy operational question with required DevSecOps engineering and maintenance costs. D-MUTRA drastically reduces all of these costs as no check or system configuration shall be worked out when deploying it as well as there is no more requirement for continuous signature management, a risky and time sensitive operation.

As detailed above, D-MUTRA's inherent energy and memory costs, although significantly higher than with the SOTA, are still marginal and totally sustainable. A four node blockchain can be easily created and implemented where resources are available. All of these nodes will run on mid range Linux servers. A typical implementation will share these resources between the blockchain and other services. As no locality constraint applies for these blockchain nodes, they can be implemented at any available and accessible resource and typically, at the lowest costs for the operator, in its network or simply be outsourced.

As D-MUTRA continuous runtime integrity delivers an accrued security level compared to the SOTA, it reduces the exposure to attacks and service downtimes, leading to lower fines and assurances fees. It also clears the way for on-going continuous security as implicitly stated in NIS2 and reduces incident time-to-notify. Our massive tests produced on a large variety of workloads show that a measurement freshness of 1 second induces penalty below the noise in all situations. Hence, D-MUTRA will be capable to orchestrate runtime integrity verifications (of 1 second freshness) without causing a measurable penalty on the workloads.

15. OPEX reduction by IBN-based SLA assurance

15.1 Abstract

Telecommunications networks currently offer best-effort services with limited options in data quotas and speeds, while private networks provide more tailored solutions at higher costs. As 5G and 6G technologies drive new use cases, such as XR and COBOTS, the demand for more specific service criteria, especially for critical applications, is growing. This has led to the increasing importance of Service Level Agreements (SLAs), which require a clear understanding of customer needs and network capabilities. SLAs must be formalized to guarantee service levels and meet the unique requirements of emerging technologies.

This report evaluates the impact of service creation time and its implications on budgets and workforce by comparing IBN with traditional systems. The shift to intent-driven systems, where operations are based on customer requirements rather than explicit tasks, offers greater autonomy and efficiency. By automating service activation and simplifying SLA negotiation, IBN technologies can accelerate service delivery and improve customer satisfaction, ultimately leading to better customer loyalty. The report also explores how these processes will evolve with the implementation of IBN and SLA-to-intent translation mechanisms.

15.2 Description Template

TABLE 24: OPEX REDUCTION BY IBN-BASED SLA ASSURANCE STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>Evaluation and comparison of IBN (also SLA-to-Intent Translator) and non-IBN</i>
Description	<i>To assess the processing time for creation of new services when using IBN and SLA-to-Intent translation compared to non-IBN solutions. The SLA to intent translation accelerates and simplifies the SLA translation process. This</i>

	<i>study examines the impact of service activation time on customer loyalty, focusing on the advantages of rapid deployment versus current systems.</i>
Layers / Components	<i>SMO/ IBN and SLA-to-Intent Translation</i>
Benchmarking	<i>Current network service solution- without IBN and SLA-to-Intent Translation</i>
Use case	<i>Fixed Wireless Access</i>
KPI/KVI	<i>Customer Interaction time, CSR Interaction time, Network Check Time, Service Activation Time, Revenue Loss per Service. Also related with reliability, availability, and scalability. Relates with economical sustainability KVI.</i>
Methodology	<i>Gathering examples of CSP processes and their durations, then statistically or through simulation comparing them with the results of the IBN solution.</i>

15.3 Introduction

In current telecommunications networks, customers are typically offered data quotas and speeds that can reach certain thresholds, delivered on a best-effort basis without any service guarantees. Service offerings tend to be limited, with options generally constrained to variations in data quotas and access speeds. In contrast, private networks provide more tailored service options and criteria, but these come at significantly higher costs.

With the advent of 5G and the anticipated development of 6G, a broader range of use cases (such as XR, COBOTs, etc.) is expected to emerge, each introducing new service requirements. Meeting these new service requirements will necessitate more detailed service criteria, particularly for critical applications that cannot rely solely on best-effort delivery. As such, Service Level Agreements (SLAs) are increasingly becoming essential for both private and public networks.

The creation of SLAs requires an in-depth understanding of the customer's needs, aligned with the capabilities and objectives of the network. It is critical to ensure that the SLA reflects a mutual agreement between the provider and the customer. Accurately interpreting and addressing the customer's usage scenarios is fundamental. If current service offerings are insufficient, new service definitions must be created. These definitions must then be formalized in SLAs, including the guarantees of how and whether the agreed-upon service levels can be met.

Intent refers to a formal declaration of requirements derived from the specific business needs of a Communications Service Provider (CSP) and its customers. When operations are guided by intent rather than explicit tasks, the system receiving the intent is granted greater autonomy in determining how to fulfill the request. This shift to requirements-driven interaction enables a clear separation of concerns and allows for more autonomous, intelligent network behavior.

The primary objective of this work is to evaluate the impact of service creation time and its implications on budget and workforce by comparing IBN and SLA-to-Intent translation mechanisms against traditional, non-IBN systems. The study explores how these technologies can accelerate service activation, simplify SLA negotiation and creation, and ultimately enhance customer loyalty through faster and more efficient service delivery.

Upon receiving a service request, two critical steps precede actual service delivery. First, the customer's needs must be understood and either mapped to existing services or lead to the definition of a new service through negotiation. Second, both the network's capability and its current resource availability to support the requested service must be verified. In today's networks, the creation of an SLA starts with initial conversations between the customer and a representative. This is followed by technical teams evaluating network capacity and offering pricing details manually. In contrast, in a fully automated, intent-driven management system with SLA-to-intent translation, this process would operate differently. The upcoming sections will outline the steps involved in SLA creation and service activation for both public and private network contexts. Furthermore, we will analyze how these processes are expected to change in the future with the solution we propose.

15.4 FWA Use Case Scenario for the Public Users

A FWA scenario in the current public network is analyzed as a use case, with study results presented as statistically replicated average values under realistic conditions. Figure 63 illustrates the service request process for FWA using a flow chart, and each step will be explained sequentially:

FIGURE 63: FLOWCHART OF THE SERVICE ORDER PROCESS IN THE TRADITIONAL NETWORK

To handle service requests from customers, resellers of CSPs are engaged, with Customer Service Representatives (CSRs) stationed at these resellers to interact directly with customers. The customer typically visits a representative in person, explains their service needs, and completes a form, after which they are informed that a response will follow. The form captures various parameters, including the customer's address, geographic coordinates, and desired service speed and quota.

As the number and variety of these parameters increase over time, the process becomes more complex. Currently, the entire workflow is handled manually. From the customer's perspective, the process—including travel and communication—takes approximately 30 minutes to 3 hours, while for the CSR, it typically takes 5 to 15 minutes to process the request.

This service model is in use both in less urbanized areas and in regions with strong infrastructure investments. As the service continues to expand, a corresponding increase in workload is anticipated. On average, between 350,000 and 400,000 new subscribers are added annually.

A dedicated FWA team is responsible for handling customer requests at the CSP. To assess feasibility, the team evaluates data speed availability at the customer's location using geographic coordinates, as well as the capacity and coverage of nearby base stations. Capacity checks are based on existing subscriber numbers. In capacity planning, a 70% threshold is applied for transmission and other resources, while 80% utilization is examined to assess the need for potential upgrades.

If coverage is deemed sufficient, the team checks whether the service request can be fulfilled. If not, an investment and return analysis is performed, followed by a cost assessment. If the investment is not feasible, the customer is politely informed that the request cannot be met.

This process typically takes about one week, requiring approximately 3 to 5 hours of a technical expert's time. During this evaluation, tools are used to assess network resources and capacity, estimate coverage, and analyze annual usage trends. The entire workflow is manual and conducted by domain specialists. When handling multiple requests, the overall process time can double.

If the service can be provided and all conditions are met, the CSR is contacted by phone to initiate service delivery, and the customer is requested to sign a contract. The customer then visits the dealer in person to sign the agreement.

The following key variables were considered in this analysis:

- **Customer and CSR Interaction Time:** Time spent by customer and CSR in understanding customer needs and processing requests.
- **Network Check and Capacity Analysis Time:** Time spent by technical teams to ensure that network capacity meets customer demand.
- **Service Activation Time:** Time taken for service in use from the customer request to activation.
- **Revenue Loss from Delayed Activation:** The revenue loss for operators due to delayed activation of services (calculated based on average subscription rates and service delays).

The required durations for the process steps, the time spent on service activation, and the service losses are presented in a tabular format in Table 25. All reported times, prices, and user counts are country-specific and may vary depending on local conditions and market dynamics. The key data points and averages derived from the study are as follows:

The average service activation time in traditional systems ranges from 10 to 15 days. This timeline includes various stages such as manual customer interactions (0.5–3 hours), network capacity and coverage check (3–5 hours), and SLA negotiations and approvals (up to 15 days). As a result of these delays, the average revenue loss per service activation is estimated between €10 and €56.

The total time for activation could be formulated as in the Equation 1. The customer interaction time and CSR interaction time are dependent of different factors. Specifically, when the CSR demonstrates a high level of familiarity with service features and operates under low workload conditions, the duration of the overall interaction is expected to decrease. Conversely, customer interaction time is influenced by external factors such as the physical distance between the customer and the service point (e.g., dealership), as well as the workload and congestion at the service location. These factors introduce variability into the interaction process and must be accounted for in any accurate time estimation model. Synchronization Time is the duration from the CSR submitting the request through

TABLE 25: KEY VARIABLES FOR ANALYSIS

Process Steps	Values	The reason for the variation
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Customer Interaction Time	0.5 - 3 (hour)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visit the dealer • Waiting time to talk CSR • interaction time with CSR
CSR Interaction Time	0.083- 0.25 (hour)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the customer's need, • Directing additional information via a form, • Entering the customer's data and request into the system.
Network Check Time	3-5 (hour)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coverage checks (manual or script) • Capacity and speed check (manual or script) • General KPI check from past to future (manual or script)
Service Activation Time	10-15 (day)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration of customer, CSR, and technical staff coordination and alignment • Send the box to the customer
Revenue Loss per Service	10-56 (Euro) (per service)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on the FWA quota, the average cost ranges between €30 and €112 per month. Considering a request-to-activation period of minimum 10 days and maximum 15 days, the average service loss cost per service can be estimated accordingly.

the system to the point when it appears in the network expert's task list and is taken up for evaluation. This duration typically depends on the number of network experts, their workload, and the volume of service requests. However, it is generally estimated to range between one week and ten days. The Network Check Time is executed by the technical staff and is typically carried out as a batch process on designated days of the week. Product Delivery Time is after the service feasibility decision until the physical equipment reaches the customer.

Equation 1

$$\text{Service Activation Time} = \text{CSR} - \text{Customer Interaction Time} + \text{Synchronization Time} + \text{Network Check Time} + \text{Product Delivery Time}$$

The revenue loss is impacted by the service activation time, we can model it using a function that maps activation time to revenue loss as in the Equation 2.

Equation 2

$$\text{Revenue Loss} = f(\text{Service Activation Time})$$

To estimate key operational metrics for customer service processes, we can model the relevant time and cost variables using a normal distribution. This approach assumes that the values are symmetrically distributed around a central mean, with a certain level of variability. For example, the customer interaction time can be modeled as a normal distribution with a mean (μ) between 0.5 and 3 hours, the CSR interaction time follows a normal distribution with a mean between 0.083 and 0.25 hours, and the network check time is normally distributed between 3 and 5 hours. Similarly, the service activation time can be modeled as a normal distribution with a mean between 10 and 15 days, while revenue loss per service follows a normal distribution between €10 and €56, accounting for service delays. In Figure 64, the average expected values of the key metrics are presented based on a scenario involving 300,000 users generated using a normal distribution.

FIGURE 64: ANALYSIS OF AVERAGE TIME CONSUMPTION, SERVICE ACTIV., REVENUE LOSS

Based on these values in the Figure 64, considering an annual addition of 300,000 new subscribers, the total revenue loss due to activation delays is estimated to €9 million, depending on exchange rates and service plans. The high variability in service activation time particularly for network evaluations, customer service coordination, and SLA discussions is largely attributed to the manual nature of the process and the complexity of customer-specific negotiations. Furthermore, service delivery time is significantly affected by network coverage variability and individual customer requirements, emphasizing the urgent need for automated, intelligent, and streamlined service activation solutions.

15.5 SLA to Intent Translation and IBN Solution

The SLA-to-Intent translation solution automates both the negotiation process between the customer and the customer representative and the collection and definition of service criteria. It also streamlines the transfer of service and customer-related information from the business to the technical domain, enabling seamless creation and digitization of SLAs.

In parallel, the ability to receive a customer service request or intent in a machine-readable format significantly accelerates automation and reduces response time. With IBN, key tasks such as service provisioning, coverage checks, and Service Level Objective (SLO) compliance assessments by the technical team can be automated. Furthermore, automated control checks enabled by IBN optimize the validation process within the network domain, allowing service feasibility assessments to be performed efficiently and autonomously.

Table 26 highlights the specific stages in the service lifecycle where automation has been implemented, effectively eliminating the "human-in-the-loop" approach. These steps now involve automated interactions between the customer and the network, enabled by AI/ML-based solutions. As illustrated in Table 2, the time from service request to delivery excluding the physical deployment of equipment has been significantly reduced. Tasks that previously required several man-hours can now be completed in just minutes. In effect, entire workflows that once spanned multiple days are now executable within a few hours.

In this context, the service activation time refers to the total duration encompassing several stages: the interaction between the customer and the SLA-to-Intent translator, the system's verification of service availability, the network validation process, the notification of sub-domains regarding the customer and

service details, and finally, the delivery of physical equipment. The duration of interaction between the customer and the SLA-to-Intent translator

TABLE 26: KEY VARIABLES FOR ANALYSIS FOR AUTOMATED SOLUTION

Process Steps	Values	Automated By	The reason for the variation
SLA-to-Intent translation = Customer Interaction time + CSR Interaction time	3-10 min	The steps automated by SLA-to-Intent Translation are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UI interaction interface • Interaction with customer and understanding requirement • Mapping the customer requirement to service specification and the current services • Translation of service requirement to network language (intent) and informing management domain 	Variation due to chat interaction delays, user typing speed, and iteration count
Network Check	2-10 min	The steps automated by IBN are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding related service specification and base information • Checks geo location and subscriber rights • Capacity and speed check (with OE) 	Depends on catalog response, optimization engine, and service type (new/current)
Service Activation Time	1-2 days	The steps automated by IBN are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform service management domain for service and customer information • Service activation and network configuration Still there is product delivery step in physically and manually	Delivery coordination and shipping delays for customer equipment

Revenue Lost	2-7.5 Euro		Driven by length of service activation delay and pricing tier
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is based on average simulation results, although edge cases may occur. The time required for IBN to validate the service, receive a response from the Optimization Engine, and relay the provisioning decision to lower layers is also based on average values obtained through simulation. Lastly, the time needed to deliver the physical equipment to the customer—or for the customer to pick it up—is included as an estimated average duration.

Figure 65 shows the average values of samples generated using normal distribution for processing time steps and service activation durations for 300,000 users. The service request and control processing times, which used to take hours, have been reduced to minutes. By automating the workload on the CSP, the service activation time has been shortened, thereby preventing revenue loss. This acceleration of service processes empowers CSPs to deliver services more rapidly and efficiently. Given the scale of the subscriber base, the time savings achieved through automation translate directly into substantial revenue gains for the CSP.

FIGURE 65: AVERAGE TIME CONSUMPTION, SERVICE ACTIVATION, AND REVENUE LOSS RESULTS WITH DESIRE6G SOLUTION

15.6 Enterprise Private Networks as an Additional Use Case

While the previous section focused on FWA with concrete figures and automation comparisons, it is important to note that other use cases, such as enterprise private networks, also present unique challenges and opportunities. These deployments often involve a wide range of specific requirements—sometimes covering 10 or more use cases per enterprise—which significantly increase complexity and negotiation timelines. Understanding the customer’s requirements, translating them into the technical domain, and communicating the potential value to the customer can take 3 to 4 weeks. The subsequent planning and solution development phases also tend to be lengthy processes.

15.7 Conclusions

This deliverable has evaluated the impact of automating service request handling and activation processes through the integration of IBN and SLA-to-Intent translation. By comparing traditional manual workflows with the proposed automated approach, we have quantified the benefits in terms of time reduction, operational efficiency, and revenue preservation.

In the current operational model, service activation timelines average between 10 to 15 days, driven by manual interactions between customers, customer service representatives (CSRs), and technical teams. This delay contributes to an average revenue loss of €10–56 per service activation, amounting to an estimated €9 million annually for a subscriber base of 300,000 new users.

The proposed automated framework—leveraging IBN and SLA-to-Intent translation—reduces customer interaction and network evaluation time from hours to minutes and shortens overall service activation to 1–2 days. Consequently, average revenue loss per delayed activation is reduced to €2–7.5, representing a substantial financial improvement.

Moreover, the solution streamlines SLA creation, eliminates redundant manual tasks, and enhances the scalability of service delivery operations, positioning CSPs to meet the growing demand for personalized, SLA-driven services across both public and enterprise network scenarios.

In conclusion, the findings of this report demonstrate that automation—particularly through IBN and SLA-to-Intent translation—can significantly improve CSP service agility, customer satisfaction, and overall

profitability. These results strongly support continued development and deployment of automated service management capabilities within future network architectures.

16. ML-assisted configuration for RIS

16.1 Abstract

This study evaluates the trade-offs between NN-assisted phase configuration methods and traditional optimization-based algorithms for RISs. Two NN approaches are considered: the first, referred to as NN-no-Het, is a classic feedforward NN without specific mechanisms to handle local data heterogeneity; the second, NN-with-Het, incorporates mechanisms to mitigate training deficiencies arising from heterogeneous datasets, as outlined in [section 5.1 D3.1], [21]. For benchmarking, an effective state-of-the-art optimization-based algorithm from [22] is considered, which is referred to as OBA.

The comparison primarily focuses on RIS configuration latency and the corresponding achievable data rates for users in both familiar (seen) and unfamiliar (unseen) environments. Results show that OBA can incur RIS configuration latencies even exceeding 1 second, while both NN-based methods achieve worst-case latencies below 8 milliseconds. This advantage is further emphasised in batch processing scenarios due to the parallel inference capabilities of NNs. However, these computational gains come at the cost of reduced data rates. In particular, NN-no-Het achieves data rates comparable to OBA in seen environments but suffers significant degradation in unseen scenarios. Conversely, NN-with-Het provides more consistent performance across both seen and unseen environments, albeit with slightly lower rates compared to OBA. Moreover, the performance of NN-with-Het can be enhanced by increasing dataset resolution, which introduces additional training overhead and an increase of the size of the NNs but leads to improved generalization and robustness.

16.2 Description Template

TABLE 27: ML-ASSISTED CONFIGURATION FOR RIS STUDY

Field	Value
Name	<i>Comparing and contrasting ML-assisted RIS configuration with optimization-based algorithms</i>

Description	<i>ML-assisted configuration RISs with traditional optimization-based algorithms are compared, in term of computation latencies, accuracy of data rate, and scalability with users.</i>
Layers / Components	<i>Physical Infrastructure Layer</i>
Benchmarking	<i>State-of-the-art Optimization based algorithms</i>
Use case	<i>ML Assisted RIS Configuration Based on FL (PoC)</i>
KPI/KVI	<i>Related with bandwidth, latency, and scalability. Impacts on economical sustainability KVI.</i>
Methodology	<i>Benchmark OBA algorithm is from [22], NN-with-Het model from [21], NN-no-Het from classic NN models, simulations are performed in Python, NNs are trained based on locally generated datasets [23].</i>

16.3 Experimental Setup

FIGURE 66: DOWNLINK RIS-ENABLED COMMUNICATION NETWORK.

We have considered a downlink RIS enabled communication network setup as shown in Figure 66. As shown in the figure, there are different RIS environments within the communication network. In our empirical setting, we considered three environments, namely Environment 1, 2, and 3. Empirical channel measurements CSI \mathbf{h} and CSI \mathbf{g} in each environment used for numerical evaluations in this section are obtained from the dataset as detailed in Section 4.3, i.e., CSI \mathbf{h}^r and CSI \mathbf{g}^r pairs for $r = 1, 2$, and 3. Given CSI \mathbf{h} , and CSI \mathbf{g} , the corresponding RIS configuration is to be computed. By using the RIS configuration the users' data rate is computed based on the commonly used Shannon's rate formula. In addition to the data rate, the computation time for RIS configuration is also of key interest since the latency requirements associated with decision making also play a key role when evaluating the performance of future wireless communication networks.

When computing RIS configurations, we rely on three methods. The first one is an optimization-based algorithm and the other two are NN-assisted methods as outlined below.

- Optimization-based algorithm (OBA) [22]: This algorithm is a block coordinate descent (BCD)-based method that obtains a stationary solution to the RIS configuration problem. The algorithm offers significantly reduced computational complexity compared to conventional optimization methods. Given the channel state information CSI \mathbf{h} and CSI \mathbf{g} , OBA computes a RIS configurations θ and the corresponding data rate R .
- NN-assisted method 1 (NN-no-Het): In this case, we consider a NN based on a commonly used feedforward NN architecture. The NN is trained based on RIS configurations θ obtained by OBA. More specifically, we consider the labeled training examples of the form $\{\mathbf{h}^r, \mathbf{g}^r, \theta^r\}$ for environments 1 and 2, (i.e., $r = 1, 2$) when training NN-no-Het. It is worth noting that the NN-no-Het is not designed to handle any heterogeneity in the data sets.
- NN-assisted method 2 (NN-with-Het) [21]: The NN considered in this case is capable of handling heterogeneity of datasets and is thus generalized to unseen environments. The NN-with-Het is trained based on the dataset detailed in Table 6, for environments 1 and 2, (i.e., $r = 1, 2$). It is worth pointing out that for each quantization index N (see Table 6), one can train an NN-with-Het NN. In our empirical results we have considered cases for $N = 2$ to $N = 10$.

16.4 Comparing OBA versus NN-no-Het

This section compares the optimization-based algorithm (OBA) and the conventional NN model NN-no-Het, focusing on both the computational efficiency for RIS configuration and the achieved data rates. The impact of deploying NN-no-Het in unfamiliar (unseen) environments is also empirically analyzed to get insight into generalization performance of NN-no-Het.

16.4.1 Computation time for RIS Configuration

FIGURE 67: CDF OF TIME FOR RIS CONFIGURATION: OBA (LEFT), NN-NO-HET (RIGHT).

Figure 67 presents the empirical cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the inference time per sample. As shown in Figure 67 (left), for all channel realizations considered, the RIS configuration time using OBA consistently exceeds 100 milliseconds. Additionally, in approximately 50% of the cases, OBA's inference time surpasses 250 milliseconds, which is unfavorable from a latency perspective, given that typical channel coherence times are significantly shorter than such delays. In extreme scenarios, the configuration latency with OBA can even reach several seconds. In contrast, as depicted in Figure 67 (right), the inference time of the NN-no-Het approach remains almost always below 0.25 milliseconds. These results highlight the suitability of NN-based methods for latency-critical applications, where rapid RIS configuration decision-making is essential.

16.4.2 Data Rates Associated with RIS Configurations

Figure 68 depicts the CDF of the relative data rate deviation ΔR computed according to

$$\Delta R = (R_{OBA} - R_{NN-no-Het})/R_{OBA},$$

where R_{OBA} and $R_{NN-no-Het}$ are the data rates obtained by using the optimized and inferred RIS configurations from OBA and NN-no-Het, respectively. Results demonstrate that, for seen environments (i.e., Environment 1 and 2), the data rates resulting from NN-inferred RIS configurations closely match

those obtained through OBA. For about 90% of the evaluated test cases, the NN achieves at least 90% of the data rate of OBA. Additionally, in roughly 2% of the cases, the NN even outperforms OBA. These outcomes indicate that NN-based methods can offer RIS configurations with performance on par with optimization approaches, while delivering a computational advantage of several thousand times faster (see Figure 67) when applied in familiar environments. However, in unseen environments (i.e., Environment 3), the data rates resulting from NN-no-Het inferred RIS configurations are considerably lower compared to those obtained with OBA. Specifically, the results reveal that nearly all NN-no-Het configurations fail to reach even 50% of the data rates achieved by OBA. This highlights the inability of NN-no-Het to generalize effectively to scenarios not represented in its training data. In other words, although NN-no-Het offers notable computational advantages for RIS configuration, the resulting data rates in unseen environments are significantly degraded, indicating it is inadequate for scenarios beyond its training environments.

FIGURE 68: CDF OF RELATIVE DATA RATE DEVIATION ΔR .

It is important to note that NN-no-Het lacks architectural provisions to address dataset heterogeneity, unlike NN-with-Het, which is explicitly designed to handle such variability. Consequently, the degraded data rate performance of NN-no-Het in unseen environments is an expected outcome.

16.5 Comparing OBA versus NN-with-Het

This section presents a comparative empirical analysis between OBA and the NN model NN-with-Het, emphasizing their respective computational efficiencies for RIS configuration and the resulting data rates. Additionally, the study evaluates the performance of NN-with-Het in previously unseen environments to assess its generalization capability.

16.5.1 Computation time for RIS Configuration

Figure 69 shows the CDF of inference time per sample of NN-with-Het type NNs under four quantization index settings $N = 2$, $N = 4$, $N = 6$, and $N = 10$. As previously discussed, the quantization index N denotes the number of representative RIS configuration points that has one-to-one correspondence to the labels used during NN training. The main reason for such a finitely labelled dataset has been dictated by the provisions for addressing the data set heterogeneity in the design of NN-with-Het [21]. Clearly, based on the NN architecture considered in [21], increasing the quantization index N directly results in a larger NN output layer and consequently increases the overall NN size.

FIGURE 69: CDF OF TIME FOR RIS CONFIGURATION OF NN-WITH-HET FOR $N = 2$, $N = 4$, $N = 6$, AND $N = 10$.

The increase in the number of NN parameters relative to the quantization index N is outlined in Table 28, where m is the number of nodes of the preceding hidden layer and P is the number of parameters between input and the preceding hidden layer, which is fixed for all the NNs. Of course, the change in general is $P + N(m + 1)$.

TABLE 28: CHANGE IN NN PARAMETERS RELATIVE TO QUANTIZATION INDEX.

N	Nodes in the last layer	Number of parameters
2	2	$P + 2(m+1)$
4	4	$P + 4(m+1)$
6	6	$P + 6(m+1)$
10	10	$P + 10(m+1)$

Although the size of the NN-with-Het model increases with higher quantization index N , the CDF plots in Figure 69 indicate that the inference time remains relatively stable, varying from approximately 6.5 ms in the best case to around 7.8 ms in the worst case. Furthermore, the results demonstrate that, when

compared to the inference time of the optimization-based algorithm OBA shown in Figure 67, left, NN-with-Het achieves a computational speed-up of several orders of magnitude. This highlights the significant computational efficiency of NN-with-Het for RIS configuration, making it a suitable candidate for latency-sensitive scenarios, similar to NN-no-Het. However, it is noted that the inference time of NN-with-Het is marginally higher than that of NN-no-Het (Figure 67, right). This is attributed to the fact that NN-with-Het employs a more complex network architecture specifically designed to manage dataset heterogeneity, unlike the simpler feedforward NN architecture used in NN-no-Het.

16.5.2 Data Rates Associated with RIS Configuration

FIGURE 70: CDF OF RELATIVE DATA RATE DEVIATION ΔR : $N = 2$, $N = 4$, $N = 6$, AND $N = 10$.

Figure 70 shows the CDF plots of the relative data rate deviation ΔR computed according to

$$\Delta R = (R_{OBA} - R_{NN-with-Het})/R_{OBA},$$

where R_{OBA} and $R_{NN-with-Het}$ are the data rates obtained by using the optimized and inferred RIS configurations from OBA and NN-with-Het, respectively. Each subfigure corresponds to a specific

quantization index, namely $N = 2$, $N = 4$, $N = 6$, and $N = 10$. The respective number of NN parameters for these cases is detailed in Table 28.

We first examine the top-left subfigure, which presents the data rate deviation between OBA and NN-with-Het for the case of $N = 2$. The results show that the curves corresponding to seen and unseen environments exhibit a comparable behavior, unlike the more significant discrepancies observed between these scenarios in Figure 68. This comparable behavior between seen and unseen scenarios remains across different quantization index values, as shown in the remaining subfigures of Figure 70. This empirical evidence confirm that NN-with-Het models exhibit superior generalization capability in unseen environments compared to NN-no-Het models.

The results further reveal that increasing the quantization index N leads to improved relative data rate deviations in both seen and unseen scenarios. Specifically, the proportion of cases where the relative data rate deviation with respect to OBA is within 0.5 increases from approximately 50% to 80% in the unseen scenario, and from 50% to 65% in the seen scenario when N is changed from 2 (see Figure 70, top-left) to 10 (see Figure 70, bottom-right). These findings indicate that enhancing the quantization index N can lead to better data rate performance, albeit at the cost of a larger NN model size, as detailed in Table 28.

16.6 Users' scalability with NN-with-Het and NN-no-Het

FIGURE 71: AVERAGE INFERENCE TIME UNDER BATCH PROCESSING.

Figure 71 depicts the average inference time versus input batch size for channel samples for NN-with-Het (with $N = 2$) and NN-no-Het models. The selection of $N = 2$ is arbitrary, as numerical experience

suggests that results remain consistent for N values ranging from 3 to 10, as previously shown in Figure 69. The slightly higher inference time of NN-with-Het is attributed to its more complex architecture designed to handle dataset heterogeneity, unlike the simpler NN-no-Het. Nevertheless, both networks maintain low average inference latencies, staying within 10 ms even with batch sizes up to 1000. For larger batches, such as 6000 samples, inference time remains below a couple of tens of milliseconds. This efficiency is a direct result of the parallelizable nature of matrix and tensor operations in NN computations. Consequently, such computational gains highlight the suitability of NN-assisted RIS configuration in multi-user wireless networks, offering a scalable solution for latency-sensitive applications where optimization-based methods like OBA would face significant delays.

16.7 Conclusions

This study presents an empirical evaluation of the trade-offs between state-of-the-art optimization-based methods and NN-based approaches for computing RIS configurations in a RIS-enabled wireless downlink. The comparison focuses on key aspects including online RIS configuration latency, achievable data rates, robustness to dataset heterogeneity, and scalability in multi-user scenarios through batch processing. A consolidated overview is provided in Table 29, summarizing the characteristics of the considered methods. In particular, OBA is a representative optimization-based algorithm [22], NN-no-Het is a conventional feedforward NN lacking provisions for dataset heterogeneity, and NN-with-Het is a proposed architecture designed to mitigate heterogeneity effects [21], [section 5.1, D3.1]. The performance of each method across the selected attributes is categorized using a three-tier classification scale: ‘limited’, ‘satisfactory’, and ‘favorable’.

TABLE 29: SUMMARY OF ASSOCIATED TRADE-OFFS.

	Online RIS configuration latency	Data rates in seen environments	Data rates in unseen environments	Robustness for dataset heterogeneity	Scalability in multiuser scenarios
OBA	limited	favorable	favorable	favorable	limited
NN-no-Het	favorable	favorable	limited	limited	favorable
NN-with-Het	favorable	satisfactory	satisfactory	favorable	favorable

Extensive empirical analysis confirms that NN-based approaches offer substantial computational advantages for online RIS configuration, achieving speed gains of several orders of magnitude over optimization-based algorithms (e.g., OBA). Consequently, for latency-critical applications demanding

rapid configuration updates, NN-assisted RIS configuration is highly recommended. In scenarios where generalization to unseen environments is not a priority, a simple feedforward NN architecture (e.g., NN-no-Het), trained on carefully curated datasets using effective heuristics such as OBA, can deliver not only rapid inference times but also high data rate performance. However, the efficacy of such models deteriorates in previously unseen environments due to their limited generalization capabilities. In these cases, specialized architectures like NN-with-Het, explicitly designed to handle dataset heterogeneity, become essential to ensure reliable RIS configuration performance across diverse conditions. Furthermore, increasing the quantization resolution of training labels has been shown to enhance data rate performance, albeit with increased model complexity and parameter count. It is also suggested that alternative methods beyond finitely labelled datasets should be explored to further improve NN generalization. Lastly, NN-based approaches inherently support scalable multi-user deployments through efficient batch processing, making them particularly suitable for future wireless network edges tasked with serving thousands of users under stringent latency constraints.

17. Concluding Remarks

This deliverable has presented a comprehensive view of both the dataset framework, and the techno-economic evaluations developed within the DESIRE6G project. The outcomes support the project's overarching goal of enabling intelligent, cost-efficient, and high-performance 6G networks.

Chapters 2 to 4 established a structured methodology for identifying and describing datasets relevant to DESIRE6G services and components. Two methodologies were applied: i) UC-oriented, focusing on service-specific data needs, and ii) Component-oriented, focusing on functional blocks used across multiple use cases.

The following datasets were defined and characterized:

- **Augmented Reality / Virtual Reality (AR/VR)** – data from UAVs, cameras, and headset interactions, including positioning, video streams, and telemetry.
- **Digital Twin (DT)** – sensor data from robots, including video, LiDAR, IMU, and control commands.
- **ML-Based Elastic Scaling** – synthetic vehicle arrival datasets at edge PoPs based on real traffic traces.
- **ML-Based SLA Decomposition** – historical admission control feedback data and SLA requests for training neural risk models.
- **ML-assisted RIS Configuration** – complex channel state information and RIS configuration indices for NN training.
- **Payload Performance Self-Monitoring** – time series metrics on control flow frequency and execution time for workload self-instrumentation.
- **Payload Remote Attestation & Integrity Verification** – cryptographic hashes and runtime measurements supporting blockchain-based attestation.

These datasets serve as the foundation for evaluating service behavior, orchestration strategies, and functional components in 6G environments.

Moreover, the following techno-economic studies have been carried out:

- **DESIRE6G Service Characterization:** This study classified key 6G use cases and compared manual (human-based) and AI-based service classification methods. AI-based approaches provided interesting and relevant results, highlighting their suitability for future service

characterization and management, which can help operators to reduce costs and increase revenues by offering precise solutions to serve such challenging demands. However, it still shows some weaknesses and inconsistencies that require eventual human supervision to decide whether the analysis is valid or not.

- **Efficient Resource Utilization:** focused on strategies for optimizing resource allocation. The study demonstrated that DESIRE6G allows a greater resource efficiency leading to remarkable cost savings in terms of CAPEX and OPEX, as well as increasing potential revenues by reducing associated per user cost. This has been validated for scenarios mixing current with envisioned DESIRE6G services and use cases.
- **Enhanced Heavy-Hitter Offload Functionality:** assessed the impact of offloading large flows to programmable data planes. Results showed significant energy savings (in the range of 55-75%) and improved system operation by means of HW-accelerated nodes. In addition to OPEX savings, expected revenues increase from efficient and dynamic HW-based NF DP management justifies the required CAPEX investment.
- **Capacity Savings with Network-Wide Hierarchical QoS:** quantified bandwidth and capacity benefits from implementing hierarchical QoS policies. Findings showed up to 30% better bandwidth distribution and improved service delivery under congestion.
- **Energy Savings from AI Model Acceleration:** the SOL server has been used for the acceleration of NN. Compared to existing NN execution frameworks like Pytorch, SOL produces consistent power consumption decrease for a wide set of different reference NN models, during both training and inference phases.
- **OPEX Reduction via MAS Operation:** demonstrated the use of MAS for autonomous routing decisions. The MAS approach led to reduced power consumption (15-30%) and improved adaptability in both aggregation and core segments.
- **Application Remote Attestation and Runtime Integrity Verification:** evaluated the feasibility and cost of blockchain-based runtime attestation (D-MUTRA). D-MUTRA drastically reduces operational costs as no check or system configuration shall be worked out when deploying it as well as there is no more requirement for continuous signature management, a risky and time sensitive operation. Continuous runtime integrity delivers an accrued security level compared to

the SOTA, it reduces the exposure to attacks and service downtimes, leading to lower fines and fees.

- **OPEX Reduction by IBN-Based SLA Assurance:** applied IBN to streamline SLA showed improvements in provisioning time and a reduction in revenue loss, i.e., reduces customer interaction and network evaluation time from hours to minutes and shortens overall service activation to 1-2 days. IBN and SLA-to-Intent translation–can significantly improve CSP service agility, customer satisfaction, and overall profitability. These results strongly support continued development and deployment of automated service management capabilities within future network architectures.
- **ML-Assisted Configuration for RIS:** explored the use of NN to optimize the configuration of RIS. Federated learning approaches achieved lower latency and stable data rate performance, particularly under heterogeneous conditions, which is crucial for reaching desired AI-based operation of foreseen extreme and massive latency-critical applications.

Table 30 summarizes each of the aforementioned studies in terms of: i) DESIRE6G KPIs and KVs described in D2.1 [8], as well as specific KPIs identified in the project proposal; ii) benchmarking scenarios and technologies used for evaluating DESIRE6G innovations, and iii) summary of results and expected trends. Note that the combination of part or all the technologies and strategies covered by the studies will bring large overall, global savings in terms of CAPEX (more efficient use of resources), OPEX (low maintenance and manual intervention actions, energy consumption reduction) as well as increased revenues and incomes (reduced latency, increased reliability and availability, enhanced security and trustworthiness).

TABLE 30: TECHNO-ECONOMIC STUDIES SUMMARY

Study	KPIs / KVs	Benchmark	Results
Characterization of DESIRE6G services	Bandwidth, Latency, Reliability <i>Economical sustainability</i>	4G/5G services and current traffic scenarios.	Human + AI-based service analysis is envisioned for accurate service characterization and efficient management of DESIRE6G networks.

Network resource utilization and cost analysis	Bandwidth <i>Economical sustainability</i>	5G SA operation on current operator infrastructures.	DESIRE6G enables much more efficient and scalable use of capacity resources. CAPEX and OPEX savings are shown from such efficient resource usage. Cost-per-user is reduced up to 85% w.r.t. benchmarking.
Enhanced heavy-hitter offload functionality	Latency (also related with KPI 4.2) <i>Environmental sustainability</i>	Current network infrastructure without HW acceleration resources	Energy savings in the range of 55-75%. Lower processing latency motivates increased revenues that can compensate CAPEX investment.
Capacity savings with NHQoS	Bandwidth (also related with KPI 5.8) <i>Economical sustainability</i>	Static, link-based QoS rules (LHQoS)	NHQoS results in larger throughput allocation than LHQoS (overprovisioning reduced in 33%) Throughput share between operators, slices and users is kept close to the desired policy.
Energy savings from AI Model Acceleration	Latency (also related KPI 3.4 and 3.5) <i>Environmental sustainability</i>	Current NN execution frameworks	Relative energy consumption savings by using SOL server for NN acceleration (baseline consumes up to three times more). Latency savings derived from AI model acceleration will impact on increased service revenues.
OPEX reduction by service MAS operation	Latency, Scalability (also related with KPI 3.1) <i>Environmental sustainability</i>	Static 5G SA operation on current infrastructures	MAS for near-real time operation allows reducing energy consumption, achieving sustained switch power in the range 15%-30%. Energy efficiency is doubled w. r. t. static operation, which clearly reduces OPEX.

Assessment of application remote attestation and runtime integrity verification of software payloads	Reliability, Availability <i>Trust</i>	Network infrastructure providing TPM for remote attestation.	The use of D-MUTRA (DESIRE6G innovation) reduces OPEX costs such as energy, memory use, and maintenance. D-MUTRA will be capable to orchestrate runtime integrity verifications (of 1 second freshness) without causing a measurable penalty on the workloads.
OPEX reduction by IBN-based SLA assurance	Reliability, Availability, Scalability <i>Economical sustainability</i>	Manual network operation workflows for service lifetime management	By adopting IBN and SLA-to-intent translation, customer interaction and network evaluation time reduces from hours to minutes and shortens overall service activation. Expected revenue loss per delayed activation is reduced to €2-7.5, representing a substantial financial improvement.
ML-assisted configuration for RIS	Bandwidth, Latency, Scalability <i>Economical sustainability</i>	State-of-the-art optimization algorithms	NN-based approaches achieve speed gains of several orders of magnitude, which is crucial for latency-critical applications. NN-assisted RIS configuration is highly recommended for reliability across heterogeneous and diverse conditions, providing scalable multi-user deployments with thousands of users under stringent latency constraints.

In conclusion, the work presented in this deliverable contributes significantly to the vision of a smarter, more sustainable DESIRE6G ecosystem. The dataset methodologies provide a scalable and consistent approach to defining data collection needs across varied services and components. This enables more effective testing, validation, and performance analysis. The techno-economic studies confirm that

DESIRE6G technologies and innovations can offer tangible benefits in terms of cost, energy efficiency, and service quality. Overall, D2.3 shows that DESIRE6G's proposed innovations are not only technically feasible but also economically advantageous, laying a strong foundation for future implementation, experimentation, and standardization efforts.

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